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*Exploring Quaternions
and
their
Natural Structure*

Master's Thesis in Mathematics
by
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Introduction

It is commonly said, that when Hamilton discovered Quaternions in 1843, he was convinced that his finding was going to revolutionize Mathematical Physics. In spite of this belief -which led him to spend the rest of his life working on it- as well as the enthusiasm and effort of several Mathematicians -even a *Quaternion Society* was founded- it "*seems that Quaternions quickly turned out to be quite disappointing*", and were then neglected in favour of *Vector Analysis*... In my experience, when talking with a few Mathematicians and Physicists, it even appeared to me that some of them would believe Quaternions to be *completely useless*... ..But is it really the case ?... Well, I would suggest that there seems to be many hints of the opposite... For instance, it may be good to remind that, ironically, it is the Theory of Quaternions that gave birth to Vector Analysis -and other theories that "*killed Quaternions*"- and that are nowadays used everywhere in areas such as Engineering or Physics (for example, Dot and Cross products, as well as Divergence and Curl directly arise from Quaternions, and appear literally everywhere in Physics, so in some point of view, it could be suggested that Quaternions should "implicitly" be "omnipresent" in Physics). Also, taking a step back and continuing the Chronology -started with Hamilton's Discovery- it should be mentioned that in 1877, Frobenius proved that there were only three finite-dimensional (associative) Division Algebras over the field of Real Numbers (namely $\mathbb{R} \subseteq \mathbb{C} \subseteq \mathbb{H}$), the most general of which being Quaternions, which is also the only one not to be commutative, i.e. it is in some sense a *completely Unique Mathematical Structure*, that is *impossible to generalize*¹ (at least without losing key properties such as associativity). This result was then improved by the Russian Mathematician Lev Pontrya-

¹Here I mean "generalize/extend in a naive way", in the sense that, for instance, unlike vector spaces, for which it is usually possible to simply "add dimensions" (while keeping the same Algebraic and Topological properties), such a phenomenon does not occur with Quaternions. However, many interesting -and more abstract- ways to "generalize" Quaternions have been suggested, such as the concept of "Quaternion Algebras" that can for instance be used in areas such as Number Theory...

gin², who, despite his blindness³ was able to make major contributions in fields such as Algebraic and Differential Topology. In 1932, Pontryagin then showed that the *Frobenius Theorem* could actually be adapted to Connected Locally Compact Division Rings. As a result, Quaternions turn out to be *The Most General Connected Locally Compact Division Ring* (with a non-trivial Topology, of course), and also the only one not to be commutative. Meanwhile, a Four-Dimensional Physical Theory, namely Special Relativity, was developed independently, and I admit I still fail to understand why Quaternions do not seem to have been given more attention, as besides being four-dimensional, they also -at first glance- exhibit many features⁴ that can immediately be related to Special Relativity. Actually, it seems that several attempts have been made to formulate Relativity by including Quaternions (it is for instance well-known that the Lorentz Group can be expressed in a very simple way in terms of Biquaternions) but most of those seem -a priori- to have failed to match the expectations that such a reformulation should significantly simplify the theory, or at least *potentially bring something new*. Should I give my opinion, I would be tempted to say that my impression is, that many people, in their enthusiasm, would tend to be a bit too *hasty*, and thus try to *directly include Quaternions in the standard theory*, not considering that it might be worth starting from Zero, forgetting everything about the standard formulation in terms of "four-vectors" and Matrices, then slowly and naively exploring Quaternions, its natural properties, and related structures, such as Automorphisms and Möbius Transformations, to then notice that Fundamental Laws of Relativity naturally appear, formulated in a way that is quite more appropriate and natural in the context of Quaternions; very different⁵ from the *standard formulation*, but *isomorphic* to it... In other words, try to *adapt Relativistic Physics to Quaternions*, rather than the converse, the *naive idea* being that *Quaternions arise naturally from Algebraic Topology*, and *Fundamental Laws of Relativistic Physics naturally arise from the Structure of Quaternions*...

As the title suggests, this work will focus on the Mathematical properties of Quaternions, rather than Physics; however, it should be kept in mind that my main motivation has always been to use such properties in order to reformulate certain aspects of (special) Relativity in a potentially more elegant and interesting way. This is why it will often contain remarks

²original spelling : Лев Понтрягин

³He lost his eyesight when he was 14 -due to a stove explosion-

⁴not even mentioning the links with many Symmetry Groups, Clifford Algebras, Pauli Matrices etc...

⁵in particular, Lorentz Boosts will not be linear w.r.t. the natural \mathbb{R} -vector space structure on \mathbb{H} , but will -for instance- have nice Geometrical properties

about potential connections with Physics; sometimes very naive ones, but also some more concrete ones, such as how a special kind of Quaternionic Möbius Transformations can be seen as isomorphic to the Lorentz Group, and how such an isomorphism can be used to reformulate some elementary concepts of Relativistic Physics -such as the addition of velocities- in a much simpler, elegant, and more intuitive way.

The first chapter will mainly be based on some of Pontryagin's work, the goal being to construct and define Quaternions from its Algebraic and Topological properties, while emphasizing how *Unique* this structure is...

The other chapters will not really be based on existing publications (though they will with no doubt contain many *well-known results*) :

In Chapter 2, I will naively explore the -very- elementary properties of Quaternions -such as, for example, Automorphisms (i.e. Rotations) etc- but with a quite non-standard approach: the whole formulation will be based on -rudimentary- concepts of Differential Algebra (for instance, it will be noted that as \mathbb{C} can be seen as a Galois extension of \mathbb{R} w.r.t. the polynomial $X^2+1 = 0$, \mathbb{H} can also in some sense be seen as a *Differential Galois Extension* of \mathbb{C} w.r.t. the *Differential Equation* $q'' + q = 0$ when seeing commutators as derivatives)

The goal of Chapter 3 will be to explore Quaternionic Möbius Transformations; in particular, a special subgroup⁶ isomorphic to the Lorentz Group, and whose restriction to the sphere of square roots of -1 in \mathbb{H} consists of exactly all biconformal maps (i.e. acts on that sphere exactly as the Complex Möbius Group does on the Riemann sphere; the difference being that in this case, the symmetry is not broken⁷ and stereographic projections in the context of Quaternions are much simpler -and more natural- to express than in the context⁸ of \mathbb{C} with \mathbb{R}^3). I should also show methods for Compass-and-Straightedge construction of such transformations (literally: by just drawing one circle and two lines), as well as defining endomorphisms (w.r.t. special group laws) on \mathbb{H} that will be invariant under those transformations⁹... Finally, at the very end of Chapter 3, remarks will be made about how such Mathematical objects are naturally connected with Relativistic Physics, and how they could potentially be used to reformulate the latter. As an example,

⁶maps of the form $f : q \mapsto (aq - b)(bq + a)^{-1}$, with the special condition that $f(0)$ should be purely imaginary (and of absolute value smaller than 1); note that boosts will be expressed by $q \mapsto (b + q)(1 - bq)^{-1}$

⁷as we do not "privilege" any axis by defining things such as "North Pole, 0, 1, .."

⁸as embedding \mathbb{C} into \mathbb{R}^3 is quite unnatural, while \mathbb{C} is already naturally embedded in \mathbb{H} : (generalized) stereographic "Projections" in \mathbb{H} are then simply expressed by maps (of order 4) of the form : $q \mapsto (q - 1)(q + 1)^{-1}$

⁹thus playing a role analogous to the *Minkowski Pseudo-Norm*

we discuss the case of *velocity addition formula*, suggesting a formulation in terms of Quaternions, which turns out to be much simpler and more efficient¹⁰ than the standard *Einstein velocity addition formula*; and show that it has a very natural geometrical interpretation and can be constructed by just drawing three lines on a circle; also mentioning that the tool we use to replace the traditional *four-velocity* turns out to be much more intuitive and using it to solve -for instance- the *Twin Paradox* makes the latter look trivial...

To give an overview of this, the **standard Einstein's Formula** -in its general form- is usually expressed as

$$\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^3 : \|\mathbf{v}_1\|, \|\mathbf{v}_2\| < c$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{v}_1 \oplus_{\mathbb{R}^3} \mathbf{v}_2 = \frac{\langle \mathbf{v}_1 | \mathbf{v}_2 \rangle \mathbf{v}_1 / \|\mathbf{v}_1\|^2 + \mathbf{v}_2 + \sqrt{1 - \|\mathbf{v}_1\|^2 / c^2} (\mathbf{v}_2 - \langle \mathbf{v}_1 | \mathbf{v}_2 \rangle \mathbf{v}_1 / \|\mathbf{v}_1\|^2)}{1 + \langle \mathbf{v}_1 | \mathbf{v}_2 \rangle / c^2} \\ \gamma(v_1 \oplus_{\mathbb{R}^3} v_2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{1 - \|v_1 \oplus_{\mathbb{R}^3} v_2\|^2}{c^2}}} \end{array} \right.$$

while we will see that in terms of Quaternions, it could simply be formulated as:

$$v, q \in \mathbb{V}, v \oplus q = (1 + v)^{-1} (v + q + vq - 1) (v + q - vq + 1)^{-1} (1 + v)$$

(Not only containing no square root, but also automatically calculating the associated Time Dilation)

Or in terms of Quaternionic Möbius Transformations:

$$f_b(q) = (b + q)(1 - bq)^{-1}, \quad b = \frac{1 + v}{1 - v}$$

¹⁰in particular no square root : only algebraic operations

Which can then be represented geometrically as follows:

None of what we will do should require the use of square roots¹¹, nor trigonometric functions¹², nor Matrices¹³, nor *four-vectors*, nor *pseudo-norm*, nor Tensors(...) This should logically make things a bit more interesting in a purely Mathematical point of view (as everything is algebraic and can thus be done with Rational Numbers [*Rational Quaternions*], or even [*who knows?*] generalized to some other more abstract field¹⁴), but not only: the absence of square root should also make it simpler in an algorithmic point of view...

Note that Chapter 1 only starts after page 23, as it is preceded by a quite long Glossary, which I put at the beginning in order to make sure that the reader would not miss it. Its reading should not be compulsory, but might be useful for the reader who would desire to *skip chapters* or sections...

¹¹there will be no "gamma factor" to calculate (explicitly), as we will directly work with four-dimensional quantities, and never "separate time and space"

¹²though they are perfectly compatible (but not necessary)

¹³though I may use $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$ to represent the Möbius Transformation:
 $q \mapsto (aq + b)(cq + d)^{-1}$

¹⁴I am obviously Not talking about the ones that are *Connected and Locally Compact*...

Notational conventions (&Glossary)

Throughout this paper, I will tend to use some standard notational conventions, along with some very unconventional ones (most of which may not be encountered anywhere else in the literature). In order to avoid any confusion as well as to make the task easier for the reader, I will try to summarize the main ones here. They will still, however, be introduced progressively throughout the chapters...

We denote by \mathbb{N} the set of Natural Numbers (including 0) as well as \mathbb{Z} the ring of Integers, $\mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}$ the respective fields of Rational, Real and Complex Numbers, and finally, \mathbb{H} the skew field of Quaternions. For the above mentioned fields, we will denote by $\mathbb{Q}^\times, \mathbb{R}^\times, \mathbb{C}^\times$ and \mathbb{H}^\times the corresponding sets of invertible (hence non-zero) elements (multiplicative group). More generally, for any given ring¹⁵ \mathbb{A} , we will denote by \mathbb{A}^\times its multiplicative group of invertible elements (or at least the corresponding set) while $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{A})$ will represent the subring of elements of \mathbb{A} commuting with all the other ones (i.e. its center).

The n-dimensional Projective Space over a (Commutative) field \mathbb{K}_C will be denoted by $\mathbf{P}^n(\mathbb{K}_C)$, while for any skew field \mathbb{K} , the symbol $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ will denote its "projective line" in the sense :

$$\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) := \mathbb{K} \cup \{\infty\}$$

In general, \bar{x} will denote the image of an element x under an involutive antiautomorphism $\bar{} : x \mapsto \bar{x}$, i.e. :

$$\overline{\bar{x}} = x, \quad \overline{xy} = \bar{y}\bar{x}$$

¹⁵N.B.: The Rings are always assumed to be Associative and with multiplicative identity; in particular, "Skew Field" will always mean the same as "Division Ring"

In particular, for a quaternion

$$q = t + x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j} + z\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{H}, \quad \mathbf{i}^2 = \mathbf{j}^2 = \mathbf{k}^2 = \mathbf{ijk} = -1$$

we will have

$$\bar{q} = t - x\mathbf{i} - y\mathbf{j} - z\mathbf{k}$$

In the same way, $|\cdot|$ will denote a valuation; in the case of $\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}, \mathbb{H}$ it will be Archimedean, and -apart from being a multiplicative endomorphism (as the 3 fields are \mathbb{R} -algebras) obtained from the involution we just defined - will correspond geometrically to the Euclidean norm. In particular,

$$|q| = \sqrt{q\bar{q}} = \sqrt{t^2 + x^2 + y^2 + z^2} = |t + x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j} + z\mathbf{k}|$$

Although Quaternions do not commute in general, I might still use the "fraction bar" under some circumstances, namely when the numerator and denominator do commute, in order to emphasize the latter fact. i.e.

$$\text{for } A, B \text{ such that } AB = BA, \quad \text{we define : } \frac{A}{B} := AB^{-1} = B^{-1}A$$

It might also be worth mentioning that I will be using the following conventions :

- \simeq isomorphism
- \approx homeomorphism
- \sim equivalence relation

Also, given a set \mathbf{T} and a function $f : \mathbf{T} \rightarrow \mathbf{T}$, I will usually say that a subset $\mathbf{S} \subseteq \mathbf{T}$ is :

- **stable** under f if $f(\mathbf{S}) = \mathbf{S}$,
hence the points are -a priori- moved, but stay in \mathbf{S}
- **fixed** under f if $\forall t \in \mathbf{S}, f(t) = t$ (i.e. pointwise)
hence *fixed* \implies *stable*, but the converse is false in general

The above-mentioned notational conventions are probably the most "standard" ones I will be using; now I will introduce some quite **non-standard** ones :

- $\mathcal{X} \mapsto \hat{\mathcal{X}}$

This will always -for a given division ring- represent some involution (and homeomorphism in the case of a topological division ring) on the projective line, i.e. :

$$\hat{x} = x$$

Most of the time, this involution will simply be $q \mapsto -q^{-1} =: \hat{q}$. When -for some purpose- representing something else (e.g.: $q \mapsto q^{-1}$), it will be explicitly stated.

- $\hat{\mathbb{K}}$

This will represent the image of a division ring \mathbb{K} under the above defined involution $x \mapsto \hat{x}$ (on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$), thus $\hat{\mathbb{K}} \simeq \mathbb{K}$ and should **not be confused with $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$**

Hence in the case of \mathbb{H} , together with $\hat{q} := -q^{-1}$, we have that $\hat{\mathbb{H}}$ can be seen as " $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{H}) \setminus \{0\}$ " ("0 replaced by ∞ ")

- $\hat{\cdot}$

This is the natural multiplicative law on $\hat{\mathbb{K}}$ (for a given division ring \mathbb{K}) such that

$$\hat{\cdot} : (\mathbb{K}^\times, \cdot) \rightarrow (\hat{\mathbb{K}}^\times, \hat{\cdot}) : x \mapsto \hat{x}$$

be a multiplicative group isomorphism.

This is naturally obtained by taking

$$a \cdot b := \hat{a} \cdot \hat{b}$$

in order to satisfy

$$\widehat{a \cdot b} = \hat{a} \cdot \hat{b}$$

In the case of \mathbb{H} together with $\hat{q} := -q^{-1}$, we will have :

$$a \hat{\cdot} b = -b \cdot a$$

Notice that in the same way, we could naturally define the "conjugate" (or -equivalently- "inverse") of " \cdot " as :

$$a \bar{\cdot} b := b \cdot a$$

- $\hat{+}$

As we did for the multiplicative law, we can define an additive law on $\hat{\mathbb{K}}$ by setting :

$$a \hat{+} b := \widehat{a + b}$$

Such that

$$\widehat{a + b} = \widehat{a} \widehat{+} \widehat{b}$$

thus giving a division ring structure on $\widehat{\mathbb{K}}$ dictated by the isomorphism:

$$\widehat{\cdot}: (\mathbb{K}, \cdot, +, 1, 0) \rightarrow (\widehat{\mathbb{K}}, \widehat{\cdot}, \widehat{+}, \widehat{1}, \widehat{0}) : x \mapsto \widehat{x}$$

Notice that $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ now has a "double structure" where the operations of the "two different skew fields" may interact with each other, as in the case of \mathbb{H} together with $\widehat{q} := -q^{-1}$

Indeed, in this case we would have :

$$a \cdot b = -b \cdot a, \quad a \widehat{+} b = a \cdot (a + b)^{-1} \cdot b$$

in which case those operations would satisfy :

("shared inverses")

$$a \cdot (a^{-1}) = -1 = \widehat{1}, \quad a \widehat{+} (-a) = \infty = \widehat{0}$$

as well as :

("crossed distributivity")

$$\left| \begin{array}{l} a \cdot (b + c) = a \cdot b + a \cdot c \\ a \cdot \widehat{(b + c)} = a \cdot \widehat{b} + a \cdot \widehat{c} \end{array} \right| \left| \begin{array}{l} a \cdot (b \widehat{+} c) = a \cdot b \widehat{+} a \cdot c \\ a \cdot \widehat{(b \widehat{+} c)} = a \cdot \widehat{b} \widehat{+} a \cdot \widehat{c} \end{array} \right|$$

- \mathbb{L} ("Light Sphere")

This is a very important set I will be using very often, and which has significant relevance in terms of Algebraic, Geometric, and Physical meaning; the latter may sometimes make me refer to it as "the Light Sphere". For \mathbb{H} together with the involution $\widehat{q} := -q^{-1}$, we can define \mathbb{L} as the the set of fixed points of \mathbb{H} under this involution, or equivalently, the set of all square roots of "-1" in \mathbb{H} . Geometrically, it can be seen as the (2-dimensional) sphere (\mathbb{S}^2) -unit imaginary quaternions- and will be precisely the set of points that will be stable under the special kind of "Quaternionic Möbius Transformations" we are going to focus on and that will play the role of the Lorentz Group (more precisely, those will be conformal on \mathbb{L} -or anticonformal if we do include time-reversal- exhibiting explicit links with the study of the Riemann Sphere). In the formulation of Special Relativity I will suggest, one of the important

uses of \mathbb{L} will be to represent the velocity of particles moving at the speed of light (hence massless particles). Thus more formally, we define:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{L} &:= \{q \in \mathbb{H} : \hat{q} = q\} \\ &= \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q^2 = -1\} \\ &= \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q + \bar{q} = 0 \wedge q\bar{q} = 1\} \\ &= \{x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j} + z\mathbf{k} : x, y, z \in \mathbb{R}, x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 1\} \approx \mathbb{S}^2\end{aligned}$$

In general, I will denote by ℓ an element of \mathbb{L}

- \mathbb{RL}

This will simply represent the kernel of the additive endomorphism

$$q \mapsto \frac{q + \bar{q}}{2}$$

hence the 3-dimensional vector space (over \mathbb{R}) of all Quaternions whose real part is zero.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{RL} &= \{r\ell : r \in \mathbb{R}, \ell \in \mathbb{L}\} \\ &= \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q + \bar{q} = 0\} \\ &= \{x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j} + z\mathbf{k} : x, y, z \in \mathbb{R}\} \approx \mathbb{R}^3\end{aligned}$$

Notice that I obviously identify \mathbb{R} to the center of \mathbb{H}

$$\mathbb{R} \hookrightarrow \mathbb{H} : \mathbb{R} := \mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{H})$$

and that we clearly have (by definition) the direct sum:

$$\mathbb{H} = \mathbb{R} \oplus \mathbb{RL}$$

- \mathbb{LL}

this is how I decided to denote the kernel of the multiplicative endomorphism $q \mapsto |q|$ in \mathbb{H} , i.e. the (3-dimensional) (hyper)sphere (\mathbb{S}^3) of unit Quaternions. As its definition indicates (kernel), it is a multiplicative group, and as its name suggests, its elements can always be seen as a (non-unique) product of two elements of \mathbb{L}

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{LL} &= \{\ell_1\ell_2 : \ell_1, \ell_2 \in \mathbb{L}\} \\ &= \ker |\cdot| \\ &= \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q\bar{q} = 1\} \\ &= \{t + x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j} + z\mathbf{k} : t, x, y, z \in \mathbb{R}, t^2 + x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 1\} \approx \mathbb{S}^3\end{aligned}$$

Note that we also clearly have :

$$\mathbb{R}^{>0}\mathbb{LL} = \mathbb{R}^\times\mathbb{LL} = \mathbb{H}^\times, \quad \mathbb{RLL} = \mathbb{H}$$

- δ_ℓ

As for a fixed element $a \in \mathbb{H}$, the map $q \mapsto [q, a] := qa - aq$ is linear and satisfies the Leibniz Rule, it can be seen as a "Derivative" on \mathbb{H} in the sense of (non-commutative) Differential Algebra (and can therefore be denoted $2\delta_a$). It is then easy to see that, as the derivative associated to a real number is always trivial, it will only be relevant to study those associated to elements of \mathbb{RL} , or more precisely, elements of \mathbb{L} . We thus define, for $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$:

$$\delta_\ell q := \frac{q\ell - \ell q}{2}$$

Also, when there is no ambiguity w.r.t. the chosen ℓ , I may use the notation :

$$q' := \delta_\ell q$$

It is easy to see that, for the derivative associated to any $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, the "differential equation" :

$$q' + q''' = 0$$

will always be satisfied for any $q \in \mathbb{H}$

(also note that, although it may not be specially relevant in most cases, I may still make use of the more general expression :

$$\delta_a q := \frac{qa - aq}{2}$$

for a general $a \in \mathbb{H}$. Notice that this will correspond geometrically to the cross product of the imaginary parts of q and a)

- \mathbb{C}_ℓ [= $\{q \in \mathbb{H} : q' = 0 \text{ w.r.t. } \delta_\ell\}$]

For a given $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, we can define the subfield of \mathbb{H} generated by ℓ over \mathbb{R} (in other words, $\mathbb{R}(\ell)$), this is obviously isomorphic to \mathbb{C} , and we have:

$$\mathbb{C}_\ell := \{t + r\ell : t, r \in \mathbb{R}\}$$

It can also be seen as the field of constants w.r.t. the "derivative" δ_ℓ or in other words, the set of all elements commuting with ℓ . Thus we have :

$$\mathbb{C}_\ell = \mathbb{R}(\ell) = \mathbb{R}[\ell] = \ker \delta_\ell$$

Note that as for the "derivative", I may also use the more general expression

$$\mathbb{C}_a = \{t + ra : t, r \in \mathbb{R}\} = \mathbb{R}(a) = \mathbb{R}[a] = \ker \delta_a$$

for a general $a \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{R}$, although it obviously "does not bring anything new" as we clearly have -for $a, b \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{R}$ -

$$\mathbb{C}_a = \mathbb{C}_b \iff ab = ba \iff a \in \mathbb{C}_b \iff b \in \mathbb{C}_a \iff \exists \ell \in \mathbb{L} : a, b \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$$

- ℓ^\perp [= $\{q \in \mathbb{H} : q'' + q = 0 \text{ w.r.t. } \delta_\ell\}$]

As we did with the kernel, we can also look at the image of δ_ℓ , $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, thus defining :

$$\ell^\perp := \delta_\ell \mathbb{H}$$

Algebraically, this corresponds to a subset of \mathbb{RL} ; more precisely, it is the \mathbb{R} -vector space of all elements that anticommute with ℓ . Geometrically, it can be seen as the plane of all elements in \mathbb{RL} that are orthogonal to the line passing through the origin and ℓ . We naturally have :

$$\mathbb{H} = \ker \delta_\ell \oplus \delta_\ell \mathbb{H} = \mathbb{C}_\ell \oplus \ell^\perp$$

We can also see that elements of \mathbb{C}_ℓ and ℓ^\perp interact with each other in a particular way; more precisely, let $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, $a, b \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$, $X, Y \in \ell^\perp$, then

$$\begin{aligned} ab &\in \mathbb{C}_\ell \text{ (as it is a field)} \\ XY &\in \mathbb{C}_\ell \text{ (see commutation relations w.r.t. } \ell \text{)} \\ aX &\in \ell^\perp \text{ (see commutation relations w.r.t. } \ell \text{)} \\ aX &= X\bar{a} \end{aligned}$$

Note that, as already mentioned, unlike the field \mathbb{C}_ℓ , we "only" have a \mathbb{R} -vector space structure on ℓ^\perp ; however, it can easily be given a field structure in a quite natural way, once we specify a Neutral element N . More precisely, let $N \in \ell^\perp \setminus \{0\}$, then by the above relations, we have :

$$\mathbb{C}_\ell N = \ell^\perp$$

The multiplication law is then given by $(X, Y) \mapsto XN^{-1}Y$ for which N is clearly the neutral element. It is obviously "nicer" to take N unitary, hence $N \in \ell^\perp \cap \mathbb{L}$, giving :

$$XN^{-1}Y = -XNY = X\bar{N}Y$$

Finally, as for the "derivative" and its "field of constants", we can also generalize

$$a^\perp := \delta_a \mathbb{H}$$

For any $a \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{R}$; it is then no longer seen as the set of elements "anticommuting with a " (such a set would only exist if $a \in \mathbb{RL}$) but rather the ones that "anticommute with the imaginary part of a " (I insist on the fact that $a \notin \mathbb{R}$)

- $\mathbb{R}\ell =: \ell^\parallel$

As its name indicates, it is simply the set $\{r\ell : r \in \mathbb{R}\}$ for a given $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, and should clearly not be confused with $\mathbb{R}(\ell) = \mathbb{C}_\ell$, nor $\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}$, to which it is obviously related by

$$\ell^\parallel = \mathbb{R}\ell = \mathbb{C}_\ell \cap \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}, \quad \mathbb{C}_\ell = \mathbb{R} \oplus \mathbb{R}\ell$$

- $P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+, P_{\ell^\perp}^+, P_{\ell^\parallel}^+ = P_{\mathbb{R}\ell}^+, P_{\mathbb{R}}^+, P_{\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}}^+, P_{\mathbb{L}\mathbb{L}}^+, P_{\mathbb{L}}^+$

Those are all projections to the corresponding subsets (hence $P \circ P = P$). Note that the "+" indicates that it is also \mathbb{R} -linear, while "." means that it is a multiplicative morphism. More explicitly, we have (for $\ell \in \mathbb{L}, N \in \ell^\perp \cap \mathbb{L}$):

$$P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(q) := \frac{q - \ell q \ell}{2}$$

$$P_{\ell^\perp}^+(q) := \frac{q + \ell q \ell}{2} = \ell \delta_\ell q =: \ell q' = -q''$$

$$P_{\ell^\parallel}^+(q) = P_{\mathbb{R}\ell}^+(q) := P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(P_{N^\perp}^+(q)) = \frac{1}{4}(q - \ell q \ell + N q N + \ell N q \ell N)$$

$$P_{\mathbb{R}}^+(q) := \frac{q + \bar{q}}{2} = P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(P_{\mathbb{C}_N}^+(q)) = \frac{1}{4}(q - \ell q \ell - N q N - \ell N q \ell N)$$

$$P_{\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}}^+(q) := \frac{q - \bar{q}}{2} = q - P_{\mathbb{R}}^+(q) = \frac{1}{4}(3q + \ell q \ell + N q N + \ell N q \ell N)$$

$$P_{\mathbb{L}\mathbb{L}}^+(q) := \frac{q}{|q|}, \quad q \neq 0$$

$$P_{\mathbb{L}}^+(q) := P_{\mathbb{L}\mathbb{L}}^+(P_{\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}}^+(q)) = \frac{q - \bar{q}}{|q - \bar{q}|}, \quad q \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{R}$$

Note that from the fact, that $P_{\ell^\perp}^+(q) = \ell q' = -q''$ (w.r.t. δ_ℓ), we can get new relations such as :

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\ell^\perp}^+(ab) &= P_{\ell^\perp}^+(a)b + \rho_\ell(a)P_{\ell^\perp}^+(b) \quad (\text{where } \rho_\ell(q) = -\ell q \ell) \\ &= P_{\ell^\perp}^+(a)b + aP_{\ell^\perp}^+(b) - 2P_{\ell^\perp}^+(a)P_{\ell^\perp}^+(b) \end{aligned}$$

While the fact that :

$$P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(ab) + P_{\ell^\perp}^+(ab) = ab = (P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(a) + P_{\ell^\perp}^+(a))(P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(b) + P_{\ell^\perp}^+(b))$$

as well as the relations between elements of \mathbb{C}_ℓ and ℓ^\perp give us

$$\begin{aligned} (ab)_\parallel &= a_\parallel b_\parallel + a_\perp b_\perp \\ (ab)_\perp &= a_\parallel b_\perp + a_\perp b_\parallel \end{aligned}$$

Where $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ and $q_\parallel := P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(q)$, $q_\perp := P_{\ell^\perp}^+(q)$

- $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ [whose elements are denoted : ρ]
It is, as its name indicates, the group of Automorphisms of \mathbb{H} , as a \mathbb{R} -algebra. It is easy to notice that they will all be rotations, as Automorphisms will preserve real part as well as norm and orientation. They obviously contain all maps $q \mapsto aqa^{-1}, a \in \mathbb{H}^{\times}$, which turn out to actually generate all rotations. More precisely, for $\ell \in \mathbb{L}, \theta \in [0, 2\pi[$ and $e^{\ell\theta} = \cos \theta + \ell \sin \theta \in \mathbb{C}_{\ell}$, we will have that the map

$$q \mapsto e^{\ell\theta} q e^{-\ell\theta}$$

will represent a rotation of an angle 2θ around the line $\mathbb{R}\ell$, as it will obviously fix points of \mathbb{C}_{ℓ} , while for $N \in \ell^{\perp}$, we will have

$$e^{\ell\theta} N e^{-\ell\theta} = e^{\ell\theta} \overline{e^{-\ell\theta}} N = e^{\ell\theta} e^{\ell\theta} N = e^{2\theta\ell} N \in \mathbb{C}_{\ell} N (= \ell^{\perp})$$

Thus

$$\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) = \{\rho_a : q \mapsto aqa^{-1}, a \in \mathbb{H}^{\times}\} = \{\rho_u : q \mapsto uq\bar{u}, u \in \mathbb{L}\mathbb{L}\} \simeq SO(3) \approx \mathbf{P}^3(\mathbb{R})$$

- $a \sim b$

The equivalence relation I will be using most often will be :

$$\begin{aligned} a, b \in \mathbb{H}^{\times}, a \sim b &\iff \exists \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{\times} : b = \lambda a \\ &\iff ab^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{\times} \\ &\iff \rho_a = \rho_b \quad (\text{i.e.: induce the same rotation}) \end{aligned}$$

- $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$

This is the subset of $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ consisting of all nontrivial involutions, i.e.:

$$\rho_{\mathbb{L}} = \{\rho_{\ell} : q \mapsto \ell q \ell^{-1} = -\ell q \ell, \ell \in \mathbb{L}\} \approx \mathbf{P}^2(\mathbb{R})$$

Note that it is obviously not a group (does not even contain the identity) but does generate $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$. (Geometrically, elements of $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$ represent "half-turns")

- $\text{Gal}_{\delta_{\ell}}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_{\ell})$

As \mathbb{C} is usually seen as a Galois extension of \mathbb{R} w.r.t. the polynomial $x^2 + 1 = 0$, \mathbb{H} can also somehow be seen as a "Differential Galois Extension" of \mathbb{C}_{ℓ} w.r.t. the "differential equation" $q'' + q = 0$, for a given $\delta_{\ell} : q \mapsto q' = \frac{q\ell - \ell q}{2}, \ell \in \mathbb{L}$. The "Differential Galois Group" is then seen as the group of "differential automorphisms" (i.e. automorphisms

that commute with the derivative: $\rho\delta_\ell = \delta_\ell\rho$) that fix \mathbb{C}_ℓ and move solutions of $q'' + q = 0$. In this case, those conditions are redundant, and the Differential Galois Group corresponds precisely to the group of differential automorphisms w.r.t. δ_ℓ . We then clearly have :

$$\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) = \{\rho : q \mapsto cq c^{-1}, c \in \mathbb{C}_\ell\}$$

• $\mathfrak{M} \quad [\langle \mathfrak{M}, \overset{\Delta}{\mathfrak{M}}, \mathfrak{M}^\triangleright \rangle]$

\mathfrak{M} will denote the group of homeomorphisms on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{H})$ generated by the maps :

$$\begin{aligned} q &\mapsto aq \\ q &\mapsto qa \\ q &\mapsto q + b \\ q &\mapsto q^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Where $a \in \mathbb{H}^\times, b \in \mathbb{H}$. \mathfrak{M} will be referred to as the "(Quaternionic) Möbius Group", and will appear in three **equivalent** representations :

– The "Left Form", denoted $\langle \mathfrak{M}$, in which the elements are written:

$$q \mapsto (qc + d)^{-1}(qa + b)$$

(and with appropriate coefficients such that the map be invertible)

– The "Central Form", denoted $\overset{\Delta}{\mathfrak{M}}$, in which the elements are either written:

$$q \mapsto aqb + c$$

or

$$q \mapsto (aqb + c)^{-1} + d$$

With $a, b \in \mathbb{H}^\times, c, d \in \mathbb{H}$ (=necessary and sufficient conditions such that the map be invertible)

– The "Right Form", denoted $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$, in which the elements are written:

$$q \mapsto (aq + b)(cq + d)^{-1}$$

(and with appropriate coefficients such that the map be invertible)

Note that switching from one representation to another can sometimes be useful to exhibit certain properties, as for instance, switching to $\overset{\Delta}{\mathfrak{M}}$ allows us to get explicit conditions on coefficients (\sim "determinant") for the map to be invertible, while it is easy to see that the inverse of a map written in $\langle \mathfrak{M}$ can trivially be found in $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ and vice-versa.

- $\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{R}$ [& $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}, \mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}, \mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}$]

Those are three subgroups of \mathfrak{M} , that I will call respectively "Linear", "Symmetric", and "Relativistic". Together, they generate \mathfrak{M} , and have the property that:

$$\mathcal{L} \cap \mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S} \cap \mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R} \cap \mathcal{L} = \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$$

- \mathcal{L} consists of elements of the form :

$$q \mapsto aqb, \quad a, b \in \mathbb{H}^{\times}$$

thus fixing 0 and ∞

- \mathcal{S} (represented in its $\mathfrak{M}^{\triangleright}$ form) consists of elements :

$$q \mapsto (aq + b)(bq + a)^{-1}$$

thus fixing 1 and -1 (note that a necessary and sufficient condition for the expression to be invertible is that 0 be not sent to 1 or -1)

- \mathcal{R} (represented in its $\mathfrak{M}^{\triangleright}$ form) consists of elements :

$$q \mapsto (aq - b)(bq + a)^{-1}$$

it is then easy to see that \mathbb{L} is stable under such transformations, which actually turn out to be conformal (on \mathbb{L}). Also, a necessary and sufficient condition for the expression to be invertible is that 0 be not sent to \mathbb{L}

We see that $\mathcal{S} \simeq \mathcal{L} \simeq \mathbb{R}^{>0} \times SO(4)$ while $\mathcal{R} \simeq U(1) \times SO(3, 1)^+$, where $SO(3, 1)^+$ represents the restricted¹⁶ Lorentz Group. For those transformations, a method for elementary "compass-and-straightedge construction" will be shown. The equivalent groups on \mathbb{C} will be denoted by $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}, \mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}$ and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}$. It is easy to see that

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathbb{R}^{>0} \times U(1) \simeq \mathbb{C}^{\times}$$

They also parametrize the (complex) Möbius Group in the same way that "boosts and rotations" in the x, y , and z directions parametrize $SO(3, 1)^+$.

¹⁶i.e. The Lorentz Transformations that preserve orientation of space and direction of time; the "identity component" (in the sense of Topological Groups) of $SO(3, 1)$

- $q \mapsto \tilde{q}$

This will represent an involution, namely

$$\tilde{q} := \frac{1-q}{1+q}$$

When applied to $\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L} \cup \{\infty\}$ or $\mathbb{L}\mathbb{L}$, it can be seen as a "Stereographic Projection" combined with a symmetry.

- \mathbb{V}

It will represent the set of "Velocities" (slower than light). More formally,

$$\mathbb{V} := \{v \in \mathbb{H} : v + \bar{v} > 0, v\bar{v} = 1\}$$

- $\tilde{\mathbb{V}}$

This will represent the open unit imaginary ball $[0, 1[\mathbb{L}$ i.e. :

$$\tilde{\mathbb{V}} = \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q + \bar{q} = 0, q\bar{q} < 1\}$$

- $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$

As previously said, \mathbb{L} is stable under \mathcal{R} (whose action on \mathbb{L} is conformal), which is itself isomorphic to $U(1) \times SO(3, 1)^+$. The center $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$ is given by the transformations with real coefficients and corresponds precisely to those which Fix the points of \mathbb{L} . It is isomorphic to $U(1)$. I then define $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ as the following subgroup of \mathcal{R} :

$$\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) := \{g \in \mathcal{R} : g(0) \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}}\}$$

(or equivalently $g(1) \in \mathbb{V}$) We can then write any element of \mathcal{R} as a composition of an element of $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$ with an element of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$, and have :

$$\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) \simeq \mathcal{R} / \mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R}) \simeq SO(3, 1)^+ \simeq PGL(2, \mathbb{C})$$

Thus our "Lorentz Group" can be seen as a representation of the "group of all biconformal maps on the \mathbb{L} sphere" (\simeq [complex] Möbius Group). Note that adding $q \mapsto -q$ generates $\pm \text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$, which then also contains anticonformal maps (on \mathbb{L}), which can be used to represent Lorentz Transformations including Time Reversal. We will see that transformations of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ can be represented geometrically by simply *drawing one circle and two lines*

- \mathbb{H}^+

$$\mathbb{H}^+ := \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q + \bar{q} > 0\}$$

(Analogous to Poincaré's Upper Half Plane)

- $*$

This will represent a general composition law, not necessarily a group. It will usually denote "Gyrogroup" laws such as :

$$(a, b) \mapsto (a + b)(1 + ab)^{-1}$$

or

$$(a, b) \mapsto (a + b)(1 - ab)^{-1}$$

- \odot

This will generally be used to represent a *multiplicative* law that is not the standard multiplication on \mathbb{H} . Depending on the context, details -such as indexes- can be added. The inverse of an element q w.r.t \odot will be denoted by $q^{\odot^{-1}}$ while its "square root" w.r.t. this law will be denoted $q^{\odot^{\frac{1}{2}}}$. e_{\odot} will denote its neutral element

- \oplus

Although it could a priori be used to represent an *additive law associated with \odot* , it will usually just be used to simply represent *direct sums* of vector spaces -as already used in some of the above definitions- (Note that although it is usually used in Physics to represent the *addition of relativistic velocities* I will rather define " \star " in order to avoid giving "multiple meanings" to \oplus)

- \otimes

This will simply denote the *Tensor Product*. I should just use it to represent the ring of Biquaternions $\mathbb{C} \otimes \mathbb{H}$

- \star

This will represent the relativistic addition of velocities. Unlike the -quite complicated- *standard formula* that is usually used in Relativity (known as *Einstein's Formula*), we will see that the *Quaternionic version* that naturally arises from the objects -such as $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ - we are going to study turns out to be very elementary, *square-root-free*, and -as for $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ - can easily be represented geometrically by drawing one circle and three lines. Also, as it is four-dimensional, it will not only calculate the total speed, but also the associated *time dilation*.

• $\mathfrak{R}, \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$

Those will -at first- represent "real endomorphisms" w.r.t. \odot and $\hat{\odot}$ respectively. More precisely, we will have :

$$\begin{aligned}\mathfrak{R}(q) &:= q \odot \bar{q} \\ \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q) &:= q \hat{\odot} \bar{q}\end{aligned}$$

Which will then satisfy relations such as :

$$\mathfrak{R}(a \odot b) = \mathfrak{R}(a) \odot \mathfrak{R}(b), \quad \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(a \hat{\odot} b) = \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(a) \hat{\odot} \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(b)$$

$$\mathfrak{R}(z) = \mathfrak{R}(\hat{z}), \quad \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(z) = \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(\hat{z})$$

$$\mathfrak{R}(a \hat{\odot} b) = \mathfrak{R}(\widehat{a \odot b}) = \mathfrak{R}(a \odot b) = \mathfrak{R}(a) \odot \mathfrak{R}(b)$$

$$\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(a \odot b) = \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(\widehat{a \odot b}) = \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(a \hat{\odot} b) = \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(a) \hat{\odot} \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(b)$$

We will then generalize such morphisms to Gyrogroup laws $*$ (i.e. non-associative), defining \mathfrak{R} such that

$$\mathfrak{R}(a * b) = \mathfrak{R}(a) * \mathfrak{R}(b)$$

Explicitly, the morphisms we shall use will usually be:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathfrak{R} &: (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\} : q \mapsto \frac{q + \bar{q}}{1 - q\bar{q}} \\ \widehat{\mathfrak{R}} &: (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\} : q \mapsto \frac{q\bar{q} - 1}{q + \bar{q}}\end{aligned}$$

for the composition law $*$: $(a, b) \mapsto (a + b)(1 - ab)^{-1}$, where

$$\mathfrak{R}(a * b) = \mathfrak{R}(a) * \mathfrak{R}(b) = \mathfrak{R}(a) \odot_{\mathcal{R}} \mathfrak{R}(b)$$

thus mapping a gyrogroup onto an Abelian group, while $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$ has a geometrical interpretation in terms of hypercycles. Those morphisms shall be used to replace the traditional *Minkowski Pseudo-Norm* as they are invariant under transformations of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$.

Chapter 1

From general Topology to Quaternions: A Unique Mathematical Structure

Our goal in this chapter will be to *create a nice Mathematical Structure*, starting from fairly weak -or at least quite *abstract*- assumptions. It could naively be seen as an attempt to bring an answer to the following question(s):

- What is the *most natural* Algebraic Structure one could think of ?
- What kind of interesting topological properties could such a structure be given ?
- Once those assumptions are made, is it possible to find a *most general* such structure ?

Although -a priori- only imposing reasonably weak and quite abstract conditions, the answer will turn out to be surprisingly concrete : there exists -precisely- *one* structure satisfying those axioms, and it will then be given the name : ***Quaternions***.

In other words, we will *construct* and *define* the skew field of Quaternions from its basic algebraic and topological properties -rather than the *usual way*- as well as put the emphasis on how unique this structure is.

The main reference for this chapter will be Pontryagin's work ^{[Po-DE][Po-EN]} about Topological Groups¹. Other relevant references/further reading -for

¹Note that personally, amongst those two ("equivalent") references I could consult, I would tend to recommend the German translation^[Po-DE] over the English one^[Po-EN], as it seems that I noticed a few (minor) mistakes in the English version that were not in the German one (though the latter is actually older)

instance about Valuated Fields²- may include [Ca][Gl][Ja][Sh][We-Zi]

1.1 Division Rings

1.1.1 Basic remarks and conventions

Although I imagine that the answer to the question :

- *What is the "most natural" Algebraic Structure one could think of ?*

might be a *matter of personal taste*, I would personally still be tempted to -naively- answer :

- *A structure in which it is possible to add, subtract, multiply and divide, just as we do with "numbers"; in more formal terms, a "Skew Field" (or "Division Ring")*

Note that, for the sake of generality, I will not require multiplication to be commutative; however, I obviously still require associativity. More generally, all the *Rings* I will be talking about will be assumed to be associative, and with multiplicative identity, although not necessarily commutative. Also, "**Skew field**" and "**Division Ring**" (as well as "**Noncommutative Field**") are **equivalent** terms, and although I may sometimes use them a bit "randomly", they will always mean the same. Note that such a structure will be denoted by \mathbb{K} , while a commutative field would be denoted \mathbb{K}_C ; this rather unusual notational convention arises from the fact that I should not use *general Commutative Fields* very often, unlike Division Algebras...

1.1.2 Möbius Transformations and the Projective Line

Once we have a Division Ring \mathbb{K} , we automatically get a couple of *-very natural-* elementary groups of bijections, namely the group of Translations :

$$\{x \mapsto x + c, c \in \mathbb{K}\}$$

as well as the following group of *linear*³ bijections :

$$\{x \mapsto axb, a, b \in \mathbb{K}^\times\}$$

²Which can be seen as an alternative approach to the one we are going to take

³I make use of this term, even though we -a priori- do not yet have a "vector space" (but note that it is easy to define one, e.g. over $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{K})$)

Combining those two, we obviously get the group of *Affine Transformations*⁴:

$$\{x \mapsto axb + c, a, b \in \mathbb{K}^\times, c \in \mathbb{K}\}$$

It is then very tempting to extend that group by including the map

$$x \mapsto x^{-1}$$

which is a bijection on \mathbb{K}^\times , however not defined in 0. The simplest solution to define such a group of bijections without having to worry much about domain issues⁵ is to simply *add a point at infinity*, which we define as being the image of 0 under the map $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ (and fixed under Affine Transformations). More formally, we take the set \mathbb{K} to which we add some point $\{\infty\}$ to get a new set that we denote *-anticipatively-* by

$$\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) := \mathbb{K} \cup \{\infty\}$$

and refer to as *the Projective Line*, then once this is done, we *extend* the *Affine Transformations* from \mathbb{K} to $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ in the *natural way* (meaning the *only way such that they remain bijections on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ while still acting the same way on \mathbb{K}*) i.e. by just sending ∞ to ∞ . Then we extend $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ from \mathbb{K}^\times to $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ by making it swap 0 and ∞ . Now it is clear that the maps :

$$x \mapsto ax \tag{1.1}$$

$$x \mapsto xb \tag{1.2}$$

$$x \mapsto x + c \tag{1.3}$$

$$x \mapsto x^{-1} \tag{1.4}$$

where $a, b \in \mathbb{K}^\times, c \in \mathbb{K}$ are all well defined bijections⁶ on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ and -as they obviously include the Identity as well as their inverses- can thus be composed together to form a group⁷, which we will refer to as the *Möbius Group*⁸ associated to \mathbb{K} , denoted $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{K}}$ or simply \mathfrak{M} when \mathbb{K} is already clearly specified.

Before having a closer look at the structure of \mathfrak{M} , we will -naively- define some *extra tools* such as *Dual Division Rings* with respect to some involutions. Indeed, let

$$\hat{} : \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \rightarrow \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) : x \mapsto \hat{x}$$

⁴For the moment, we just (naively) **Define** it this way

⁵as combining $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ with affine transformations may obviously *move the "pole"*

⁶We are not putting any topological structure on it yet

⁷And clearly (1.1)(1.2) and (1.3) generate the subgroup of *Affine Transformations* on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$

⁸and naturally call its elements *Möbius Transformations*

be an involution. Then it will obviously map \mathbb{K} to $\widehat{\mathbb{K}} = \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \setminus \{\widehat{\infty}\}$. It is then easy to define $\widehat{+}, \widehat{\cdot}$ on $\widehat{\mathbb{K}}$, such that the latter⁹ become a Division Ring isomorphic to \mathbb{K} , which we will refer to as the *Dual Division Ring of \mathbb{K} w.r.t. $\widehat{\cdot}$* : $x \mapsto \widehat{x}$. It is clear that the above mentioned laws can easily be defined the following way (for $\alpha, \beta \in \widehat{\mathbb{K}}$):

$$\alpha \widehat{+} \beta := \widehat{\alpha + \beta} \quad (1.5)$$

$$\alpha \widehat{\cdot} \beta := \widehat{\alpha \cdot \beta} \quad (1.6)$$

Such that we get (for $x, y \in \mathbb{K}$):

$$\widehat{x + y} = \widehat{x} \widehat{+} \widehat{y} \quad (1.7)$$

$$\widehat{x \cdot y} = \widehat{x} \widehat{\cdot} \widehat{y} \quad (1.8)$$

Although we could -a priori- find in \mathfrak{M} a lot of nontrivial involutions, the *most obvious and natural* ones are probably -at least at first glance- these two:

$$\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \rightarrow \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) : x \mapsto -x \quad (1.9)$$

$$\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \rightarrow \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) : x \mapsto x^{-1} \quad (1.10)$$

As (1.9) is clearly an Additive Automorphism of $(\mathbb{K}, 0, +)$, the associated addition law [i.e. (1.5)] will remain the same¹⁰ (i.e. $\cdot +$), while the associated multiplicative law [i.e.: given by (1.6)] will simply be :

$$(x, y) \mapsto -x \cdot y \quad (1.11)$$

In the same way, we can look at (1.10). This time, it may be expected that it be a Multiplicative Automorphism of $(\mathbb{K}^\times, 1, \cdot)$, however, it should be noted that unlike addition, multiplication is a priori not commutative (i.e. $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ is an **antiautomorphism**), so the multiplicative law associated with (1.10) according to (1.6) will be:

$$\cdot^{-1} : (x, y) \mapsto x \cdot^{-1} y := yx \quad (1.12)$$

while the Additive Law will be given by :

$$+^{-1} : (x, y) \mapsto x +^{-1} y := (x^{-1} + y^{-1})^{-1} \quad (1.13)$$

$$= xx^{-1}(x^{-1} + y^{-1})^{-1}y^{-1}y \quad (1.14)$$

$$= x(y(x^{-1} + y^{-1})x)^{-1}y \quad (1.15)$$

$$= x(x + y)^{-1}y \quad (1.16)$$

⁹ $(\widehat{\mathbb{K}}, \widehat{+}, \widehat{\cdot}, \widehat{0}, \widehat{1})$

¹⁰in particular, \mathbb{K} is sent to $-\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{K}$ so it *does make sense* to say it this way

Now combining (1.9) with (1.10) gives a new involution¹¹ on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$, namely:

$$\widehat{\cdot} : \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \rightarrow \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) : x \mapsto \widehat{x} := -x^{-1} \quad (1.17)$$

From now, unless otherwise specified, $\widehat{\cdot} : x \mapsto \widehat{x}$ will always refer to (1.17). The associated addition and multiplication laws are then respectively given by

$$x \widehat{+} y := x(x+y)^{-1}y = y(x+y)^{-1}x \quad (1.18)$$

$$x \widehat{\cdot} y := -yx \quad (1.19)$$

In other words, we now have two structures (namely $\mathbb{K}, \widehat{\mathbb{K}}$) that are Dual of each other, and which can interact in a nontrivial way in $\mathbb{K} \cap \widehat{\mathbb{K}} = \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \setminus \{0, \infty\}$, as they will for instance -clearly- satisfy :

("shared inverses")

$$x \widehat{\cdot} (x^{-1}) = -1 = \widehat{1}, \quad x \widehat{+} (-x) = \infty = \widehat{0}$$

as well as :

("crossed distributivity")

$$\left| \begin{array}{l} x \cdot (y+z) = x \cdot y + x \cdot z \\ x \widehat{\cdot} (y+z) = x \widehat{\cdot} y + x \widehat{\cdot} z \end{array} \right| \left| \begin{array}{l} x \cdot (y \widehat{+} z) = x \cdot y \widehat{+} x \cdot z \\ x \widehat{\cdot} (y \widehat{+} z) = x \widehat{\cdot} y \widehat{+} x \widehat{\cdot} z \end{array} \right|$$

Now we come back to \mathfrak{M} and try to characterize it a bit better.

Remark 1.1.2.1. *The Möbius Group is generated by the maps of the form :*

$$x \mapsto axb, \quad a, b \in \mathbb{K}^\times \quad (1.20)$$

$$x \mapsto x + 1 \quad (1.21)$$

$$x \mapsto \widehat{x} := -x^{-1} \quad (1.22)$$

It is clear, as (1.20) will generate (1.1) as well as (1.2), and, combined with (1.22), will also generate (1.4); so it just remains to check that including (1.21) will be enough to also generate all possible Translations (1.3), but this is obvious as¹² $c(c^{-1}x + 1) = x + c$

The transformations of the form (1.20) can be referred to as the Linear Möbius Transformations (and -as previously mentioned- clearly form a subgroup of \mathfrak{M}), while the subgroup of \mathfrak{M} generated by (1.21) and (1.22) can be, if one wishes, referred to as the Modular Group

¹¹Which is quite important as it is -for instance- well known for generating (together with $x \mapsto x + 1$) the *Modular Group Gamma* used to define Modular Forms

¹²we obviously assume without loss of generality, that $c \neq 0$ (otherwise trivial)

Remark 1.1.2.2. Note that with the "Dual Division Ring" structure we just defined, it is possible to -once again- reformulate the previous result in a quite natural and symmetric way. Indeed, we can redefine \mathfrak{M} as being generated by maps on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ of the form :

$$\left| \begin{array}{l|l} x \mapsto x + 1 & x \mapsto x\hat{+}1 \\ x \mapsto a.x & x \mapsto a\hat{.}x \end{array} \right|$$

With $a \in \mathbb{K}^\times = \widehat{\mathbb{K}^\times}$. Note that this time, only left (or respectively, right) multiplication laws are required (i.e. not "both" at the same time), and we also did not need to explicitly include special involutions such as (1.4) or (1.22); only Left (OR Right) multiplication + increment. It is easy to check that the above maps do generate \mathfrak{M} , as by (1.19), we have that $a\hat{.}x = -x.a$ thus clearly generating (1.2). Then by the exact same argument as in Remark (1.1.2.1), we will also get all the translations (1.3), and so all the Affine Transformations; it finally just remains to check that (1.4) [or equivalently, (1.22)] is also generated, but this is clear, as

$$((x-1)\hat{+}1) - 1 = (x-1)(x-1+1)^{-1}.1 - 1 = 1 - x^{-1} - 1 = -x^{-1} = \hat{x}$$

Now, rather than only looking at its generators, we will seek to characterize the general form of elements of \mathfrak{M} (e.g. as already known in the case of Affine Transformations).

Proposition 1.1.2.3. The Möbius Group \mathfrak{M} exactly composed of all maps of the following two possible kinds :

$$(A) \quad x \mapsto axb + c$$

$$(B) \quad x \mapsto (axb + c)^{-1} + d$$

(With $a, b \in \mathbb{K}^\times$, $c, d \in \mathbb{K}$)

Where in **type (A)**, we clearly recognize the **Affine Transformations**, while I would be tempted to -anticipatively- refer to **type (B)** as "**Boosted Transformations**"¹³...

Proof. It is clear that (A) and (B) generate AND are generated by (1.1), (1.2), (1.3) and (1.4). It then just remains to check *stability*, i.e. that composing (A) or (B) to any of the transformations (1.1), (1.2), (1.3) or (1.4) will again give an element of either type (A) or (B) (note that as those are themselves (finitely) generated by elements of the form (1.1), (1.2), (1.3) and

¹³(although it may seem a bit odd... It would obviously refer to the Physical interpretation of elements of \mathfrak{M} (in the context of \mathbb{H}) in terms of *boosts* and *rotations*)

(1.4), we can see them as being (finitely) generated by *left-composition*, i.e. we will only need to check stability under *left-composition*). It is clear that Type (A) is stable under Affine transformations (...by definition) while the left-composition by $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ will clearly give transformations of type (B) (with $d = 0$). In the same way, it is clear that transformations of type (B) are stable under left-composition by maps of the form (1.1), (1.2) and (1.3), while, we also clearly have, in the case where $d = 0$, that an element of type (B) will turn into an element of type (A) after left-composition with $x \mapsto x^{-1}$. Hence it just remains to check stability w.r.t. $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ in the case of a transformation of type (B) with $d \neq 0$, i.e. show that

$$((axb + c)^{-1} + d)^{-1}, d \neq 0 \text{ can be written in the form } (Ax + B)(Cx + D)^{-1} + D$$

So it just remains to calculate¹⁴ :

$$\begin{aligned} ((axb + c)^{-1} + d)^{-1} &= (axb + c) \widehat{+} d^{-1} \\ &= (axb + c)(axb + c + d^{-1})^{-1} d^{-1} \\ &= (axb + c + d^{-1} - d^{-1})(axb + c + d^{-1})^{-1} d^{-1} \\ &= d^{-1} - d^{-1}(axb + c + d^{-1})^{-1} d^{-1} \\ &= ((-da)x + (bd) + (-dcd - d))^{-1} + d^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

□

Note that although all Möbius Transformations can be written in the way described above, there are actually many ways to (re-)write them, several of which may look quite "natural". More precisely, we here show some of them:

Remark 1.1.2.4. *Any Möbius Transformation can be (re-)written in the form*

$$x \mapsto (Ax + B)(Cx + D)^{-1} \quad (1.23)$$

Conversely, any invertible map of the form (1.23) can be rewritten in the form (A) or (B) as in Proposition (1.1.2.3), i.e. are Möbius transformations. The exact same remark can be made with maps of the form :

$$x \mapsto (x\tilde{C} + \tilde{D})^{-1}(x\tilde{A} + \tilde{B}) \quad (1.24)$$

Proof. It is easy to notice that Affine Transformations (A) can easily be rewritten in the form (1.23) or (1.24) :

$$\begin{aligned} axb + c &= (ax + cb^{-1})(0x + b^{-1})^{-1} \\ &= (0x + a^{-1})^{-1}(xb + a^{-1}c) \end{aligned}$$

¹⁴Reminding that $(x + y)^{-1} = x^{-1} +^{-1} y^{-1} = x^{-1} \widehat{+} y^{-1}$

Now we show that *Boosted Transformations* (B) can be written in the form (1.23) (as the exact same argument should be used to write it as in (1.24))

$$\begin{aligned}
(axb + c)^{-1} + d &= b^{-1}(ax + cb^{-1})^{-1} + d \\
&= b^{-1}(ax + cb^{-1})^{-1} + d(ax + cb^{-1})(ax + cb^{-1})^{-1} \\
&= (b^{-1} + d(ax + cb^{-1}))(ax + cb^{-1})^{-1} \\
&= (dax + (dcb^{-1} + b^{-1}))(ax + cb^{-1})^{-1}
\end{aligned}$$

Conversely, we now show that invertible transformations of the form (1.23), (i.e. the image of x being given by $(Ax+B)(Cx+D)^{-1}$) can be rewritten as in (A) or (B). In the case where $C = 0$, we clearly get an affine transformation:

$$(Ax + B)D^{-1} = AxD^{-1} + BD^{-1}$$

(noting that conditions such that the transformation be well defined and invertible automatically imply $A, D \neq 0$ [and clearly $D^{-1} \neq 0$ as $D \in \mathbb{K}$])
Now if $C \neq 0$, we can write :

$$\begin{aligned}
(Ax + B)(Cx + D)^{-1} &= (AC^{-1}Cx + AC^{-1}D - AC^{-1}D + B)(Cx + D)^{-1} \\
&= AC^{-1} + (B - AC^{-1}D)(Cx + D)^{-1} \\
&= AC^{-1} + (Cx(B - AC^{-1}D)^{-1} + D(B - AC^{-1}D)^{-1})
\end{aligned}$$

Where the second line clearly shows¹⁵ that a necessary and sufficient condition for such a transformation to be invertible is that $B - AC^{-1}D \neq 0$. \square

Based on this remark, I will now define 3 terms to refer to such represen-

¹⁵otherwise, one could still notice that $(B - AC^{-1}D = 0 \wedge D \neq 0) \implies (f(0) = f(\infty))$ while $(B - AC^{-1}D = 0 \wedge D = 0) \implies (f(x) = AX X^{-1} C^{-1} = AC^{-1} \forall x)$

tations :

Definition 1.1.2.5 (Left Form, Central Form, Right form). *Let $f \in \mathfrak{M}$, then we will say that f is written:*

- in its **Left Form** if it appears as :

$$x \mapsto (\tilde{D} + x\tilde{C})^{-1}(\tilde{B} + x\tilde{A})$$

(obviously with $(\tilde{C} = 0 \wedge \tilde{A} \neq 0 \wedge \tilde{D} \neq 0) \vee (\tilde{C} \neq 0 \wedge \tilde{B} - \tilde{D}\tilde{C}^{-1}\tilde{A} \neq 0)$)

- in its **Central Form** if it appears as one of those :

(A) $x \mapsto axb + c$

(B) $x \mapsto (axb + c)^{-1} + d$

(obviously with $a, b \in \mathbb{K}^\times, c, d \in \mathbb{K}$)

- in its **Right Form** if it appears as :

$$x \mapsto (Ax + B)(Cx + D)^{-1}$$

(obviously with $(C = 0 \wedge A \neq 0 \wedge D \neq 0) \vee (C \neq 0 \wedge B - AC^{-1}D \neq 0)$)

If I want to specify/emphasize that I am working with Möbius Transformations represented in a particular form, I may use the symbols $\triangleleft \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{M} \triangleright$ to respectively denote the Left, Central, and Right one¹⁶.

It is now easy to express the inverses:

Remark 1.1.2.6. *The inverse of a Möbius Transformation expressed in its Left (respectively Right) Form is very easily expressible in its Right(respectively Left) Form, while the inverse of an element of \mathfrak{M} naturally appears in \mathfrak{M} as well. More precisely, for*

$$\mathfrak{M} \triangleright \ni f : x \mapsto (Ax + B)(Cx + D)^{-1}$$

we get

$$\triangleleft \mathfrak{M} \ni f^{-1} : x \mapsto (A - xC)^{-1}(-B + xD)$$

¹⁶i.e. "Let $f \in \mathfrak{M} \triangleright$ " would thus mean "Let $f \in \mathfrak{M}$ and consider that it is written in its Right Form", keeping in mind, however, that $\triangleleft \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{M} \triangleright$ and \mathfrak{M} obviously still represent the same group \mathfrak{M}

Now represented in \mathfrak{M}^Δ , the inverse of

$$x \mapsto axb + c$$

is clearly

$$x \mapsto a^{-1}xb^{-1} - a^{-1}cb^{-1}$$

while the inverse of

$$x \mapsto (axb + c)^{-1} + d$$

is represented by

$$x \mapsto (bxa - bda)^{-1} - a^{-1}cb^{-1}$$

Proof. Just a trivial and standard calculus in which we write $y = f(x)$ and isolate x ... \square

Finally, note that in $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$, the composition of two maps

$$g : x \mapsto (ax + b)(cx + d)^{-1}$$

$$G : x \mapsto (Ax + B)(Cx + D)^{-1}$$

Is clearly given by

$$g \circ G : x \mapsto ((aA + bC)x + (aB + bD))((cA + dC)x + (cB + dD))^{-1}$$

Which can naturally be represented in terms of Matrices¹⁷

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (aA + bC) & (aB + bD) \\ (cA + dC) & (cB + dD) \end{pmatrix}$$

Those will be explored a bit more in-depth in Chapter 3, in a much more specific context. We will now leave those for a moment and look at what happens when a Topology is added to Algebraic Structures such as Division Rings...

¹⁷Note that invertible 2×2 Matrices with coefficients in \mathbb{K} with multiplication defined that way would obviously form a bigger group than \mathfrak{M} , i.e. The matrices used to represent Möbius Transformations are far from being unique... e.g. $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$

1.2 Topological Structure

Now that we have an Algebraic Structure, namely a Division Ring, it will always be possible to add a Topological structure to it. In this section, we look at what kind of nontrivial topology would be relevant to be considered, in order to bring new interesting properties, while also trying not to be too restrictive. Note that the Algebraic and Topological structures will interact with each other in a nontrivial way. More precisely, we will require that the topology on \mathbb{K} be compatible with its algebraic operations, i.e. that

$$\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{K} : (x, y) \mapsto x + y \quad (1.25)$$

$$\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{K} : (x, y) \mapsto x.y \quad (1.26)$$

$$\mathbb{K}^\times \rightarrow \mathbb{K}^\times : x \mapsto x^{-1} \quad (1.27)$$

be continuous. \mathbb{K} Is then called a Topological Division Ring¹⁸. Also note that the affine maps, and in particular (1.1), (1.2) and (1.3) will be homeomorphisms on \mathbb{K} while (1.27) will be a homeomorphism on \mathbb{K}^\times

1.2.1 Connected Components

As said, the Algebraic structure will impose some restrictions on the Topology we want to put on \mathbb{K} . A first example will be shown in the more general context of *Topological Rings* with -even stronger- consequences on Division Rings.

Lemma 1.2.1.1. *Let \mathbb{A} be a Topological Ring, then the connected component containing 0 (call it \mathfrak{C}) is a two-sided Ideal.*

Proof. As \mathfrak{C} is the *identity component*¹⁹ of $(\mathbb{A}, +)$, it is clearly an additive subgroup. Now let $a \neq 0$, as $x \mapsto ax$ and $x \mapsto xa$ are homeomorphisms, we have that

$$a\mathfrak{C} \approx \mathfrak{C} \approx \mathfrak{C}a$$

Thus $a\mathfrak{C}$ and $\mathfrak{C}a$ are connected and clearly contain 0, hence

$$a\mathfrak{C} \subseteq \mathfrak{C} \supseteq \mathfrak{C}a$$

□

¹⁸Similarly, we can also define -in the obvious way- a *Topological Ring* (just omitting (1.27)) as well as a *Topological Group*

¹⁹i.e. the connected component containing the identity; it is easy to see -by just using canonical homeomorphisms- that the "Identity Component" of a topological group is a subgroup of the latter : first notice that it will obviously contain all the inverses, then (using translations) it becomes clear that it will be stable under addition

Corollary 1.2.1.2. *Any topological Division Ring \mathbb{K} is always either connected or totally disconnected.*

Proof. As in a Division Ring, all the ideals (and a fortiori the two sided ones) are trivial, the connected component containing 0 can only be :

- either \mathbb{K} itself, in which case \mathbb{K} is connected
- or $\{0\}$, in which case it will be totally disconnected, as translations are homeomorphisms.

□

1.2.2 Hausdorff Topology

A well-known and very important topological property is the one of being Hausdorff (i.e. satisfying T2 : the second axiom of separability²⁰). It is very useful, for instance when studying limits of sequences, as it ensures that if a limit exists, it will necessarily be unique. We will see that this property is in fact naturally implied²¹ by the Division Ring structure, and thus need not be "postulated".

Lemma 1.2.2.1. *Any topological Group \mathbb{G} admitting a "closed singleton" $\{a\} = \overline{\{a\}}$ (or equivalently, being T1, as the property can be "translated" to all other points) is automatically Hausdorff (T2)*

Proof. If some $\{a\}$ is closed, so are all the other singletons as translations are homeomorphisms, (in other words \mathbb{G} is T1). Reminding that a necessary and sufficient condition for a space \mathbf{E} to be Hausdorff is that the *diagonal* :

$$\{(x, x) : x \in \mathbf{E}\}$$

be closed in $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{E}$, it suffices to see that the latter is simply the inverse image of the closed set $\{1\}$ under the continuous map

$$\mathbb{G} \times \mathbb{G} \rightarrow \mathbb{G} : (x, y) \mapsto xy^{-1}$$

thus itself closed

□

From this, we can immediately deduce :

Corollary 1.2.2.2. *Any non-connected (hence totally disconnected) division Ring is Hausdorff*

²⁰i.e. the existence of non-intersecting neighbourhoods for any pair of distinct points

²¹as long as the topology on \mathbb{K} is not the Trivial (=indiscrete) one

as totally disconnected spaces are clearly T1. Although this may already seem to be a fairly strong result, it actually turns out to be *even (much) better than that*. At first sight, *all* Topological Division Rings can clearly not be Hausdorff as there is an obvious, and literally *Trivial* counter-example:

- *Just take Any Division Ring and give it the Indiscrete Topology...*

Fortunately, this actually turns out to be ***the only*** counter-example

This can easily be shown in a quite direct and naive way, by just assuming that $\{0\}$ be not closed, taking a point in its closure, using the homeomorphism $x \mapsto ax$ to deduce that all the other points are in its closure, then use $x \mapsto x + c$ to deduce that it should be the same with any other point and thus any non-empty closed set is the entire space... There is however, a slightly more interesting way to get to the same result:

Lemma 1.2.2.3. *Let \mathbb{A} be a Topological Ring, and \mathcal{I} an Ideal. Then its closure $\overline{\mathcal{I}}$ is also an ideal.*

Proof. Let $x, y \in \overline{\mathcal{I}}$, then, by definition, any neighbourhood of x , as well as any neighbourhood of y will intersect \mathcal{I} (we show that this property still holds for $x + y$ and αx). Let V_{x+y} be any neighbourhood of $x + y$, then, as addition is continuous, there must exist a neighbourhood V_x of x as well as a neighbourhood V_y of y such that $V_x + V_y \subseteq V_{x+y}$, taking $a \in \mathcal{I} \cap V_x, b \in \mathcal{I} \cap V_y$, we get that $a + b \in V_{x+y}$ and as \mathcal{I} is an ideal, $a + b \in \mathcal{I}$. Now let us take $\alpha \neq 0$ and $U_{\alpha x}$ a neighbourhood of αx , as $X \mapsto aX$ is continuous, there exists a neighbourhood U_x of x such that $\alpha U_x \subseteq U_{\alpha x}$, taking $c \in \mathcal{I} \cap U_x$, we have that $\alpha c \in U_{\alpha x}$ as well as $\alpha c \in \mathcal{I}$ □

Corollary 1.2.2.4. *In particular, $\overline{\{0\}}$ is an Ideal of \mathbb{A}*

Corollary 1.2.2.5. *In particular, a Division Ring \mathbb{K} with a nontrivial Topology is always Hausdorff.*

Proof. As \mathbb{K} is a Division Ring -hence in particular, all its ideals are trivial- we clearly only have two possibilities :

- either $\overline{\{0\}} = \{0\}$, i.e. $\{0\}$ is closed, in which case Lemma (1.2.2.1) holds and \mathbb{K} is Hausdorff
- or $\overline{\{0\}} = \mathbb{K}$, but then, as $x \mapsto x + c$ is a homeomorphism, we will also have $\overline{\{c\}} = \mathbb{K}$ for any $c \in \mathbb{K}$, thus the only non-empty closed set is \mathbb{K} itself. In other words, \mathbb{K} has the Trivial (indiscrete) topology

□

1.2.3 Local Compactness

We have already seen that the best way to study the *Möbius group* of a Division Ring \mathbb{K} was to *add a point at ∞* , thus defining the *Projective Line* $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) := \mathbb{K} \cup \{\infty\}$. Now the latter can also naturally be given a topology in the case in which \mathbb{K} is itself a Locally Compact Division Ring. More precisely, if \mathbb{K} is a Topological Division Ring a topology on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) = \mathbb{K} \cup \{\infty\}$ can be defined by taking as open sets:

- The open sets of \mathbb{K}
- The sets of the form $\mathcal{K}^c \cup \{\infty\}$ where \mathcal{K}^c is the complement of a compact set \mathcal{K} of \mathbb{K}

It can easily be shown that this is a topology on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$, since compact sets of a Topological Division Ring are clearly always closed (as \mathbb{K} is Hausdorff or indiscrete), and also using the fact that compactness is stable by finite union as well as taking a closed subset. Now provided that \mathbb{K} be locally compact, we have that $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ is **compact** : to see this, it suffices to take an open cover of $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$, then one of the sets must contain ∞ , thus be of the form $\mathcal{K}^c \cup \{\infty\}$ it then suffices to take a finite subcover of \mathcal{K} . Note that if, besides from being Locally Compact, the topology of \mathbb{K} is not the indiscrete, \mathbb{K} is Hausdorff and **so is $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$** : as it then suffices to see that ∞ can be separated from any other point $x \in \mathbb{K}$ by taking a compact neighbourhood \mathcal{K}_x around x which clearly won't intersect $\mathcal{K}_x^c \cup \{\infty\}$. It is also trivial²² to check that the subset topology on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \setminus \{\infty\}$ will be the same as the one on \mathbb{K} . Also, it is clear that as the *Affine Transformations* are homeomorphisms²³ on \mathbb{K} and fix ∞ , they will extend to homeomorphisms on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$, and it will be shown later that this will also be the case for $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ (thus naturally turning the Möbius Group into a group of Homeomorphisms on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$). This way of giving a compact topology on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ -for \mathbb{K} locally compact- is (well) known as the *Alexandroff One-Point Compactification*. The fact of $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ being compact has nice implications, as the following lemma shows :

Lemma 1.2.3.1. *Let E be an infinite subset of a compact set \mathcal{K} , then E has a limit point in \mathcal{K}*

Proof. If no point in \mathcal{K} were a limit of E , then it would be possible for each $x \in \mathcal{K}$ to find an open neighbourhood U_x of x such that $U_x \cap E \subseteq \{x\}$. Then, as \mathcal{K} is compact, it would be possible to find a finite subcover U_{x_1}, \dots, U_{x_n} of \mathcal{K} , thus giving $E \subseteq \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ and so contradicting our assumption that E should be infinite. \square

²²as the \mathcal{K}^c will be open in \mathbb{K}

²³in particular open sets are sent to open sets, compact sets to compact sets

N.B. Local Compactness on \mathbb{K} actually brings much more than *just a (compact) topology on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ together with Lemma (1.2.3.1)* : using more advanced tools, we could deduce²⁴ the existence of a Haar Measure^[Gl] on \mathbb{K} , which would then induce a valuation^[We-Zi] on \mathbb{K} (that would be continuous and generate the same topology as the one on \mathbb{K}), which should then be either archimedean (iff \mathbb{K} connected) or non-archimedean^[Ca] (iff \mathbb{K} totally disconnected). Using tools of Valuation Theory^{[Ca][Ja][Sh]}, it would then be possible to deduce that \mathbb{K} would include a copy of \mathbb{R} in the case of an archimedean valuation, while in the case of a non-archimedean one, it would include either a copy of some p-adic field \mathbb{Q}_p (iff the Characteristic of \mathbb{K} is 0) or a copy of the field of formal Laurent series over a finite field $\mathbb{F} := \mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$ (thus iff prime Characteristic). Once we have such a subfield, a generalization of Riesz's lemma can be used to show that \mathbb{K} will actually be a finite-dimensional Algebra over that field... However, as already mentioned, this would require nontrivial results from different areas of Mathematics, such as Measure as well as Valuation Theory... We will still be able to achieve similar results by means of *elementary* topology. What will follow will mainly be based on Pontryagin's work^{[Po.DE][Po.EN]}.

Although many results will be proved in the quite "general" context of Locally Compact Division Rings, it should be kept in mind that our final purpose will be to explore the special case where \mathbb{K} is also Connected...

1.3 Continuous Division Rings

1.3.1 Basic definition

Given the remarks that have been made at the previous section, it would seem interesting to study *Locally Compact Division Rings*. However, as we would like the Topology in such a skew field \mathbb{K} not to be completely useless, we will exclude the *trivial* ones. It may be convenient to define a new term to refer to such structures (I will use the same terminology as Pontryagin).

Definition 1.3.1.1 (Continuous Division Ring). *A Topological Division Ring will be said to be **continuous** iff its topology is **Locally Compact** and **nontrivial**, i.e. **not discrete** and **not indiscrete***

Reminding that by Corollary (1.2.2.5) every *Continuous* Division Ring will automatically be Hausdorff. (Also note that -by Corollary (1.2.1.2)- one

²⁴provided that the topology on \mathbb{K} be "nontrivial" (not discrete nor indiscrete)

of the conditions in the definition will always be redundant²⁵)

It will also be useful to define :

Definition 1.3.1.2 (Continuous Closure). *A Topological Division Ring will be said to admit Continuous Closure iff it is not discrete and can be mapped isomorphically to a Topological Division Subring of a Continuous Division Ring (i.e. is embeddable in a Continuous Division Ring)*

Remark 1.3.1.3. *Note that if \mathbb{K} is a Continuous Division Ring, and \mathbb{A} a non-discrete Topological Division Subring of \mathbb{K} , then the closure $\overline{\mathbb{A}} \cup \{\infty\}$ is a closed subset of the compact set $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) = \mathbb{K} \cup \{\infty\}$ thus itself compact, implying that $\overline{\mathbb{A}}$ (with the induced Topology) is itself locally compact, while the fact that $\{0\}$ is closed in \mathbb{K} implies that it will also be closed in \mathbb{A} (preventing \mathbb{A} from having the indiscrete topology). In other words, the closure of \mathbb{A} is continuous, thus explaining the above-mentioned terminology. It will be shown later that the Continuous Closure of such a Division Ring does only depend on its own topology, and not on the Continuous Division Ring it is embedded in.*

1.3.2 First Countability and consequences

A first property we are going to look at is the one of being *first-countable* (i.e. that each point should have a *countable neighbourhood basis*), this property will be very useful in order to study sequences. In particular, it will allow us to construct converging sequences; and will also imply that *sequential compactness* and *countable compactness* be equivalent properties (which is not the case in general). Note that I may sometimes implicitly make use of the *Axiom of Countable Choice* (a quite intuitive, and much weaker condition than the *Axiom of Choice*)

Lemma 1.3.2.1 ([Po_EN] p.172, [Po_DE] p.191, part of *Lemma 1 §27*). *Let \mathbb{A} be a Topological Ring, let \mathcal{K} be a compact set in \mathbb{A} , and W any neighbourhood of 0, then, there exists a neighbourhood V of 0 such that*

$$\mathcal{K}V \subseteq W \tag{1.28}$$

Proof. (NB as $\emptyset V = \emptyset$ for any V , we can clearly suppose without loss of generality that \mathcal{K} is nonempty)

Since $x.0 = 0$ and as multiplication is continuous, it follows that for every

²⁵as connected \implies not discrete, while totally disconnected \implies not indiscrete

$x \in \mathcal{K}$, there exist open neighbourhoods V_x and U_x of 0 and x respectively such that :

$$U_x V_x \subseteq W$$

As \mathcal{K} is compact, the covering formed by all the U_x admits a finite subcover U_{x_1}, \dots, U_{x_n} . It is then clear than (1.28) is satisfied by just taking :

$$V = V_{x_1} \cap \dots \cap V_{x_n}$$

□

Corollary 1.3.2.2. *Let \mathbb{K} be a Continuous²⁶ Division Ring, \mathbb{K} cannot be compact.*

Proof. Assuming that \mathbb{K} be compact, and applying Lemma (1.3.2.1) with $\mathcal{K} := \mathbb{K}$, we get that for any neighbourhood of 0 -call it W - there must exist a neighbourhood of 0 -call it V - such that

$$\mathbb{K}V \subseteq W$$

As \mathbb{K} is Continuous, it is in particular not discrete, thus there exists $a \in V \setminus \{0\}$, and as \mathbb{K} is a topological Division Ring, $x \mapsto xa$ is a homeomorphism mapping \mathbb{K} to itself, thus

$$\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{K}\{a\} \subseteq \mathbb{K}V \subseteq W$$

So the only neighbourhood of 0 is $W = \mathbb{K}$, and -translating- the same holds for any other point, thus the only non-empty open set is \mathbb{K} itself; in other words, our *Continuous Division Ring* has the indiscrete topology : a contradiction □

Now we show that *Continuous Division Rings* are first-countable.

Lemma 1.3.2.3 ([Po_EN] pp171-172, [Po_DE] pp190-191, part. Lem1 §27). *Let \mathbb{K} be a Continuous Division Ring, then any point in \mathbb{K} admits a countable neighbourhood basis, in other words, \mathbb{K} is first-countable*

Proof. As \mathbb{K} is locally compact, 0 admits a compact neighbourhood \mathcal{K} , furthermore, as \mathbb{K} is non-discrete, as well as Hausdorff, it is clear that any neighbourhood must be infinite. Let us then take some infinite countable subset E of \mathcal{K} , then by Lemma (1.2.3.1), E admits a limit point in \mathcal{K} - call it c - which we can, without loss of generality, assume as being outside E (otherwise just consider $E \setminus \{c\}$ instead of E). Again, without loss of generality, it can be assumed that $c = 0$ (otherwise, just *translate*, taking $E - c$), hence we have a countable set²⁷ whose limit point is 0, let $\{b_1, \dots, b_n, \dots\}$

²⁶Note that although the property of being *locally compact* is not explicitly used in the proof, dropping this condition would not bring anything relevant, as *Compact Spaces* are always *Locally Compact* anyway

²⁷Not a *sequence* !

be an enumeration of any such set, and U any compact neighbourhood of 0 (or equivalently, an open neighbourhood having compact closure, if one prefers to work with open sets; note that here again, the existence of such a U is implied by Local Compactness). We shall show that that Ub_1, \dots, Ub_n, \dots constitutes a base at 0. Indeed, for any neighbourhood W of 0, we can apply Lemma (1.3.2.1) with $\mathcal{K} := U$ (or $\mathcal{K} := \bar{U}$ if U has been chosen as an *open neighbourhood admitting compact closure* instead of a *compact neighbourhood*), we get a neighbourhood V of 0 such that the equation (1.28) be satisfied. But since 0 is a limit point of the set $\{b_1, \dots, b_n, \dots\}$, it follows that V contains some b_m , implying that

$$Ub_m \subseteq W$$

In other words we have just constructed a countable basis of Neighbourhood at 0, and -once again- since translation are homeomorphisms, it follows that the same can be done at each point. \square

Remark 1.3.2.4. *Once we have such a basis $(U_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of neighbourhoods - at some point, say 0 for instance- it is always possible to construct a "new one" with the property of being ordered (i.e. forming a strictly decreasing sequence). For this, just define :*

$$V_n := U_0 \cap U_1 \cap \dots \cap U_n$$

thus getting a decreasing sequence of neighbourhoods²⁸ :

$$V_0 \supseteq V_1 \supseteq \dots \supseteq V_n \supseteq \dots$$

Then, as \mathbb{K} is Hausdorff, and not discrete, the sequence can clearly not be stationary, and it can then be assumed without loss of generality that $V_k \neq V_{k+1}$, $\forall k \in \mathbb{N}$ (otherwise, just take a subsequence), thus getting

$$V_0 \supsetneq V_1 \supsetneq \dots \supsetneq V_n \supsetneq \dots \tag{1.29}$$

Hence without loss of generality, it can always be assumed that any basis of neighbourhood satisfies (1.29)

Remark 1.3.2.5. *Given the previous remark, it is always possible²⁹, for any element in \mathbb{K} to construct a sequence of distinct elements converging to it. If c is the³⁰ limit of a converging sequence $(c_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, we will write :*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (c_n) = c \tag{1.30}$$

²⁸as the intersections are finite

²⁹As previously said, I will often make use of the Axiom of Countable Choice, although I will not keep mentioning it each time

³⁰as Continuous Division Rings are Hausdorff

Remark 1.3.2.6. *An elementary result of Topology tells us that in a First-Countable Topological space, the following equivalence holds :*

Sequential Compactness \iff ***Countable Compactness***

And thus in particular, we have :

Compactness \implies ***Sequential Compactness***

We will now seek to *improve* a bit those results :

Lemma 1.3.2.7 ([Po_EN] pp172-173, [Po_DE] pp191-192, part. *Lem1*§27). *Let F be any Countably Compact subset of a Continuous Division Ring \mathbb{K} , $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ a sequence of non-zero elements converging to 0, and W be any neighbourhood of 0, then*

$$\exists \nu \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n \in \mathbb{N}, (n \geq \nu) \implies (Fa_n \subseteq W \supseteq a_n F) \quad (1.31)$$

Proof. Assuming (1.31) does not hold, we then get :

$$\forall \nu \in \mathbb{N}, \exists n \in \mathbb{N} : (n \geq \nu) \wedge (Fa_n \not\subseteq W \vee a_n F \not\subseteq W)$$

From which we can clearly extract a subsequence (a'_n) such that for all n , we always have

- either $Fa'_n \not\subseteq W$
- or $a'_n F \not\subseteq W$

As at least one of the above (*non-*)inclusions will be satisfied for an infinite number of elements in (a'_n) , we can, without loss of generality extract a subsequence (b_n) such that

$$\forall n, b_n F \not\subseteq W$$

(otherwise, just take the other (*non-*)inclusion) It should thus be possible to find in F some sequence c_n such that

$$\forall n, b_n c_n \notin W \quad (1.32)$$

As F is assumed to be countably compact, thus sequentially compact, according to Remark (1.3.2.6), it will be possible to extract from (c_n) a subsequence (c_k) that will converge to some $c \in F$. But then, as multiplication is continuous, we would have :

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} (b_n c_n) = 0c = 0$$

Which clearly contradicts (1.32) □

Corollary 1.3.2.8 ([Po_EN] p.173, [Po_DE] p.192, part of *Lemma 1 §27*).
Let F be any closed countably compact subset of a Continuous Division Ring \mathbb{K} , then F is compact

Proof. As \mathbb{K} is continuous, we can find a compact neighbourhood W of 0 as well as a sequence $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of non-zero elements converging to 0. Then by the previous lemma, we can easily find some a_N such that

$$a_N F \subseteq W$$

as $a_N \neq 0$, $x \mapsto a_N x$ is a homeomorphism, i.e.:

$$a_N F \approx F$$

but then $a_N F$ is a closed subset of the compact set W , thus itself compact \square

Lemma 1.3.2.9. *Let F be any Countably Compact subset of a Continuous Division Ring \mathbb{K} , then F is closed*

Proof. Let $a \in \overline{F}$, then every neighbourhood of a intersects F . By Lemma (1.3.2.3) as well as Remark (1.3.2.4) we can find some strictly decreasing countable neighbourhood basis $(V_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of a , and the condition of a being in the closure of F is equivalent to all V_i intersecting F . Then we can construct a sequence $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in F converging to a by choosing (ACC) :

$$a_k \in F \cap V_k$$

As F is countably compact, thus sequentially compact according to Remark (1.3.2.6), we can find a subsequence converging to an element of F ; but as the limit is unique (\mathbb{K} Hausdorff), this limit is a , i.e.: $a \in F$ \square

Corollary 1.3.2.10. *Any countably compact subset of a Continuous Division Ring is in fact Compact*

Proof. Corollary (1.3.2.8) together with Lemma (1.3.2.9) \square

Remark 1.3.2.11. *To summarize, we now know that in a Continuous Division Ring, the following equivalence holds:*

$$\text{Compactness} \iff \text{Countable Compactness} \iff \text{Sequential Compactness} \quad (1.33)$$

Although those results tend to confirm the intuition, one must keep in mind that we are still working in a fairly abstract structure that could a

priori have very counter-intuitive features, thus even the most *obvious* properties should be carefully checked. (Actually, even very *strong* and familiar structures such as *p-adic Numbers* [which are, amongst others, Valued Local Fields] can sometimes behave in a fairly counter-intuitive manner, and note that those certainly do belong to the general class of Division Rings we are studying...)

Lemma 1.3.2.12. *Let \mathbb{K} be a Continuous Division Ring, and $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ a sequence of elements in \mathbb{K} , then the following are equivalent :*

1. $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ has no converging subsequence in \mathbb{K}
2. for any Compact³¹ \mathcal{K} , it is possible to find some $\nu \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\forall n \geq \nu, a_n \notin \mathcal{K}$
3. for any Compact Neighbourhood \mathcal{K}_0 of 0, it is possible to find some $\nu \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\forall n \geq \nu, a_n \notin \mathcal{K}_0$
4. (a_n) converges to ∞ in the sense of the -previously defined- topology on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$

Proof.

- (2) \iff (4) by definition
- it is trivial that (2) \implies (3) while the converse (3) \implies (2) is a consequence³² of Lemma (1.3.2.7)
- clearly $\neg(2) \implies \neg(1)$ by definition of sequential compactness, and $\neg(1) \implies \neg(2)$ by just taking a compact neighbourhood of the limit of the converging subsequence.

□

Note that the remark made about Lemma (1.3.2.7) [enlarging compact neighbourhoods of 0 in order to include other compact sets] can also be used to give us the following result :

³¹"Compact" obviously refers to "compact subset of \mathbb{K} " (Not $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$)

³²as it has been shown that any (countably) compact set can be "reduced" to fit in any neighbourhood of 0, by applying some homeomorphism $x \mapsto a_N x$, $a_N \neq 0$, then similarly applying the inverse map, a neighbourhood of 0 can be "enlarged" to include any compact \mathcal{K} of \mathbb{K}

Lemma 1.3.2.13. *Let \mathbb{K} be a Continuous Division Ring, let W be any Compact Neighbourhood of 0 in \mathbb{K} , and let $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence of non-zero elements in \mathbb{K} , converging to 0, then a countable neighbourhood basis of ∞ (w.r.t. the -previously defined- topology on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$) is given by :*

$$\{(a_n^{-1}W)^c \cup \{\infty\} : n \in \mathbb{N}\} = \{a_n^{-1}W^c \cup \{\infty\} : n \in \mathbb{N}\} \quad (1.34)$$

Thus in particular, $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ is first-countable

Proof. As \mathbb{K} is Continuous and W neighbourhood of 0, by Lemma (1.3.2.7), we have that :

$$\forall \mathcal{K} \text{ Compact of } \mathbb{K}, \exists N \in \mathbb{N} : a_N \mathcal{K} \subseteq W$$

then as a_N is non-zero, $x \mapsto a_N x$ is a homeomorphism, and taking the inverse map, we have :

$$\forall \mathcal{K} \text{ Compact of } \mathbb{K}, \exists N \in \mathbb{N} : \mathcal{K} \subseteq a_N^{-1}W$$

But as all³³ open neighbourhoods of ∞ w.r.t. the topology on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ are of the form :

$$\mathcal{K}^c \cup \{\infty\}$$

Each of them will include some

$$(a_N^{-1}W)^c \cup \{\infty\} = a_N^{-1}W^c \cup \{\infty\}$$

where $a_N^{-1}W$ is compact as W is assumed to be compact, and $x \mapsto a_N^{-1}x$ homeomorphism \square

Remark 1.3.2.14. *It might be useful to note that Lemma (1.3.2.7) actually gives us more detailed information about the countable basis of neighbourhoods at ∞ we just constructed, namely :*

$$\forall \mathcal{K} \text{ Compact of } \mathbb{K}, \exists \nu \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n \geq \nu, \mathcal{K} \subseteq a_n^{-1}W$$

thus according to what has just been said in Lemma (1.3.2.13), we get :

$$\forall V_\infty \text{ open neighbourhood of } \infty, \exists \nu \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n \geq \nu, a_n^{-1}W^c \cup \{\infty\} \subseteq V_\infty \quad (1.35)$$

³³see definition of the Topology on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ as well as remarks about stability of compact sets under finite union, and closed subset

Lemma 1.3.2.15. *The map $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \rightarrow \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) : x \mapsto x^{-1}$ is (bi)continuous, and thus a homeomorphism on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$, and so is any Möbius Transformation³⁴*

Proof. We already know that the map is continuous on \mathbb{K}^\times , so it only remains to check continuity at 0 and ∞ . As by Lemma (1.3.2.13), $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ is *first-countable*, *continuity* is equivalent to *sequential continuity* (also, *compactness* is equivalent to *sequential compactness*). Now if some sequence $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in \mathbb{K}^\times tends to 0, the inverse sequence $(a_n^{-1})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ must tend to ∞ . This can be proved means of sequential compactness, but also works by using the the previous Remark (1.3.2.14). Indeed, let W be some³⁵ Compact Neighbourhood of 0 not containing 1, then $1 \in W^c$ and by Remark (1.3.2.14), we have :

$$\forall V_\infty \text{ open nbh. of } \infty, \exists \nu \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n \geq \nu, a_n^{-1} \in a_n^{-1}W^c \cup \{\infty\} \subseteq V_\infty$$

Hence $(a_n^{-1})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ tends to ∞ , thus $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \rightarrow \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) : x \mapsto x^{-1}$ is (sequentially) continuous at 0. But as $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ is Compact and Hausdorff, a subspace is compact in $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$ if and only if it is closed in $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$, and as Compactness is stable by continuous image while the continuous preimage of a closed set is closed, it is easy to see that $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ maps \mathbb{K} to $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \setminus \{0\}$ homeomorphically, and since it is an involution, must clearly be continuous at ∞ . Thus $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \rightarrow \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) : x \mapsto x^{-1}$ is a homeomorphism, and, as it has already been noticed that it is also the case for any *Affine Transformation*, it follows that it also holds for any *Möbius Transformation*. \square

1.3.3 Principal Neighborhood and global Topology

Although we do not (yet) dispose of anything like a valuation or even a metric, we will still seek to define a kind of "unit ball" on a Continuous Division Ring \mathbb{K} . We will see that once this tool defined, it may be used to uniquely determine the entire topology of \mathbb{K} .

Lemma 1.3.3.1 (See [Po.EN] pp173-176, [Po.DE] pp192-195, *Lemma 2 §27*). *Let \mathbb{K} be a Continuous Division Ring, and for each $x \in \mathbb{K}$, construct the sequence of powers :*

$$(x^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}} = (x, x^2, \dots, x^n, \dots) \quad (1.36)$$

³⁴as previously defined

³⁵Note that such a W clearly exists given the previous lemmas and remarks (e.g.: local compactness+Hausdorff+reducing compact spaces such that they can fit into some neighbourhood of 0)

Define :

$$\mathbb{B} := \{x \in \mathbb{K} : \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (x^n) = 0\} \quad (1.37)$$

$$\mathbb{B}_0^{-1} := \{x \in \mathbb{K} : \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (x^n) = \infty\} \quad (1.38)$$

$$\mathbb{U} := \{x \in \mathbb{K} : \text{no subsequence of } (x^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}} \text{ tends to } 0 \text{ nor } \infty\} \quad (1.39)$$

Then, we have :

$$1. \mathbb{K} = \mathbb{B} \sqcup \mathbb{U} \sqcup \mathbb{B}_0^{-1}$$

$$2. \mathbb{U}^{-1} = \mathbb{U}$$

3. \mathbb{B} is an open set about 0, with compact closure $\overline{\mathbb{B}}$, \mathbb{U} is compact, and \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} is open

Proof. Let W be an open neighbourhood of 0 with compact closure \overline{W} , such that $1 \notin \overline{W}$, and let $F := \overline{W} \cup \{1\}$, we shall show that if some x satisfies the condition :

$$\exists k \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\} : x^k F \subseteq W \quad (1.40)$$

Then $(x^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}}$ converges to 0 :

It can be assumed without loss of generality that $x \neq 0$ (otherwise trivial), then from (1.40) together with the fact that the multiplication by x^k is a homeomorphism, used recursively we get :

$$W \supseteq x^k F \supseteq x^k W \supseteq x^{2k} F \supseteq x^{2k} W \supseteq \dots \supseteq x^{nk} F \supseteq \dots \quad (1.41)$$

In particular, the sequence $(x^{n_k})_{n_k \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}}$ is contained in W , and, as its closure is compact, a subsequence must converge in \overline{W} . We show that this limit cannot be other than 0 : suppose it were the case, then we would have a subsequence $((x^k)^{M_n})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converging to some $c \in \mathbb{K}^\times$, where M_n denotes a strictly increasing sequence of strictly positive integers. Then by definition,

$$\mathbb{N} \ni M_{n+1} > M_n > 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} ((x^k)^{M_{n+1}}) = c = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} ((x^k)^{M_n}) \quad (1.43)$$

Thus as c is nonzero and division is continuous (also note that powers of x^k commute together³⁶), we get :

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} ((x^k)^{M_{n+1}-M_n}) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{(x^k)^{M_{n+1}}}{(x^k)^{M_n}} \right) = \frac{c}{c} = 1 \quad (1.44)$$

³⁶thus in particular $\frac{A}{B}$ can be used to denote division when both terms commute

In other words, we have a sequence of strictly positive integral powers of x^k (thus all contained in W), converging to $1 \notin \overline{W}$, which contradicts the fact that \overline{W} Compact (hence closed). Thus any converging subsequence $((x^k)^{M_n})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ must converge to 0, and it is easy to deduce from that fact, that $(x^{nk})_{n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}}$ will itself converge to 0 (otherwise, just take $((x^k)^{M_n} W)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ as a basis of neighbourhood of 0, noting that $x^{km} \in (x^k)^{M_n} W \forall m > M_n$). Once we have that the sequence $(x^{nk})_{n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}}$ converges to 0, it suffices to multiply it by x, x^2, \dots, x^{k-1} to get that $(x^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}}$ converges to 0 i.e.: $x \in \mathbb{B}$. Now, conversely, if $x \in \mathbb{B}$, as $(x^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}}$ has to converge to 0, it follows from Lemma (1.3.2.7) that (1.40) will be satisfied. Thus

$$(x \in \mathbb{B}) \iff (\exists k \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\} : x^k F \subseteq W) \quad (1.45)$$

Note that, by definition of \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} , together with³⁷ Lemma (1.3.2.15), we have, as its name indicates, that $\mathbb{B}_0^{-1} = (\mathbb{B} \setminus \{0\})^{-1}$, from which we deduce :

$$(x \in \mathbb{B}_0^{-1}) \iff (x^{-1} \in \mathbb{B} \setminus \{0\}) \iff (\exists k \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\} : x^{-k} F \subseteq W) \quad (1.46)$$

We can now prove **(1)** : it is clear, according to the way they have been defined (and the fact that \mathbb{K} Hausdorff) that none of the three sets \mathbb{B}, \mathbb{U} , and \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} will intersect. Thus

$$\mathbb{U} \subseteq \mathbb{K} \setminus (\mathbb{B} \sqcup \mathbb{B}_0^{-1})$$

so it just remains to prove the other inclusion :

$$\mathbb{U} \supseteq \mathbb{K} \setminus (\mathbb{B} \sqcup \mathbb{B}_0^{-1})$$

i.e. : that if (x^n) does not itself converge to 0 nor ∞ no subsequence does so. But it is clear that if a subsequence should converge to 0 then (1.40) would be satisfied, and by (1.45), we would have $x \in \mathbb{B}$, and with the same argument, if a subsequence tended to ∞ so would do the entire sequence and $x \in \mathbb{B}_0^{-1}$. Now that **(1)** is proved, **(2)** becomes trivial, as obviously $0 \notin \mathbb{U}$ and we clearly have

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in \mathbb{K}^\times, (x \in \mathbb{U}) &\iff (x \notin \mathbb{B} \wedge x \notin \mathbb{B}_0^{-1}) \\ &\iff (x^{-1} \notin \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} \wedge x \notin \mathbb{B}) \iff (x^{-1} \in \mathbb{U}) \end{aligned}$$

It now just remains to prove **(3)** : we will show that if (1.40) is satisfied for some $x \in \mathbb{K}$, then it remains the case for some open neighbourhood X

³⁷we clearly use the fact that $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) \rightarrow \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K}) : x \mapsto x^{-1}$ is bicontinuous, and in particular sequentially continuous at 0 and ∞ , to show that x^n converges to 0 iff x^{-n} tends to ∞

around x ; in other words (by (1.45)) \mathbb{B} is open. First note that by continuity of

$$\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{K} : (x, y) \mapsto x^k y$$

as well as the fact that W is open and contains $x^k y \forall y \in F$ (i.e. is a neighbourhood of $x^k y$), we can find for all $y \in F$, open neighbourhoods V_y of y , X_y of x such that :

$$X_y^k V_y \subseteq W \quad (1.47)$$

A fortiori, the union of all V_y cover F , and as the latter is compact, we can extract a finite subcover V_{y_1}, \dots, V_{y_m} . Now defining $X := X_{y_1} \cap \dots \cap X_{y_m}$, the inclusion

$$\chi^k F \subseteq W$$

clearly holds for all $\chi \in X$. Now we know that \mathbb{B} is open (and obviously contains 0), the rest becomes quite trivial: clearly³⁸ $\mathbb{B} \setminus \{0\}$ is open, and so is \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} (as $x \mapsto x^{-1}$ is a homeomorphism). Also, as \mathbb{B} is an open neighbourhood of 0, then by Lemma (1.3.2.15), \mathbb{B}^{-1} is an open neighbourhood of ∞ in $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{K})$, thus of the form $\mathcal{K}^c \cup \{\infty\}$ where \mathcal{K} is a compact of \mathbb{K} . Hence

$$\mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} \text{ is compact} \quad (1.48)$$

Which clearly³⁹ implies that $\overline{\mathbb{B}}$ compact, as well as \mathbb{U} compact □

Before going any further, we will need to prove the claim that has been made in Remark (1.3.1.3). In order to do this, it might be relevant to keep in mind that (in a Continuous⁴⁰ Division Ring \mathbb{K}):

Remark 1.3.3.2.

1. If E is any set, and U open, then $E + U$ is open⁴¹

³⁸as we are Hausdorff, and in particular, T1

³⁹as $\mathbb{B} \subseteq \mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{B}_0^{-1}$, $\overline{\mathbb{B}}$ closed subset of a compact, same argument for $\mathbb{U} = (\mathbb{K} \setminus \mathbb{B}_0^{-1}) \setminus \mathbb{B}$ where \mathbb{B} open

⁴⁰as it is the case we are interested in, although it could obviously be formulated with much weaker conditions

⁴¹N.B.: This result is actually valid for any Topological Group, in particular, the composition law of any Topological Group is Open; so in a Topological Division Ring, we obviously have that addition is open on \mathbb{K} while multiplication is naturally open on \mathbb{K}^\times ; it is easy to see that multiplication is in fact also open on \mathbb{K} : indeed, if V is an open neighbourhood of 0 and W an open set not containing 0, then just write $VW = \bigcup_{w \in W} V\{w\}$, otherwise, if W contains 0, it is then clear that $VW = (V(W \setminus \{0\})) \cup \{0\} = V(W \setminus \{0\})$ as it already contains 0

2. If U, V are neighbourhoods of 0 , then $U + V$ is also a neighbourhood of 0 , in particular, if U is open, then $U + V$ is open
3. If $\mathcal{K}_1, \mathcal{K}_2$ are compact, then $\mathcal{K}_1 + \mathcal{K}_2$ is also compact
4. If V_n is a basis of neighbourhoods at 0 , then $V_n + V_n$ is also a basis of neighbourhoods at 0 , and in particular, we have :

$$\forall W \text{ neighbourhood of } 0, \exists V \text{ nbh of } 0 : V + V \subseteq W$$

Proof. (1) is trivial since $E = \cup_{x \in E} \{x\}$, then (2) is a direct consequence. (3) simply comes from the fact that $\mathcal{K}_1 \times \mathcal{K}_2$ is compact in $\mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{K}$ and addition is continuous. Now regarding (4), it suffices to notice that if F is a compact neighbourhood of 0 , then by (3) and (2) $F + F$ is also a compact neighbourhood, and if $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is any sequence that converges to 0 , we know by the previous Lemmas⁴² that $a_n(F + F)$ is a basis of (compact) neighbourhoods at 0 , but $a_n(F + F) = a_n F + a_n F$, and if $(V_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is any basis of neighbourhoods at 0 , we can always find some $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $V_m \subseteq a_n F$ hence clearly $V_m + V_m \subseteq a_n(F + F)$, i.e. $(V_n + V_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a basis of neighbourhoods at 0 , and in particular, any nbh. W of 0 can be split as $W \supseteq V + V$, for some V nbh. of 0 \square

Remark 1.3.3.3. *In what will follow, the term "isomorphism" will always refer to a "Topological Ring Isomorphism" (i.e. Algebraic Isomorphism + Homeomorphism). We will use the term "Algebraic Isomorphism" when we want to specify that the latter should not necessarily be continuous. Also, The term "Fundamental Sequence" (or Cauchy Sequence) will refer to sequences $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ that have the property that for any neighbourhood V_0 of 0 , there exists a natural number $N_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that*

$$\forall n, m \geq N_0, a_n - a_m \in V_0 \tag{1.49}$$

It is then easy to see that standard proofs can be adapted to show that every Converging sequence is Fundamental; and also that if a Fundamental Sequence has a converging subsequence, then the whole sequence converges, and in particular, any Continuous Division Ring is complete. (Note that to adapt the standard proofs that are commonly used in the context of Metric Spaces, one must replace the argument of "taking $\varepsilon/2$ " by one of the style of Remark (1.3.3.2), i.e. "splitting" $W \supseteq V + V$)

⁴²such as (1.3.2.7) or even (1.3.2.3)

Lemma 1.3.3.4 (See [Po_DE] pp174-176, recommended over [Po_EN] pp156-158, Prop. F §25). Let \mathbb{A} be a Topological Division Ring satisfying the First Axiom of Countability⁴³, let \mathbb{T} be an everywhere dense subring in \mathbb{A} , and let f be an isomorphism of the Topological Ring \mathbb{T} onto a Topological Subring \mathbb{T}' of a Continuous Division ring \mathbb{K}' . Then, there exists one and only one isomorphism ϕ from \mathbb{A} onto a Topological Division Subring \mathbb{A}' of \mathbb{K}' which coincides with f on \mathbb{T}

Proof. We will prove this by constructing ϕ . Let α be a fixed but arbitrary point in \mathbb{A} , then as \mathbb{T} is dense in \mathbb{A} (and as \mathbb{A} is first-countable), we can find some sequence $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of elements in \mathbb{T} converging to α . Now since $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is convergent in \mathbb{A} , it is fundamental, and therefore also fundamental in \mathbb{T} . But as f is an isomorphism between \mathbb{T} and \mathbb{T}' , letting $(a'_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} := (f(a_n))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, gives us a fundamental sequence in \mathbb{T}' . It is then also fundamental in \mathbb{K}' , and as the latter is Continuous⁴⁴, it must converge to some element $\alpha' \in \mathbb{K}'$. It is then obvious that α' is determined uniquely by α and does not depend on the choice of the sequence⁴⁵ Also, it is clear⁴⁶ that if $\alpha \in \mathbb{T}$, then $\alpha' = f(\alpha)$. Now if a continuous extension ϕ of f exists, it must then satisfy $\phi(\alpha) = \alpha'$ and is thus uniquely determined by f . Accordingly, we regard this relation as defining ϕ and show that the map thus obtained is an isomorphism of the Topological Division Ring \mathbb{A} onto $\mathbb{A}' := \phi(\mathbb{A}) \subseteq \mathbb{K}'$. We first show that ϕ preserves addition and multiplication, i.e. is a homomorphism of Division Rings :

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\alpha) + \phi(\beta) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(a_n) + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(b_n) \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(a_n + b_n) = \phi(\alpha + \beta) \end{aligned}$$

and the exact same argument holds to show that $\phi(\alpha)\phi(\beta) = \phi(\alpha\beta)$. This implies that the kernel of ϕ must be an ideal of \mathbb{A} , but as the latter is a Division Ring (i.e. only has Trivial ideals), while f is itself not trivial (bijection between \mathbb{T} and \mathbb{T}'), it follows that the kernel must be $\{0\}$, i.e. ϕ is injective, and thus an Algebraic Isomorphism between \mathbb{A} and $\mathbb{A}' := \phi(\mathbb{A})$. It thus remains to prove that ϕ is a homeomorphism, i.e. continuous and open. Once again, as translations are homeomorphisms, it will suffice to show that the property holds at 0. We start by proving continuity. Let W'

⁴³even though we formulate the Lemma in a more general context, we will obviously be interested in the case where \mathbb{A} is itself a Continuous Division Ring

⁴⁴in particular Locally Compact (as well as first-countable and Hausdorff)

⁴⁵otherwise, just take two such sequences and subtract them to "see what happens"...

⁴⁶as f is a homeomorphism between \mathbb{T} and \mathbb{T}' (or using the previous remark taking a constant sequence)

be an arbitrary neighbourhood of 0 in \mathbb{A}' , and let M' be an open (in \mathbb{A}') neighbourhood of 0 such that $\overline{M'} \subseteq W'$ (taking the closure w.r.t. \mathbb{A}'). Now define $V' := \mathbb{T}' \cap M'$ and $V := f^{-1}(V')$. V being open in \mathbb{T} , we can find some open neighbourhood M of 0 in \mathbb{A} such that $M \cap \mathbb{T} = V$. Continuity will then be proven once it is shown that $\phi(M) \subseteq W'$. For this, let α be an arbitrary element of M . Then, as \mathbb{T} is assumed to be dense in \mathbb{A} , there exists a sequence $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of elements in V converging to α , so that⁴⁷ $\phi(\alpha) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(a_n) \in \overline{V'} \subseteq \overline{M'} \subseteq W'$. It just remains to show that ϕ is open : in the same fashion, let W be an arbitrary open neighbourhood of 0 in \mathbb{A} , and M another open neighbourhood of 0 such that $\overline{M} \subseteq W$. Let $V := M \cap \mathbb{T}$ and define $V' := f(V)$. Here again⁴⁸, V' is open in \mathbb{T}' , and thus we can find some open neighbourhood M' of 0 in \mathbb{A}' such that $V' = M' \cap \mathbb{T}'$. We shall show that $\phi(W) \supseteq M'$, thus completing the proof. For this, let $\alpha \in M'$, then according to the definition of \mathbb{A}' , there exists a sequence $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that the sequence $(f(a_n))_{n \in \mathbb{N}} =: (a'_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of elements in \mathbb{T}' converges to α' . Since M' is open in $\mathbb{A}' \supseteq \mathbb{T}'$ and contains α , it follows that all terms of the sequence from some point must lie in $M' \cap \mathbb{T}' =: V'$, thus w.l.o.g. we may and do assume that the entire sequence lies in V' , but then, the sequence $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is contained in V , whence it follows that $\alpha = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n \in \overline{V} \subseteq \overline{M} \subseteq W$, which show that $\phi(W) \supseteq M'$ \square

Corollary 1.3.3.5 (See [Po.EN] p.158, or [Po.DE] p.176, *Proposition G§25*). *Let \mathbb{T} be a Topological Division Ring admitting Continuous Closure (i.e. as defined⁴⁹ at Def (1.3.1.2)), then the closure $\overline{\mathbb{T}}$ is uniquely determined by the Topology of \mathbb{T} , and thus does not depend on the choice of the Continuous Division Ring -say \mathbb{K} - it is embedded in.*

Proof. Let \mathbb{T} be a Topological Division Ring admitting Continuous Closure, and let $\overline{\mathbb{T}}$ be the closure of \mathbb{T} in some larger Continuous Division Ring. Let f be an isomorphism of \mathbb{T} onto a Topological Division Subring \mathbb{T}' of an arbitrary Continuous Division Ring \mathbb{K}' , then, as \mathbb{T} is obviously dense in $\overline{\mathbb{T}}$ which (by Remark (1.3.1.3)) is itself Continuous thus first-countable, the previous Lemma applies i.e. there is one and only one isomorphism ϕ of $\overline{\mathbb{T}}$ onto $\overline{\mathbb{T}'}$ which coincides with f on \mathbb{T} . \square

We can now explicitly define the *main tool* of this section :

Definition 1.3.3.6 (Principal Neighbourhood). *Let \mathbb{T} be a Topological Division Ring admitting Continuous Closure, and let \mathbb{B} be, as defined in Lemma*

⁴⁷closure still taken w.r.t. \mathbb{A}'

⁴⁸still because f is a homeomorphism between \mathbb{T} and \mathbb{T}'

⁴⁹i.e. *Non-discrete and embeddable in a Continuous Division Ring*

(1.3.3.1), the set of all $x \in \mathbb{T}$ whose sequence of positive integral powers converges to 0, then \mathbb{B} is called the **Principal Neighbourhood**⁵⁰ of \mathbb{T}

Lemma 1.3.3.7 (See [Po.DE] p.195, recommended over [Po.EN] p.176, Prop B §27). *The topology of a Topological Division Ring admitting Continuous Closure is uniquely determined by its Principal Neighbourhood. More precisely, let \mathbb{T} be a Topological Division Ring admitting Continuous Closure, and let \mathbb{T}' such that there be some **Algebraic** isomorphism $f : \mathbb{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{T}'$, suppose further that $f(\mathbb{B}) = \mathbb{B}'$, where \mathbb{B}, \mathbb{B}' denote the Principal Neighbourhoods of \mathbb{T}, \mathbb{T}' respectively. Then f is necessarily a homeomorphism, and therefore, an Isomorphism (of Topological Division Rings)*

Proof. Let b be any element in⁵¹ $\mathbb{B} \setminus \{0\}$, i.e. the sequence $(b^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to 0, since \mathbb{T} can be considered as a Topological Subring of some Continuous Division Ring, it follows [from Lemmas (1.3.3.1), (1.3.2.7)] that $(b^n \mathbb{B})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ form a basis of neighbourhoods at 0 in \mathbb{T} . Let now $b' := f(b)$, we know -from our assumption- that $b' \in \mathbb{B}' \setminus \{0\}$ i.e. $((b')^n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ also converges to 0 and thus $((b')^n \mathbb{B}')_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is also a basis of neighbourhoods of 0 in \mathbb{T}' . But as $f(b^n \mathbb{B}) = (b')^n \mathbb{B}'$, it clearly follows that f is bicontinuous at 0, and -once again using the argument that translations are homeomorphisms- bicontinuous everywhere, which proves what we wanted \square

Remark 1.3.3.8. *Note that combining Lemma (1.3.3.7) with Corollary (1.3.3.5) clearly tells us that \mathbb{B} uniquely determines the closure $\overline{\mathbb{T}}$.*

Remark 1.3.3.9. *Considering \mathbb{Q} as a Topological Subfield of \mathbb{R} (with its standard topology), we trivially have that the principal neighbourhood of \mathbb{Q} consists of all rational numbers r satisfying $|r| < 1$.*

(Also note that, although -for our purposes- we shall not use it, it is also easy to characterize the principal neighbourhood of \mathbb{Q} , this time seen as a topological subfield of \mathbb{Q}_p : it clearly consists of all rational numbers of the form $\frac{a}{b}p$, $a \in \mathbb{Z}, b \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$ such that p does not divide b , i.e. the Principal Ideal $\mathbb{Q} \cap p\mathbb{Z}_p$ of the Local Ring $\mathbb{Q} \cap \mathbb{Z}_p$)

Remark 1.3.3.10 (See [Po.EN] p.177 or [Po.DE] p.196, Proposition D §27). *Let $\mathbb{B}, \mathbb{U}, \mathbb{B}_0^{-1}$ be the subsets of some Continuous Division Ring \mathbb{K} as defined in Lemma (1.3.3.1), and let $x, y \in \mathbb{K}$ such that $xy = yx$; then, it immediately*

⁵⁰Note that the fact that \mathbb{B} is an Open Neighbourhood of 0 is known from Lemma (1.3.3.1)

⁵¹note that such a nonzero element does necessarily exist as \mathbb{B} is open, and \mathbb{T} is assumed Not to be Discrete

follows from the definitions of \mathbb{B} , \mathbb{U} , and \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} , that :

$$\begin{aligned} x, y \in \mathbb{B} &\implies xy \in \mathbb{B} \\ x \in \mathbb{B}, y \in \mathbb{U} &\implies xy \in \mathbb{B} \\ x, y \in \mathbb{U} &\implies xy \in \mathbb{U}, x^{-1} \in \mathbb{U} \text{ (i.e. Group)} \\ x \in \mathbb{B}_0^{-1}, y \in \mathbb{U} &\implies xy \in \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} \\ x, u \in \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} &\implies xy \in \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Much more could actually be deduced about the *Principal Neighbourhood*, as it seems quite clear that we have just defined an equivalent of an *Open Ball*. Actually, if we had taken the approach involving Valuation Theory, we would see that \mathbb{B} would exactly be the open ball -w.r.t. the Valuation- while \mathbb{U} would represent the "Unit Sphere". In particular, in the case of a non-Connected (i.e. Totally Disconnected) Division Ring, $\mathbb{B} \cup \mathbb{U}$ would⁵² form a subring (that would in particular be a *Local Ring*, as well as a *Principal Ideal Domain*). However, we will take another direction by exploring the structure of Connected Continuous Division Rings.

1.3.4 Connectedness and \mathbb{R} -Algebras

Theorem 1.3.4.1 (See [Po.DE] pp196-198, recommended over [Po.EN] pp177-179, Lem.3 § 27). *A Connected Continuous Division Ring \mathbb{K} always has Characteristic 0, and the closure $\overline{\mathbb{P}}$ of its Prime subfield \mathbb{P} is isomorphic with the field of Real Numbers. In other words, \mathbb{K} is an \mathbb{R} -Algebra.*

Proof. Let \mathbb{B} be the Principal Neighbourhood of \mathbb{K} , and $\mathbb{U}, \mathbb{B}_0^{-1}$ defined as in Lemma (1.3.3.1), then, we define⁵³ :

$$\mathbb{B}_n := \mathbb{B} + \mathbb{B} + \dots + \mathbb{B} \quad n \text{ times } (n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}) \quad (1.50)$$

Since \mathbb{B} is open, Remark (1.3.3.2) implies that \mathbb{B}_n should also be open, and, since $\overline{\mathbb{B}}$ is compact, it follows -still from Remark (1.3.3.2)- that

$$\overline{\mathbb{B}} + \overline{\mathbb{B}} + \dots + \overline{\mathbb{B}} \quad n \text{ times } (n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}) \quad (1.51)$$

is also compact, and is clearly⁵⁴ equal to $\overline{\mathbb{B}_n}$. Now we clearly have :

$$\mathbb{B}_m + \mathbb{B}_n = \mathbb{B}_{m+n} \quad (1.52)$$

$$\overline{\mathbb{B}_m} + \overline{\mathbb{B}_n} = \overline{\mathbb{B}_{m+n}} \quad (1.53)$$

⁵²as the valuation would be non-Archimedean

⁵³Note that obviously, as 0 is contained in \mathbb{B} , it follows that $(\mathbb{B}_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is an increasing sequence w.r.t. inclusion (it is a trivial remark, but necessary for the proof to work)

⁵⁴closed and includes \mathbb{B}_n so includes $\overline{\mathbb{B}_n}$ and the properties of the limit clearly imply that it cannot be strictly bigger

and we will show that

$$\overline{\mathbb{B}_m} + \mathbb{B}_n = \mathbb{B}_{m+n} \quad (1.54)$$

Indeed, let $x \in \overline{\mathbb{B}_m}$, $y \in \mathbb{B}_n$, then as \mathbb{B}_n is open, we can find an open neighbourhood V of 0 such that $y - V \subseteq \mathbb{B}_n$, but as $x \in \overline{\mathbb{B}_m}$, $x + V$, as a neighbourhood of x , will intersect \mathbb{B}_m i.e.

$$\exists v \in V : x + v \in \mathbb{B}_m$$

according to which, we get :

$$x + y = (x + v) + (y - v) \in \mathbb{B}_n + \mathbb{B}_m = \mathbb{B}_{m+n}$$

Now before going any further, it should be noted that, since the whole division ring \mathbb{K} is not itself compact⁵⁵ -thus different from any $\overline{\mathbb{B}_n}$ - but is connected⁵⁶ -so that the boundary of any open set different from \mathbb{K} itself should be nonempty- we have in particular :

$$\partial\mathbb{B}_n := \overline{\mathbb{B}_n} \setminus \mathbb{B}_n \neq \emptyset \quad (1.55)$$

We shall now show that for every positive integer $m \geq 2$, there exists an element $\omega_m \in \overline{\mathbb{B}}$ satisfying the condition :

$$m \times \omega_m \in \mathbb{K} \setminus \overline{\mathbb{B}_{m-1}} \quad (1.56)$$

Where $m \times \omega_m$ denotes⁵⁷ $\omega_m + \dots + \omega_m$ (m times) According to Remark⁵⁸ (1.3.3.2), let V be an open neighbourhood of 0 such that

$$\mathbb{B} \supseteq V + V + \dots + V \quad m \text{ times} \quad (1.57)$$

and select from the covering

$$\bigcup_{a \in \overline{\mathbb{B}}} (a + V)$$

of the compact set $\overline{\mathbb{B}}$ a finite subcover $(a_1 + V) \cup \dots \cup (a_k + V)$. Also, let $n := km$ and $z \in \partial\mathbb{B}_n$. Then,

$$z = x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n, \quad x_j \in \overline{\mathbb{B}}, \quad j = 1, \dots, n \quad (1.58)$$

⁵⁵For instance, by Corollary (1.3.2.2), (or simply by the many remarks about sequences tending to $\infty \notin \mathbb{K}$)

⁵⁶i.e. the only subset that is both Open and Closed is \mathbb{K} itself

⁵⁷as it is not yet proven, that $\mathbb{N} \subseteq \mathbb{K}$, so $m\omega_m$ may "not be well defined" as a priori $m \notin \mathbb{K}$, once we prove, that \mathbb{K} has Characteristic 0, I will obviously stop using " \times " and just write $m\omega_m$

⁵⁸Iterating (4)

Since there are $n = km$ of the elements x_j , and only k of the covering sets $(a_i + V)$, it follows that at least one of them -say, a_1 - must contain at least m of the x_j , and so without loss of generality -reenumerating if necessary- we can suppose that the elements x_1, \dots, x_m all belong to $a_1 + V$. Defining:

$$x := x_1 + \dots + x_m \in \overline{\mathbb{B}_m} \quad (1.59)$$

$$y := y_{m+1} + \dots + y_n \in \overline{\mathbb{B}_{n-m}} \quad (1.60)$$

we have (by definition of z):

$$x + y = z \notin \mathbb{B}_n \quad (1.61)$$

which combined with (1.54) necessarily implies that

$$x \in \partial\mathbb{B}_m \quad (1.62)$$

Furthermore, we have $x_i = a_1 + v_i$, $v_i \in V$, $i = 1, \dots, m$. Thus

$$m \times a_1 + v \in \partial\mathbb{B}_m \quad (1.63)$$

where $v := v_1 + \dots + v_m$, with $v_i \in V$, so that -by definition of V -

$$v \in \mathbb{B} \quad (1.64)$$

Then, using (1.54) again, we see that (1.56) must be satisfied for $\omega_m := a_1$

It is now easy to see that \mathbb{K} has characteristic 0 : indeed (1.56) implies in particular that

$$\forall m \in \mathbb{N}^{\geq 2}, m \times \omega_m \neq 0 \quad (\text{and in particular, } \omega_m \neq 0) \quad (1.65)$$

Which, dividing by ω_m gives

$$\forall m \in \mathbb{N}^{\geq 2}, m \times 1_{\mathbb{K}} \neq 0 \quad (1.66)$$

So, $\text{Char}(\mathbb{K}) = 0$ and $\mathbb{P} \simeq \mathbb{Q}$. We thus identify the prime subfield \mathbb{P} with \mathbb{Q} also naturally embedding \mathbb{Z} , \mathbb{N} etc, and thus writing nx for $n \times x$.

We can now show that the closure of the Prime Subfield of \mathbb{K} is actually isomorphic to \mathbb{R} (and so proving that \mathbb{K} is a \mathbb{R} -Algebra). For this, according to Lemma (1.3.3.7) as well as Remarks (1.3.3.8), (1.3.3.9), it will suffice to show that the Principal Neighbourhood of $\mathbb{P} \simeq \mathbb{Q}$ is can be described as

$$\left\{ \pm \frac{n}{m} : n, m \in \mathbb{N}, m > n \right\} \quad (1.67)$$

as it is obvious that $1 \notin \mathbb{B}, 0 \in \mathbb{B}, x \in \mathbb{B} \iff -x \in \mathbb{B}$, it will suffice to show that for all $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $m > n \geq 1$, we have:

$$\frac{m}{n} \in \mathbb{B}_0^{-1} \quad (1.68)$$

Suppose on the contrary $\frac{m}{n} \in \mathbb{B} \cup \mathbb{U}$, then, since $\frac{m}{n}$ commutes with every element in \mathbb{K} , it follows from Remark (1.3.3.10), that $\frac{m}{n}\mathbb{B} \subseteq \mathbb{B}$ hence $\frac{m}{n}\overline{\mathbb{B}} \subseteq \overline{\mathbb{B}}$, and in particular:

$$\frac{m}{n}\omega_m \in \overline{\mathbb{B}} \quad (1.69)$$

which multiplied by n gives:

$$m\omega_m \in \overline{\mathbb{B}_n} \quad (1.70)$$

thus contradicting (1.56) since it is assumed that $\overline{\mathbb{B}_n} \subseteq \overline{\mathbb{B}_{m-1}}$. Hence (1.68) holds, which by Lemma (1.3.3.1) implies that for any $n \neq m \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$, we have that⁵⁹

$$\frac{n}{m} \in \mathbb{B} \iff m > n \quad (1.71)$$

which is what we wanted. \square

1.3.5 Finite dimensionality from generalized Riesz Lemma

We have just seen that a Connected Continuous Division Ring \mathbb{K} always includes a copy of \mathbb{R} , (which is the closure of the Prime Subfield -which in particular, commutes with all elements of \mathbb{K} -), so in other words, is a Topological Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra (and in particular a Topological \mathbb{R} -Vector Space). We will now see that this result can be improved: Indeed, as our Division Ring is *Continuous*, i.e. in particular, *Locally Compact*, it turns out that its dimension over \mathbb{R} is actually finite. To prove this, we will use a slightly modified version of Riesz's Lemma. Note that, although in our assumptions, we will work with Connected Continuous Division Rings -in order to avoid having to prove any additional Lemma⁶⁰ about Topological Vector Spaces- it should be kept in mind that the *true* result is usually stated as follows:

A Hausdorff Topological \mathbb{R} -Vector Space is Locally Compact if and only if its Dimension is finite

For our purposes, we will allow ourselves to make stronger assumptions (although not necessary):

⁵⁹note that the *if and only if* comes from the fact that -by Lemma (1.3.3.1)- $\mathbb{B}_0^{-1} \cap \mathbb{B} = \emptyset$ while $\forall x \neq 0, x \in \mathbb{B} \iff x^{-1} \in \mathbb{B}_0^{-1}$

⁶⁰such as the ones we had required for Continuous Division Rings (e.g.: first-countability, explicit basis of Neighbourhoods etc...)

Proposition 1.3.5.1. *Let \mathbb{K} be a Connected Continuous Division Ring (hence also a Topological Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra, and in particular a \mathbb{R} -Vector Space), then, its dimension over \mathbb{R} is finite*

Proof. Let U be any Open neighbourhood at 0 with compact closure \bar{U} , then from the covering:

$$\bigcup_{x \in \bar{U}} x + \frac{U}{2}$$

select a finite subcover and call F the finite set of the corresponding x_i , i.e.

$$\bar{U} \subseteq F + \frac{U}{2} \quad (1.72)$$

Let V be the \mathbb{R} -Vector Space generated by the finite set F , we shall show that $U \subseteq V$. A fortiori, (1.72) implies :

$$U \subseteq V + \frac{U}{2} \quad (1.73)$$

Whence $\frac{U}{2} \subseteq V + \frac{U}{4}$, which can be recombined with (1.73) recursively to give:

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, U \subseteq V + \frac{U}{2^n} \quad (1.74)$$

Now let $x \in U$, then $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \exists x_n \in V, y_n \in \frac{U}{2^n} : x = x_n + y_n$. But as $(\frac{U}{2^n})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ forms a basis of neighbourhoods at 0, clearly, $y_n \rightarrow 0$ and so $x_n \rightarrow x$. Thus $x \in \bar{V}$, but as the latter is a Finite-Dimensional \mathbb{R} -Vector space, we have $\bar{V} = V$, and so $U \subseteq V$. Now, as for a sequence $(c_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of nonzero elements in $\mathbb{R} \subseteq \mathbb{K}$ converging to 0, we will have that, for any $x \in \mathbb{K}$, the sequence $(c_n x)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ will also converge to 0 whence:

$$\forall x \in \mathbb{K}, \exists n_0(x) \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n \geq n_0(x), c_n x \in U$$

and so

$$\forall x \in \mathbb{K}, \exists n_0(x) \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n \geq n_0(x), x \in \frac{U}{c_n}$$

but as V is a \mathbb{R} -vector space including U , it also includes all $\frac{U}{c_n}$ and thus includes \mathbb{K} □

Remark 1.3.5.2. *The following remarks could be made about Proposition (1.3.5.1):*

- *As already mentioned, "Connected Continuous Division Ring" is a too strong condition : the same proof works for Hausdorff Topological \mathbb{R} -Vector Spaces (just checking that those also have all the "good properties" required for the proof to work [which we already checked for Continuous Division Rings])*

- At Thm (1.3.4.1), we only treated the Connected case: a similar proof -at least, also involving the Principal Neighbourhood- can be made for the more General Case^{[Po-DE][Po-EN]} (e.g. if \mathbb{K} is Continuous, Totally Disconnected and has Characteristic 0, then it is an algebra over the p -adics \mathbb{Q}_p), and the proof of Proposition (1.3.5.1) can also be adapted (e.g.: for p -adic numbers, instead of dividing by 2, multiply by p ...)

Now that we know that all Connected Continuous Division Rings are Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebras, studying this -a priori- larger class will be relevant if we want to classify Connected Continuous Division Rings. In fact, it turns out that we can very easily classify all Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebras⁶¹: this is known as *Frobenius Theorem*. Note that, as the following remark suggests, the fact that our Finite Dimensional \mathbb{R} -Algebra should admit Division need not be postulated, provided that we impose the -a priori weaker- condition that it should not have Zero-Divisors

Remark 1.3.5.3. Any Finite-Dimensional Algebra over a (commutative) field \mathbb{K}_C (and so in particular also for $\mathbb{K}_C = \mathbb{R}$) is a Division Algebra if and only if it has no Zero-Divisors (i.e. is an Integral Domain)

Proof. As the *only if* is trivial, we prove the *if* part:

Let \mathbb{A} be a Finite-Dimensional \mathbb{K}_C -Algebra with no Zero-Divisor, then for every $a \in \mathbb{A} \setminus \{0\}$, the \mathbb{K}_C -linear endomorphism :

$$f_a : x \mapsto ax$$

Must be injective, and so -as the dimension is finite- surjective by the Rank-Nullity Theorem, so in particular, there is always a x such that $ax = 1$ \square

We will now try to characterize those structures, and relate them more closely to *Continuous Division Rings*.

Remark 1.3.5.4. In what will follow, we will work on a Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra \mathbb{K} , for which we denote -as previously- the multiplicative identity $1_{\mathbb{K}} =: 1$ and identify its real multiples with \mathbb{R} , then, if we write -something such as- $x \leq 0$, we obviously -implicitly- assume that $x \in \mathbb{R}$. Also, as \mathbb{K} is an \mathbb{R} -Algebra, it can in particular be seen as a \mathbb{R} -Vector Space, and every $a \in \mathbb{K}$ naturally defines -by left multiplication- a \mathbb{R} -linear endomorphism $x \mapsto ax$, which of course can itself be seen as a Real Matrix as the dimension of \mathbb{K} over \mathbb{R} is finite. We can thus identify a to that endomorphism and may then speak about its **Trace**, **Determinant**, and **Characteristic**

⁶¹Note that I am always referring to **Associative** Algebras.

(as well as Minimal) **Polynomial**, that we denote by $\mathbf{Tr}(a)$, $\mathbf{Det}(a)$, and \mathbf{p}_a respectively.

Finally, for any $z \in \mathbb{C}$, we can define the following Real Quadratic Polynomial:

$$Q(z; x) := (x - z)(x - \bar{z}) = x^2 - 2\operatorname{Re}(z)x + |z|^2 \quad (1.75)$$

noting that if $z \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{R}$, $Q(z; x)$ is clearly irreducible over \mathbb{R}

Now that those remarks have been made, we can prove the following (standard) Lemma:

Lemma 1.3.5.5. *Let \mathbb{K} be a Finite-Dimensional Division⁶² \mathbb{R} -Algebra, and \mathbf{V} be the set of all elements v of \mathbb{K} satisfying $v^2 \leq 0$, then \mathbf{V} is a \mathbb{R} -Vector Subspace of \mathbb{K} with codimension 1. Furthermore, we have :*

$$\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R} \oplus \mathbf{V} \quad (1.76)$$

and so in particular, \mathbf{V} generates \mathbb{K} as an \mathbb{R} -Algebra.

Proof. Let $a \in \mathbb{K}$ and let p_a be its Characteristic Polynomial; then by the Fundamental Theorem of Algebra, we have :

$$p_a(x) = (x - t_1) \dots (x - t_r)(x - z_1)(x - \bar{z}_1) \dots (x - z_s)(x - \bar{z}_s) \quad (1.77)$$

which in terms of⁶³ $Q(z; x)$ gives:

$$p_a(x) = (x - t_1) \dots (x - t_r)Q(z_1; x) \dots Q(z_s; x) \quad (1.78)$$

Noting that, since the z_j are in $\mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{R}$, the $Q(z_j; x)$ are all irreducible over \mathbb{R} . By Cayley-Hamilton Theorem, we have $p_a(a) = 0$, and as \mathbb{K} does not have Zero-Divisors, we necessarily have that one of the factors must be zero, i.e. either one of the $(a - t_i)$ or one of the $Q(z_j; a)$. In the first case, a is real, while in the second case, we have that (for some j) $Q(z_j; x)$ must be the Minimal Polynomial of a . Now as $p_a(x)$ has the same roots as the Minimal Polynomial of a (only multiplicities may of course vary), and since it is real, it follows that (for some $k \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}$)

$$p_a(x) = Q(z_j; x)^k = (x^2 - 2\operatorname{Re}(z_j)x + |z_j|^2)^k \quad (1.79)$$

⁶²or equivalently, as in Remark (1.3.5.3), a Finite-Dimensional \mathbb{R} -Algebra with no Zero-Divisors

⁶³as defined in Remark (1.3.5.4)

Since p is the Characteristic Polynomial of a and has degree⁶⁴ $2k$, we know that the coefficient of the term in x^{2k-1} should, up to a sign, give the *Trace* of a . We thus immediately deduce from (1.79) that

$$\text{Tr}(a) = 0 \iff \text{Re}(z_j) = 0 \quad (1.80)$$

which -recombined with the definition of the Minimal Polynomial of a - gives

$$\text{Tr}(a) = 0 \iff a^2 = -|z_j|^2 < 0 \quad (1.81)$$

in other words, \mathbf{V} is the set of all elements whose trace is zero, and therefore a \mathbb{R} -Vector Subspace of \mathbb{K} . Moreover, as $x \mapsto \text{Tr}(x)$ is a nontrivial linear form -whose kernel is \mathbf{V} -, it follows that \mathbf{V} has codimension 1, clearly implying that $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R} \oplus \mathbf{V}$. In particular, \mathbf{V} generates \mathbb{K} as an \mathbb{R} -Algebra. \square

Now, before classifying all such Algebras, we will seek to describe some of their general features... (Note that in what will follow, \mathbb{K} , \mathbb{R} and \mathbf{V} will be defined and used as in Lemma (1.3.5.5))

Definition 1.3.5.6. *Let $v, w \in \mathbf{V}$, then we call **Inner Product of v and w** and denote by $\langle v|w \rangle$ the following expression:*

$$\langle v|w \rangle := - \left(\frac{vw + wv}{2} \right) \quad (1.82)$$

Proposition 1.3.5.7. *Let $v, w \in \mathbf{V}$, then $\langle v|w \rangle \in \mathbb{R}$. Furthermore, $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle$ is \mathbb{R} -Bilinear, Symmetric, and Positive Definite; in other words, the bilinear form:*

$$\langle v|w \rangle : \mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : (v, w) \mapsto \langle v|w \rangle = - \left(\frac{vw + wv}{2} \right) \quad (1.83)$$

defines, as its name indicates, an Inner Product on the \mathbb{R} -Vector Space \mathbf{V}

Proof. The fact that it is Bilinear and Symmetric is trivial. Now the fact that $\forall v, w \in \mathbf{V}, \langle v|w \rangle \in \mathbb{R}$, can immediately be deduced from the following (*Pythagoras-like*) identity:

$$vw + wv = (v + w)^2 - v^2 - w^2 \quad (1.84)$$

and it is clearly Positive Definite as $\langle v|v \rangle = -v^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{\geq 0}$ (and \mathbb{K} has no Zero-Divisors, i.e. in particular no nilpotent) \square

⁶⁴note that this already suggests that the dimension of any Finite Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra more "complex" than \mathbb{R} itself should have even dimension over \mathbb{R}

It follows that we can now talk about orthogonality⁶⁵ in \mathbf{V} . (Note that this is obviously *only relevant* for *higher Dimensional* \mathbb{R} -Algebras than \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C})

Remark 1.3.5.8. *It might be useful to have in mind that, for $v \in \mathbf{V}, w \in \mathbf{V} \setminus \{0\}, x \in \mathbb{K}$ we have :*

1. $(x^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{\leq 0} \iff x \in \mathbf{V}), \quad (x^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{\geq 0} \iff x \in \mathbb{R})$
2. $v \perp w \iff vw = -wv \iff w^{-1}v = -vw^{-1} \iff v \perp w^{-1}$
3. $v \parallel w \iff vw = wv \iff vw^{-1} = w^{-1}v \iff v \parallel w^{-1}$
4. $xw = -wx \implies x \in \mathbf{V} \quad (\text{and so } x \perp w)$
5. $vw - wv$ anticommutes with both v, w and so $(vw - wv)$ is in \mathbf{V} and orthogonal to both v and w

Proof. **(1)** is just the definition of \mathbf{V} combined with the fact that (for $t \in \mathbb{R}, v \in \mathbf{V}$) we have

$$((t + v)^2 = t^2 + 2tv + v^2 \in \mathbb{R}) \iff (2tv = 0) \iff (t = 0 \vee v = 0)$$

(2) is just the definition of orthogonality combined with the fact that⁶⁶ $ab = -ba \iff a^{-1}(ab)a^{-1} = a^{-1}(-ba)a^{-1}$

For **(3)** [\implies] is trivial so we show [\impliedby] by combining **(1)** with the remark in **(2)** (about inverses) : indeed, supposing that $vw = wv$, we have to show that there exists $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $v = \lambda w$, i.e. $vw^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}$, but by (1), this is equivalent to showing that its square is positive, thus (using the assumption that v commutes with w and so with w^{-1}) we calculate $(vw^{-1})^2 = vw^{-1}vw^{-1} = v^2(w^{-1})^2$ which is the product of two negative numbers, thus positive.

For **(4)**, write $x = t + v$, $t \in \mathbb{R}, v \in \mathbf{V}$ then⁶⁷,

$$\begin{aligned} (t + v)w = -w(t + v) &\iff 2tw = -(vw + wv) = 2\langle v|w \rangle \\ &\implies tw \in \mathbf{V} \cap \mathbb{R} = \{0\} \\ &\implies t = 0 \quad (\text{as it is assumed that } w \neq 0) \end{aligned}$$

⁶⁵We will obviously write $v \perp w$ for $\langle v|w \rangle = 0$ and $v \parallel w$ when $((v = 0) \vee (\exists \lambda \in \mathbb{R} : w = \lambda v))$. Also, from here, it can already be seen that any Finite Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra strictly bigger than \mathbb{C} will be noncommutative

⁶⁶and note that obviously, $w \in \mathbf{V} \setminus \{0\} \iff w^{-1} \in \mathbf{V} \setminus \{0\}$ as $w^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{<0} \iff w^{-2} \in \mathbb{R}^{<0}$

⁶⁷Note that this can actually be generalized to $w \in \mathbb{K}^\times$ rather than $w \in \mathbf{V} \setminus \{0\}$

Finally, **(5)** is clearly satisfied as $v(vw - wv) = v^2w - vvw = wv^2 - vvw = -(wv - vw)v$, so by **(4)**, it is in \mathbf{V} , and by **(2)** (or just the definition of $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle$), it is orthogonal to v and w \square

Corollary 1.3.5.9. *Let $v, w \in \mathbf{V}$, then it is always possible to "split" the product vw in the following way:*

$$vw = \frac{vw + wv}{2} + \frac{vw - wv}{2} \quad (1.85)$$

Where

$$\frac{vw + wv}{2} \in \mathbb{R} \quad (1.86)$$

$$\frac{vw - wv}{2} \in \mathbf{V} \quad (\text{and orthogonal to both } v, w) \quad (1.87)$$

Proof. Direct consequence from **(5)** at Remark (1.3.5.8) together with Proposition (1.3.5.7) \square

This will now allow us to naturally define a *Conjugation* on \mathbb{K} (i.e. \mathbb{K} is an *Involutive Algebra*)

Definition 1.3.5.10 (Conjugation). *We call **Conjugation** and denote by $\bar{\cdot}$ the \mathbb{R} -linear involution on \mathbb{K} that fixes elements of \mathbb{R} and act on \mathbf{V} as the additive inversion, i.e.*

$$\bar{\cdot} : \mathbb{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{K} : x = t + v \mapsto \bar{x} := t - v, \quad (t \in \mathbb{R}, v \in \mathbf{V}) \quad (1.88)$$

\bar{x} is then naturally referred to as the **Conjugate** of x

Remark 1.3.5.11. *Note that the conjugation can obviously be used to describe the **Real**⁶⁸ and **Imaginary**⁶⁹ Parts of an element of \mathbb{K} , i.e. its linear projections on \mathbb{R} and \mathbf{V} respectively:*

$$Re(x) := P_{\mathbb{R}}^+(x) = \frac{x + \bar{x}}{2} \quad (1.89)$$

$$Im(x) := P_{\mathbf{V}}^+(x) = \frac{x - \bar{x}}{2} \quad (1.90)$$

Lemma 1.3.5.12. *Let $v, w \in \mathbf{V}$, then:*

$$\overline{vw} = wv \quad (1.91)$$

⁶⁸or "Scalar" (or "time-like")

⁶⁹or "Vector" (or "space-like")

Proof. According to Corollary (1.3.5.9), we write:

$$\begin{aligned}\overline{vw} &= \frac{vw + wv}{2} + \frac{vw - wv}{2} \\ &= \frac{vw + wv}{2} - \left(\frac{vw - wv}{2} \right) \\ &= wv\end{aligned}$$

□

Proposition 1.3.5.13. *Let $x, y \in \mathbb{K}$, then*

$$\overline{xy} = \bar{y}\bar{x} \quad (1.92)$$

In other words, The \mathbb{R} -linear Involution $\bar{\cdot} : \mathbb{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{K} : x \mapsto \bar{x}$ is also a multiplicative antiautomorphism (thus naturally giving $(\mathbb{K}, \bar{\cdot})$ the structure of an Involution Algebra)

Proof. We shall use Lemma (1.3.5.12) : write:

$$\begin{aligned}\overline{xy} &= \overline{(s+v)(t+w)}, \quad s, t \in \mathbb{R}, v, w \in \mathbf{V} \\ &= \overline{st + sw + tv + vw} \\ &= st - sw - tv + wv \\ &= (t-w)(s-v) \\ &= \bar{y}\bar{x}\end{aligned}$$

□

Noting that for all $x \in \mathbb{K}$ (with $x = t + v, t \in \mathbb{R}, v \in \mathbf{V}$), we have: $x\bar{x} = \bar{x}x = t^2 - v^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{\geq 0}$ we can now define an *Archimedean Valuation* (or *Absolute Value* or *modulus*) on \mathbb{K} :

Definition 1.3.5.14. *We call valuation the map:*

$$|\cdot| : \mathbb{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\geq 0} : x \mapsto |x| := \sqrt{x\bar{x}} = \sqrt{\bar{x}x} \quad (1.93)$$

and shall call $|x|$ the valuation (or absolute value, or modulus) of x

Remark 1.3.5.15. *It is clear that for $v \in \mathbf{V}$, we always have*

$$|v|^2 = -v^2 = \langle v|v \rangle \quad (1.94)$$

Then it is trivial⁷⁰ to see (considering \mathbb{K} as a \mathbb{R} -Vector space dimension n) that $|\cdot|$ is exactly the -standard- Euclidean Norm on $\mathbb{K} \simeq_{\mathbb{R}} \mathbb{R}^n$. (where $\simeq_{\mathbb{R}}$ denotes an isomorphism of \mathbb{R} -Vector Spaces)

⁷⁰as for $x = t + v, x\bar{x} = t^2 - v^2$

Lemma 1.3.5.16. $|\cdot| : \mathbb{K}^\times \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{>0}$ is a multiplicative epimorphism⁷¹.

Proof. It just comes from the fact that

$$xy\overline{xy} = xy\overline{y}\overline{x} = x(y\overline{y})\overline{x} = x\overline{xy}\overline{y}$$

(also surjectivity is trivial) □

Corollary 1.3.5.17. As its name indicates, $|\cdot|$ defines an Archimedean Valuation (or "Absolute Value" or "Modulus") on \mathbb{K} . i.e. it satisfies for all $x, y \in \mathbb{K}$:

1. $|x| \geq 0$
2. $|x| = 0 \iff x = 0$
3. $|x + y| \leq |x| + |y|$
4. $|xy| = |x||y|$

(and also $\exists x, y \in \mathbb{K} : |x + y| > \max\{|x|, |y|\}$ (Archimedean))

Proof. (1), (2), (3) are obvious consequences from the definition of $|\cdot|$ and the fact that, according to Remark (1.3.5.15), it can be regarded as the Euclidean Norm. (4) is just Lemma (1.3.5.16) combined with the trivial fact that $|0y| = 0 = |0||y|$. Note that it obviously does not satisfy the *Ultrametric Inequality* as $|1 + 1| = 2 > 1$ □

Remark 1.3.5.18. Clearly, seen as a Norm, $|\cdot|$ naturally induces a Topology on $\mathbb{K} \simeq_{\mathbb{R}} \mathbb{R}^n$, which is simply the Standard Topology. In other words, \mathbb{K} can naturally be given the structure of a Topological \mathbb{R} -Vector Space, which we know is Connected and Locally Compact (and obviously not indiscrete). Proving that multiplication and inversion are continuous (which intuitively "should logically be the case" as $|\cdot|$ is also a multiplicative endomorphism) would then give us the structure of a Connected Continuous Division Ring

Lemma 1.3.5.19. Let \mathbb{K} be a Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{K} \times \mathbb{K} &\rightarrow \mathbb{K} : (x, y) \mapsto xy \\ \mathbb{K}^\times &\rightarrow \mathbb{K}^\times : x \mapsto x^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

are continuous w.r.t. the topology induced by $|\cdot|$

In other words, \mathbb{K} together with the topology generated by $|\cdot|$ is a Connected Continuous Division Ring.

⁷¹Note that its kernel $\ker |\cdot|$ can be referred to as the *Unit Sphere* -which by definition is a multiplicative subgroup of \mathbb{K}^\times -

Proof. This is certainly far from being the best proof, but it is quite elementary and intuitive (although not very subtle):

As the topology we are working with is the one of \mathbb{R}^n , it suffices to prove sequential continuity : For multiplication, we shall show that

$$(x_n, y_n) \rightarrow (x, y) \implies x_n y_n \rightarrow xy$$

but this is clear as

$$\begin{aligned} |x_n y_n - xy| &= |(x_n - x + x)(y_n - y + y) - xy| \\ &= |(x_n - x)(y_n - y) + x(y_n - y) + (x_n - x)y| \\ &\leq |(x_n - x)||y_n - y| + |x||y_n - y| + |(x_n - x)||y| \end{aligned}$$

which clearly converges to 0. Now for the inversion $x \rightarrow x^{-1}$, just write (for a sequence $(x_n)_n \in \mathbb{N}$ of elements in \mathbb{K}^\times converging to some $x \in \mathbb{K}^\times$):

$$|x_n^{-1} - x^{-1}| = |x_n^{-1}(x - x_n)x^{-1}| = |x_n|^{-1}|x_n - x||x|^{-1}$$

which obviously converges to 0 as well □

Corollary 1.3.5.20. *Every Connected Continuous Division Ring is a Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra, while conversely, every Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra can naturally be given a structure of Connected Continuous Division Ring. Also, it is clear that the topology on a Connected Continuous Division Ring is the one of its Vector Space $\approx \mathbb{R}^n$ i.e. two different Connected Continuous Division Rings cannot correspond to the "same" Algebraic structure (i.e. Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra). (If not clear, it is still possible to check that, for a Connected Continuous Division Ring \mathbb{K} , the valuation $|\cdot|$ associated to its corresponding Algebra is clearly continuous⁷² w.r.t. the topology on \mathbb{K} , and thus uniquely determines its Principal Neighbourhood as $x^n \rightarrow 0 \iff |x|^n \rightarrow 0$). The following concepts can thus be regarded as equivalent:*

- *Connected Continuous Division Ring*
- *Connected, Locally Compact Nontrivial⁷³ Division Ring*
- *Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra*
- *Finite-Dimensional \mathbb{R} -Algebra with no Zero-Divisor*

Now that we have seen that such structures are *equivalent*, we will seek to completely classify them. Actually, this will be quite easy and could already have been done since Lemma (1.3.5.5), but I wanted first to define the different tools that generalize the ones used in \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C} .

⁷²as it is obtained from the product of x with \bar{x}

⁷³Meaning "not equipped with the Indiscrete Topology"

1.4 Defining Quaternions

Here comes the moment we finally define Quaternions. Unlike standard definitions (in terms of $\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}$), we will rather seek to emphasize its unique Algebraic and Topological Properties i.e. base it on Frobenius (and Frobenius-Pontryagin) Theorem.

1.4.1 Most General Structure and Frobenius Theorem

We will now classify all *Connected Continuous Division Rings*, we will see that there are only three⁷⁴ of them, and they form a chain (w.r.t. embedding).

Proposition 1.4.1.1. *The set of all Connected Continuous Division Rings (up to isomorphism) is totally ordered w.r.t. embedding and possesses a Maximal Element. More precisely, there exist only **at most three** such Division Rings, and the dimension⁷⁵ of the latter cannot exceed 4.*

Proof. According to the previous section, we can see \mathbb{K} as a Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra (that can be equipped with an absolute value $|\cdot|$, and can be written as $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R} \oplus \mathbf{V}$, with an inner product $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle$ on \mathbf{V} , compatible with $|\cdot|$); let then n be the dimension of \mathbb{K} as a \mathbb{R} -Vector Space, we will then treat all possibilities:

- $n = 1$, In this case, we simply have $\mathbb{K} \simeq \mathbb{R}$
- $n = 2$, In this case, \mathbf{V} has dimension 1 and is generated as a \mathbb{R} -Vector space by a unitary element e_1 , so we have that

$$\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R} \oplus \mathbf{V} = \{t + e_1x : t, x \in \mathbb{R}, e_1^2 = -1\} \simeq \mathbb{C}$$

- $n = 3$, This is **Impossible**, as \mathbf{V} would have dimension 2, but then, let e_1, e_2 be an orthonormal basis of \mathbf{V} (w.r.t.⁷⁶ $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle$), then as e_1 and e_2 should -by definition- anticommute (as they are orthogonal in \mathbf{V}), we can easily see, defining $e_3 := e_1e_2$, that⁷⁷ $e_3^2 = -1$ and clearly anticommutes with both e_1 and e_2 i.e. is orthogonal to both of them, which is clearly impossible in \mathbb{R}^2 : we need an extra dimension.

⁷⁴up to isomorphism

⁷⁵as a \mathbb{R} -Vector Space

⁷⁶See Definition (1.3.5.6) [Two elements of \mathbf{V} are orthogonal iff they anticommute, and unitary iff their square is -1]

⁷⁷ $e_3^2 = e_1e_2e_1e_2 = -e_1e_1e_2e_2 = -(-1)(-1) = -1$

- $n = 4$, The dimension of \mathbf{V} would then be 3, and an orthonormal basis of it would clearly be given by e_1, e_2 , and $e_3 := e_1e_2 = -e_2e_1$ such that $e_1^2 = e_2^2 = e_3^2 = e_1e_2e_3 = -1$. Note that "if such a structure should Exist", it would obviously include copies of \mathbb{C} (e.g. by taking the subspace generated by 1 and e_1 [that is, any arbitrary unitary element in \mathbf{V}])
- $n > 4$, It is **Impossible**. To prove this, we shall once again seek to construct an orthonormal basis of \mathbf{V} . For this, we first pick an arbitrary unitary element e_1 in \mathbf{V} , then take another unitary element $e_2 \in \mathbf{V}$ that is orthogonal to e_1 , and finally, for the third basis element, we shall take $e_3 := e_1e_2 = -e_2e_1$. Then we clearly⁷⁸ have that $e_3e_2e_1 = 1$. Now, as it is assumed that $\dim \mathbb{K} > 4$, i.e. $\dim \mathbf{V} > 3$, we should be able to complete the basis, i.e. in particular, find a unitary $e_4 \in \mathbf{V}$ that would be orthogonal to e_1, e_2 , and e_3 , i.e. anticommute with them. But then it should also anticommute with $e_3e_2e_1$ (anticommutes 3 times⁷⁹), in other words, $e_4 \neq 0$ anticommutes with 1, which is absurd.

□

Now, according to Proposition (1.4.1.1), it does make sense to define the following:

Definition 1.4.1.2 (Quaternions). We call **Quaternions** and denote by⁸⁰ \mathbb{H} **The Most General Connected Continuous Division Ring**.

Now still according to Proposition (1.4.1.1), the dimension of \mathbb{H} could either be 2 or 4. We obviously expect it to be 4 -as the name "Quaternion" suggests- but for this, we -a priori- first have to make sure that $\mathbb{H} \neq \mathbb{C}$, i.e. that a *Four-Dimensional Connected Continuous Division Ring* "does exist".

Proposition 1.4.1.3. Let \mathbb{K}_4 be the free (Associative) \mathbb{R} -Algebra generated by the elements $\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}$, satisfying the relations :

$$\mathbf{i}^2 = \mathbf{j}^2 = \mathbf{k}^2 = \mathbf{ijk} = -1 \quad (1.95)$$

Then \mathbb{K}_4 is well-defined and each of its elements $q \in \mathbb{K}_4$ can be put in the form:

$$q = t + x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j} + z\mathbf{k}, \quad t, x, y, z \in \mathbb{R} \quad (1.96)$$

⁷⁸ $e_3e_2e_1 = e_1e_2e_2e_1 = -e_1e_1 = 1$

⁷⁹Note that associativity is crucial here: if we were working in the more general context of "Non-Associative Algebras", this argument would fail, and we would then find *Octonions*. This result is described in Hurwitz's Theorem.

⁸⁰as its discoverer Hamilton (though for the moment, we have not yet proven that $\mathbb{H} \neq \mathbb{C}$)

In other words, \mathbb{K}_4 is a Four-Dimensional \mathbb{R} -Vector Space. Furthermore \mathbb{K}_4 admits Division, i.e. it is a Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra, thus by Corollary (1.3.5.20), a Connected Continuous Division Ring, thus implying that :

$$\mathbb{H} = \mathbb{K}_4 \neq \mathbb{C} \quad (1.97)$$

Proof. For this, we define $Q_8 := \{1, \mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}, -\mathbf{k}, -\mathbf{j}, -\mathbf{i}, -1\}$, then it is easy to see from the relations (1.95) that Q_8 forms a multiplicative group, the respective inverses of $\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}$ being given by $-\mathbf{i}, -\mathbf{j}, -\mathbf{k}$, while $\mathbf{ij} = \mathbf{k} = -\mathbf{ji}$, $\mathbf{jk} = \mathbf{i} = -\mathbf{kj}$, $\mathbf{ki} = \mathbf{j} = -\mathbf{ik}$. This then clearly implies that \mathbb{K}_4 is "stable" and its elements can all be put in the form (1.96), i.e. is a 4-Dimensional \mathbb{R} -Vector Space. Now it is clear that \mathbb{K}_4 is of the form $\mathbb{R} \oplus \mathbf{V}$, as defined in Lemma (1.3.5.5), so that in particular, we can use the tools we defined in the previous section, including "conjugation" $q \mapsto \bar{q}$, and noting that $\forall q \in \mathbb{K}_4 \setminus \{0\}, q\bar{q} = \bar{q}q \in \mathbb{R}^{>0}$, thus clearly giving

$$q^{-1} := \frac{\bar{q}}{(q\bar{q})} \quad (1.98)$$

□

Although it may be a bit redundant, we can now close this subsection by restating the *original version* of Frobenius (and Frobenius-Pontryagin) Theorem:

Theorem 1.4.1.4 (Frobenius). *Every Finite-Dimensional (Associative) Division⁸¹ \mathbb{R} -algebra is isomorphic to either $\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C},$ or \mathbb{H}*

Theorem 1.4.1.5 (Frobenius-Pontryagin). *Every Connected Continuous Division Ring is isomorphic to either $\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C},$ or \mathbb{H}*

Proof. We already proved it. □

1.4.2 Equivalent definitions

To summarize, although Quaternions are usually defined as the *free (Associative) Algebra generated by $\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}$ such that $\mathbf{i}^2 = \mathbf{j}^2 = \mathbf{k}^2 = \mathbf{ijk} = -1$* , the previous subsection tells us that there are actually many ways to define them, from their natural -and Unique- properties, for instance:

Definition 1.4.2.1. *Quaternions can equivalently be defined as:*

- *The Most General Connected Continuous Division Ring.*

⁸¹or equivalently, Algebra with no Zero-Divisors

- *The Only Non-Commutative Connected Continuous Division Ring.*
- *The Most General Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra.*
- *The Only Non-Commutative Finite-Dimensional Division \mathbb{R} -Algebra.*

etc...

Note -once again- that, in the above definitions, *Division Algebra* could be replaced by *Algebra with no Zero-Divisors*, and *Continuous* by *Nontrivial Locally Compact*. It should also be possible (though it would a priori require to prove extra results) to add extra definitions to that list (e.g. defining Quaternions in terms of its Archimedean Valuation, or other special properties⁸²)

1.4.3 Importing properties from \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C}

We have seen that tools could be defined on \mathbb{H} , such as an absolute value $|\cdot|$ or the conjugation $\bar{\cdot} : q \mapsto \bar{q}$, clearly generalizing those defined on \mathbb{C} or \mathbb{R} . Another useful way to directly get information about \mathbb{H} is to use the embedding $\mathbb{C} \hookrightarrow \mathbb{H}$. Prior to this, bringing back our involution⁸³ $\hat{\cdot} : q \mapsto \hat{q} := -q^{-1}$, we will define a special set (that can actually be related to Relativity⁸⁴, being the reason why I would sometimes refer to it by the "fanciful name" of "Light Sphere"⁸⁵...).

Definition 1.4.3.1 (Light Sphere). *I will call "Light Sphere" and denote by \mathbb{L} the following set:*

$$\mathbb{L} := \{q \in \mathbb{H} : \hat{q} = q\} \quad (1.99)$$

$$= \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q^2 = -1\} \quad (1.100)$$

$$= \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q + \bar{q} = 0 \wedge q\bar{q} = 1\} \quad (1.101)$$

$$= \{x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j} + z\mathbf{k} : x, y, z \in \mathbb{R}, x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 1\} \approx \mathbb{S}^2 \quad (1.102)$$

In other words, it can either be regarded as

- *the fixed set under the involution $\hat{\cdot} : q \mapsto \hat{q} := -q^{-1}$*
- *the set of all square roots of -1*

⁸²e.g.: the fact that $\mathbb{H} \otimes_{\mathbb{R}} \mathbb{H}$ is isomorphic to the ring of all 4×4 Matrices (i.e. linear maps $\mathbb{R}^4 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^4$)

⁸³(on \mathbb{H}^\times or $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{H})$)

⁸⁴e.g. to Massless particles travelling at the speed of Light

⁸⁵Obviously, I am with no doubt the only one to use that terminology...

- the unit, purely imaginary numbers in \mathbb{H}
- the unit (2D-)sphere in⁸⁶ $\mathbf{V} \approx \mathbb{R}^3$

Now, for $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, we can define:

$$\mathbb{C}_\ell := \{t + r\ell : t, r \in \mathbb{R}\} \quad (1.103)$$

Clearly (as $\ell^2 = -1$), \mathbb{C}_ℓ is a field, isomorphic to \mathbb{C} . Now the following should be noted:

Remark 1.4.3.2. $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{H}) = \mathbb{R}$, i.e. \mathbb{H} as an \mathbb{R} -Algebra is Central-Simple. Also, for all $\alpha \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{R}$, we can define the following set:

$$\mathbb{C}_\alpha := \{t + r\alpha : t, r \in \mathbb{R}\} \quad (1.104)$$

that is also isomorphic to \mathbb{C} , and corresponds to the subfield of all elements of \mathbb{H} that commute with α .

Proof. We obviously know⁸⁷ that $\mathbb{R} \subseteq \mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{H})$. It is then easy to show the converse: take \mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j} as previously defined, then the field of all elements commuting with \mathbf{i} clearly includes $\mathbb{C}_\mathbf{i} \simeq \mathbb{C}$ but does not contain \mathbf{j} (i.e. $\subsetneq \mathbb{H}$) thus it is exactly $\mathbb{C}_\mathbf{i}$, but then, as $\mathbf{i} \in \mathbb{C}_\mathbf{i}$ and does not commute with \mathbf{j} , we have: $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{H}) \subsetneq \mathbb{C}_\mathbf{i}$ and so $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{H}) = \mathbb{R}$, showing that \mathbb{H} is a Central-Simple⁸⁸ Algebra. Now for a general $\alpha \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{R}$, we have that the field of elements commuting with α must obviously contain the two-dimensional vector space⁸⁹ $\mathbb{C}_\alpha \approx \mathbb{R}^2$, but as $\alpha \notin \mathbb{R} = \mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{H})$, the field we are looking for cannot be \mathbb{H} itself, and must thus be isomorphic to $\mathbb{C} \approx \mathbb{R}^2$, and is thus \mathbb{C}_α itself⁹⁰. \square

Note that $\mathbb{C}_\alpha, \alpha \notin \mathbb{R}$ is always equal to some $\mathbb{C}_\ell, \ell \in \mathbb{L}$ (normalized imaginary part), i.e. in general⁹¹, $\forall q \in \mathbb{H}, \exists \ell \in \mathbb{L} : q \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$. (Trivial but useful...)

We will now characterize square roots in \mathbb{H} . Note that from now, I will always use " \mathbb{RL} " instead " \mathbf{V} " (from Lemma (1.3.5.5)), i.e. $\mathbb{H} = \mathbb{R} \oplus \mathbb{RL}$

⁸⁶defined as in Lemma (1.3.5.5)

⁸⁷It is also clear that the set of all elements commuting with a fixed α must form a Division Subring (I will say "Subfield") of \mathbb{H} (i.e. isomorphic to \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C} or \mathbb{H})

⁸⁸as it obviously has no nontrivial Ideals

⁸⁹it is Obviously a field (and clearly corresponds to some \mathbb{C}_ℓ taking ℓ as the normalized imaginary part of α), but it need not be mentioned for the proof

⁹⁰Note that I really "abused" of Frobenius Theorem, which is of course not necessary to prove such basic results

⁹¹(i.e. also if $q \in \mathbb{R}$)

Proposition 1.4.3.3. *Let $q \in \mathbb{H}$, then the equation*

$$x^2 = q \tag{1.105}$$

possesses in \mathbb{H} :

- *A unique (trivial) solution iff $q = 0$*
- *An infinity of solutions (that form a (2D-)Sphere in \mathbb{RL}) iff $q \in \mathbb{R}^{<0}$*
- *Exactly two solutions (which differ by a minus sign) in all other cases*

Proof. The first case is trivial while the second one is just the definition of a sphere in \mathbb{RL} w.r.t. the norm (referred to as "valuation") from Definition (1.3.5.14). For the last remaining case, we first note that the equation must have *at least* two solutions. Indeed, as previously remarked, $\exists \ell \in \mathbb{L} : q \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$, and as $\mathbb{C}_\ell \simeq \mathbb{C}$ Algebraically Closed, it has exactly two solutions in \mathbb{C}_ℓ . We now show that there is no other solution. Suppose that there is some solution y outside \mathbb{C}_ℓ , then $\exists \ell' \in \mathbb{L} : y \in \mathbb{C}_{\ell'}$ (thus with $\mathbb{C}_{\ell'} \neq \mathbb{C}_\ell$), but then, as $\mathbb{C}_{\ell'}$ is a subfield, we have $q = y^2 \in \mathbb{C}_{\ell'}$ and so $q \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \cap \mathbb{C}_{\ell'} = \mathbb{R}$, so, given the hypothesis, $q \in \mathbb{R}^{>0}$. But then the two solutions in $\mathbb{C}_{\ell'}$ are Real, and so $y \in \mathbb{R} \subseteq \mathbb{C}_\ell$, a contradiction. \square

Obviously, it will often be useful to treat Quaternions that commute together (i.e. are in a same \mathbb{C}_ℓ) as Complex Numbers.

Also, we can naturally define the Euler Formula on \mathbb{H} :

$$e^{\theta \ell} = \cos \theta + \ell \sin \theta, \quad \ell \in \mathbb{L}, \theta \in \mathbb{R} \tag{1.106}$$

Noting that every unitary element in \mathbb{H} can be written in this fashion (as they will always lie in some $\mathbb{C}_\ell, \ell \in \mathbb{L}$)

1.4.4 Some additional remarks

Note that, as it could already be remarked from Corollary (1.3.5.9), if we write a quaternion as :

$$q = (t; \vec{v}) \tag{1.107}$$

where $t \in \mathbb{R}$ and \vec{v} is a vector representing the imaginary part of q , then for purely imaginary numbers:

$$v := (0; \vec{v}), \quad w := (0; \vec{w})$$

we have that the product is given by

$$vw = (-\vec{v} \cdot \vec{w} ; \vec{v} \times \vec{w}) \tag{1.108}$$

This is not a coincidence : historically, the dot and cross products (as well as Divergence and Curl) have been obtained from Quaternions... However, I shall never make use of such ""barbaric tools"", as I personally find that Quaternions provide a Much *nicer* structure with much more interesting properties, and generally simplify things ... One can still note, though, that for *general* Quaternions:

$$p := (s; \vec{v}), \quad q := (t; \vec{w})$$

the product is expressed as:

$$pq = (st - \vec{v} \cdot \vec{w} ; s\vec{w} + \vec{v}t + \vec{v} \times \vec{w}) \quad (1.109)$$

i.e. the Real Part corresponds to the Minkowski (pseudo-)Inner product -quite used in Relativity- while the *Imaginary part* may look like expressions that typically appear in physics (e.g. by taking $(\partial_t; \vec{\nabla})$ instead of $(s; \vec{v})$ one can see expressions that look familiar⁹²). Those are of course very naive remarks, and there are clearly much deeper connections with Relativity (such as Symmetry Groups). It should later be seen that the Lorentz Group can naturally be expressed in terms of Quaternionic Möbius Transformations that stabilize the "Light Sphere" \mathbb{L} (and act on it in a conformal way). The goal of this chapter was rather to show that, unlike other tools that are commonly usually used by Physicists, Quaternions are far from being a *mere object that has been artificially created for the only purpose of doing Physics*, but are in fact a *unique and completely natural structure* that arises from Algebraic Topology. (And yet it seems to potentially appear everywhere in Physics...)

⁹²e.g. Maxwell Equations, though not exactly the same

Chapter 2

Exploring elementary features via basic Differential Algebra

We have defined Quaternions as The Most General Connected Locally Compact Division Ring -with a nontrivial Topology- and seen that some properties could directly be *imported* from \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C} . However, there is an obvious feature that Quaternions have and that Real and Complex Numbers do not : it has a noncommutative -thus much more subtle- structure. This naturally gives \mathbb{H} a nontrivial structure of *Differential (Skew) Field* : indeed, by fixing some element, say $a \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{H})$, we have that the map :

$$\mathbb{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{H} : q \mapsto [q, a] := qa - aq \quad (2.1)$$

is \mathbb{R} -linear¹, and satisfies Leibniz's Rule; it can thus be seen as a nontrivial *Derivative* on \mathbb{H} . This means that tools of *Differential Algebra* can be used to explore some features of \mathbb{H} . Of course, the use of such tools is far from being necessary for what we are going to do, and we will only use very, very basic concepts of *Differential Algebra*. However, I personally find that this approach has the advantage of exhibiting some nice links between the Algebraic structure of \mathbb{H} and its Geometry, as well as simplifying some proofs...

More details about Differential Algebra can be found in Kaplansky's work^[Ka] and a short introduction to Differential Galois Theory is easily available online^[Hu-Lu]; they however -unlike us- work on Commutative structures. Despite the fact of working on a Noncommutative Division Ring, it turns out that the structure of \mathbb{H} still remains much simpler than the Fields of Functions usually described in Differential Algebra, i.e. the results we will find will be much simpler and more intuitive than those (also -as already said- we will only use basic concepts)

¹actually more than just " \mathbb{R} -linear"; but extra details will be given when defining the Field of Constants

2.1 Basic Definitions and Remarks

2.1.1 Differential Rings and Fields

Definition 2.1.1.1 (Derivative). Let \mathbb{A} be a Ring, then $\delta : \mathbb{A} \mapsto \mathbb{A} : x \mapsto \delta(x) =: x'$ is said to be a Derivative on \mathbb{A} if δ satisfies :

$$\delta(x + y) = \delta(x) + \delta(y) \quad (2.2)$$

$$\delta(xy) = \delta(x)y + x\delta(y) \quad (2.3)$$

in other words, if δ is additive and satisfies Leibniz's Rule
In this case, \mathbb{A} is called a Differential Ring

Remark 2.1.1.2. Note that often, the brackets will be omitted, and $\delta(x)$ will be shortened δx .

Also notice that any ring can be given the Trivial Derivative $\delta : x \mapsto 0$

Remark 2.1.1.3. If, furthermore, our Differential Ring \mathbb{A} is also a Division Ring, we will say that it is a Differential Division Ring, or Differential (Skew) Field. It is then easy to see from² (2.3) that the Derivative of the inverse is given by :

$$\delta(x^{-1}) = -x^{-1}\delta(x)x^{-1} \quad (2.4)$$

or to make it shorter :

$$(x^{-1})' = -x^{-1}x'x^{-1}$$

Remark 2.1.1.4. Note that if δ and Δ are two derivatives on some Ring \mathbb{A} , then so is $\delta + \Delta$, as it is clearly additive, and

$$(\delta + \Delta)(xy) = \delta(xy) + \Delta(xy) = \delta(x)y + x\delta(y) + \Delta(x)y + x\Delta(y) = (\delta(x) + \Delta)x + x(\delta(y) + \Delta)$$

So the set of all possible derivatives on a Ring \mathbb{A} form an additive Group.
Furthermore, it is easy to see that if $z \in \mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{A})$, we get :

$$\begin{aligned} z\delta(x + y) &= z\delta(x) + z\delta(y) \\ z\delta(xy) &= z\delta(x)y + zx\delta(y) = (z\delta(x))y + x(z\delta(y)) \end{aligned}$$

Thus the set of all possible Derivatives on a ring \mathbb{A} is in fact a $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{A})$ -**module**, and obviously, in the case of a Division Ring \mathbb{K} , a $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{K})$ -**vector space**.

²together with the fact that $1' = (1.1)' = 1'.1 + 1.1' = 2.1' = 0$

2.1.2 Kernel and "Constants"

Definition 2.1.2.1 (Constants of a Differential Ring). *Let \mathbb{A} be a Differential Ring, of derivative $\delta : x \mapsto x'$. Then the elements of the kernel:*

$$\ker \delta = \{c \in \mathbb{A} : \delta(c) = 0\} \quad (2.5)$$

are called the constants of \mathbb{A}

Remark 2.1.2.2. *As δ is an additive endomorphism, its kernel is clearly an additive group, furthermore, for any $a, b \in \ker \delta$, we have :*

$$(ab)' = a'b + ab' = 0b + a0 = 0$$

*hence stable by multiplication; and as it is obvious that $1' = (1.1)' = 1'.1 + 1.1' = 2.1' = 0$, Constants of a Differential Ring always form a **nontrivial Differential Subring**. In the case of a Differential Division Ring, it is also easy to see from (2.4)- that*

$$(c^{-1})' = -c^{-1}c'c^{-1} = 0, \quad \forall c \in \ker(\delta) \setminus \{0\}$$

*we thus get a **Differential Division Subring**. The terminology **Field of Constants** is then frequently used³, and the latter obviously always includes the Prime subfield (\mathbb{Q} or \mathbb{F}_p depending on the characteristic).*

Remark 2.1.2.3. *If \mathbb{A} is a Differential Ring, c a constant, we clearly have :*

$$\forall x \in \mathbb{A}, (cx)' = c'x + cx' = cx', \quad (xc)' = x'c + xc' = x'c$$

*Now in the case of a Differential Division Ring \mathbb{K} , it is clear that the derivative δ is **linear** (in the usual sense⁴) over the (commutative) Subfield $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{K}) \cap \ker \delta$ (which obviously always includes the prime Subfield)*

2.1.3 Differential Morphisms

Definition 2.1.3.1 (Differential Morphism). *Let $\mathbb{A}, \tilde{\mathbb{A}}$, be Differential Rings whose derivatives are respectively denoted by $\delta, \tilde{\delta}$, then a map $\mathbb{A} \rightarrow \tilde{\mathbb{A}}$ is called a **Differential Morphism** if*

- *f is a Ring Homomorphism*
- *$\tilde{\delta}f(x) = f(\delta x), \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{A}$*

³Though usually referring to commutative fields

⁴otherwise, it is still $\ker \delta$ -linear in the sense of bimodules

It is of course possible to go much further, for instance by defining *Differential Ideals* (ideals which remain stable under δ) etc..., but we won't make much use of such tools (unless we work with Hurwitz's Quaternions⁵); as we will focus on \mathbb{H} , we will rather work with *Division Ring Endomorphisms* (and more precisely, *Differential Automorphisms* : i.e. Automorphisms ρ that commute with the derivative : $\delta\rho(q) = \rho(\delta q)$)

2.1.4 Most basic ideas of Differential Galois Theory

By analogy with *Galois Theory* -for Fields-, a *Differential Galois Theory* -for Differential Fields- could be developed in a rigorous way. However, for our purposes, we are only going to require some (*very*) *basic intuition* about *what kind of objects we should be looking at*. We will therefore not need to spend time defining (accurately) concepts such as *Picard-Vessiot extensions* nor the *Differential Galois Group*, -as they will turn out to take a very simple and intuitive form in the context of Quaternions anyway- but the reader should keep in mind the following analogy :

- While in standard Galois Theory, field extensions arise from roots of Polynomials:

$$p(x) = x^n + a_{n-1}x^{n-1} + \dots + a_0 = 0$$

in Differential Galois Theory, they arise from solutions of Homogeneous Linear Differential Equations:

$$p(\delta)x := \delta^n x + c_{n-1}\delta^{n-1}x + \dots + c_0x = 0$$

- While in standard Galois Theory, we define the Galois Group by looking at the automorphisms of the field extension, that fix the field we started with (thus permuting roots of the polynomial the extension comes from), in Differential Galois Theory, the same description holds, but roughly replacing *Automorphisms* by *Differential Automorphisms*, as well as *polynomial* by *differential equation*.

No further description nor extra tool/result will be required for our purposes, as the idea is to find analogies, rather than making extensive use of such tools.

⁵note that in this case, the *ring of constants* of a nontrivial derivative will turn out to be isomorphic to either the ring of *Gaussian Integers*, or the one of *Eisenstein Integers*

2.2 Continuous derivatives on \mathbb{H}

Now that we had a brief overview of some rudiments of Differential Algebra, as well as remarked that the fact of \mathbb{H} being non-commutative would directly imply the existence of nontrivial Derivatives, the first thing to do might be to try to describe *all* possible derivatives on \mathbb{H} , or at least, all possible **Continuous** derivatives. Note that the condition of continuity for δ is equivalent to the fact of being \mathbb{R} -linear, as \mathbb{R} -linear functions over \mathbb{R}^4 are obviously always continuous, while we know from Remark (2.1.2.3) that a derivative on \mathbb{H} will always be \mathbb{Q} -linear, thus continuity implying \mathbb{R} -linearity⁶.

2.2.1 General Properties

Although the problem of describing "all possible Continuous Derivatives \mathbb{H} could be equipped with" could be solved quite quickly by a direct calculus, in which we would find that $\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}$ should anticommute with their respective derivatives, then writing the general expression and finding a *cross-product* (...), I promised I would avoid the use of such *barbaric tools*. Instead, I decided to slowly and naively explore general properties of such derivatives via some Lemmas...

Remark 2.2.1.1.

- As it has already been said, the fact of δ being continuous is equivalent to \mathbb{R} -linearity, and in particular, $\mathbb{R} \subseteq \ker \delta$
- Obviously, we now only work on \mathbb{H} , not in any other General Ring
- To denote a general derivative on \mathbb{H} , $\delta(q)$ will often⁷ be shortened: q'

Lemma 2.2.1.2. *Let $v \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}$, then $vv' = -v'v$, i.e.: purely imaginary numbers anticommute with their derivative.*

Proof.

$$v^2 \in \mathbb{R} \implies 0 = (v^2)' = v'v + vv'$$

□

⁶ $\mathbb{R} = \mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{H})$ as well as the implication $\delta(\mathbb{Q}) = \{0\} \implies \delta(\mathbb{R}) = \{0\}$ for δ continuous

⁷i.e.: when there is no ambiguity on the derivative we are working with: when there aren't several derivatives involved

Remark 2.2.1.3. *It is easy to notice from Lemma (2.2.1.2), that for a general $q \in \mathbb{H}$, we will have :*

$$q'q = \bar{q}q'$$

(It suffices for this to write $q = t + v$, $t \in \mathbb{R}, v \in \mathbb{RL}$)

Corollary 2.2.1.4.

$$(v \in \mathbb{RL}) \implies (vv' \in \mathbb{RL} \wedge v' \in \mathbb{RL})$$

hence in particular $\delta(\mathbb{H}) = \delta(\mathbb{RL}) \subseteq \mathbb{RL}$

Proof. $v'v$ and vv' have the same real part, which thus must be 0, also, as v anticommutes with vv' , the same argument holds⁸, showing that $v' \in \mathbb{RL}$, i.e. : $\delta(\mathbb{RL}) \subseteq \mathbb{RL}$, but as $\mathbb{H} = \mathbb{R} \oplus \mathbb{RL}$, and $\delta(\mathbb{R}) = \{0\}$ the last equation is trivial. \square

Remark 2.2.1.5. *Actually, one can see that the condition $v \in \mathbb{RL}$ turns out not to be necessary : as for a general $q \in \mathbb{H}$, we have $q = t + v$, $t \in \mathbb{R}, v \in \mathbb{RL}$, we have $q' = v' \in \mathbb{RL}$ and $qq' = tv' + vv' \in \mathbb{RL}$*

Corollary 2.2.1.6. *Still for $v \in \mathbb{RL}$, we have that v' commutes with vv'' . (and also v'' with $v'v'''$, v''' with $v''v''''$ etc...)*

Proof. trivial \square

Remark 2.2.1.7. *Just notice that we clearly have for all $q \in \mathbb{H}$:*

- $(\bar{q})' = \overline{(t+v)'} = (t-v)' = -v' = -q' = \overline{(q')}$
- $(q^2)' = qq' + q'q = qq' + \bar{q}q' = (q + \bar{q})q' = 2\text{Re}(q)q'$
- $\sqrt{q}' = \frac{q'}{2\text{Re}(\sqrt{q})}$
- $(q^{-1})' = -q^{-1}q'q^{-1} = \frac{-q'}{|q|^2}$ (as $(q^{-1})'(q^{-1}) = \overline{(q^{-1})}(q^{-1})'$)

Lemma 2.2.1.8. *Let $\delta : Q \mapsto Q'$ be a nontrivial derivative on \mathbb{H} , let $q \in \mathbb{H}$ such that $q' \neq 0$, then, we also have :*

$$q'' \neq 0, q''' \neq 0, q'''' \neq 0 \text{ etc...}$$

Proof. Let $q \in \mathbb{H} : q' \neq 0$, and suppose $q'' = 0$, then

$$(qq')' = (q')^2 + qq'' = (q')^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{<0}$$

which contradicts the fact that $(qq')'$ should be in \mathbb{RL} (see⁹ Corollary (2.2.1.4)). Hence if $q' \neq 0$, so is q'' and thus all its derivatives. \square

⁸dividing by $v^2 \in \mathbb{R}, (v \neq 0 \text{ w.l.o.g.})$

⁹more precisely, the last part : $\delta(\mathbb{H}) \subseteq \mathbb{RL}$

Corollary 2.2.1.9.

$$\mathbb{H} = \ker \delta \oplus \delta(\mathbb{H})$$

Proof. As $\delta : \mathbb{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}$ is a \mathbb{R} -linear endomorphism, and $\mathbb{H} \simeq \mathbb{R}^4$ (hence finite-dimensional over \mathbb{R}), it suffices to prove that

$$\ker \delta \cap \delta(\mathbb{H}) = \{0\}$$

but this is an immediate consequence of the previous lemma (Lemma (2.2.1.8)) \square

Lemma 2.2.1.10. *Let $\delta : q \mapsto q'$ be any derivative on \mathbb{H} , then*

$$\exists w \in \mathbb{RL} \setminus \{0\} : w' = 0$$

In other words, the inclusion found in Corollary (2.2.1.4) is strict: $\delta(\mathbb{H}) \subsetneq \mathbb{RL}$, as the restricted map $\delta : \mathbb{RL} \rightarrow \mathbb{RL}$ cannot be a bijection¹⁰

Proof. If δ is trivial, so is the proof. Let δ be nontrivial, and $q \in \mathbb{H} : q' \neq 0$ (and by Lemma (2.2.1.8), $q'' \neq 0, q''' \neq 0 \dots$). Note that by Corollary (2.2.1.4), we know $\delta(\mathbb{H}) \subseteq \mathbb{RL}$, and in particular, $q' \in \mathbb{RL}$ and (still by Corollary (2.2.1.4), taking $v := q'$) $q'q'' \in \mathbb{RL}$. If $(q'q'')' = 0$, then we are done (just take $w := q'q''$). Now assume $(q'q'')' \neq 0$, then

$$(q'q'')' = (q'')^2 + q'q''' \in \mathbb{RL} \setminus \{0\}$$

where $(q'')^2$ is real, while (by Corollary (2.2.1.6), taking $v := q'$) $q'q'''$ commutes with q'' , from which we deduce¹¹ :

$$\exists \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^\times : (q'q'')' = \lambda q''$$

Thus $q'q''$ and $\lambda q'$ have the same derivative while they are clearly distinct (they clearly anticommute by Lemma (2.2.1.2)), implying that the restricted map

$$\delta : \mathbb{RL} \rightarrow \mathbb{RL}$$

cannot be a bijection (more precisely, it is not injective), which proves what we wanted \square

Corollary 2.2.1.11. *For a nontrivial derivative δ , the field of constants $\ker \delta$ as well as the image $\delta(\mathbb{H})$ have both dimension 2 over \mathbb{R} . In particular, the field of constants is isomorphic to \mathbb{C} and generated by the w from Lemma (2.2.1.10) i.e. :*

$$\ker \delta = \mathbb{C}_w, \quad w \in \mathbb{RL} \setminus \{0\}, w' = 0$$

¹⁰rank-nullity theorem

¹¹as $(q'q'')' \in \mathbb{RL} \setminus \{0\}$ and commutes with q''

Proof. As δ is not trivial, the *field of constants* $\ker \delta$ is strictly smaller than \mathbb{H} , and, by the previous lemma, strictly greater than \mathbb{R} , so it must be isomorphic to \mathbb{C} , and as it contains $w \in \mathbb{RL} \setminus \{0\}$, it is clearly \mathbb{C}_w . i.e.: $\ker \delta$ has dimension 2, and so has $\delta(\mathbb{H})$ $(4 - 2)$ \square

Corollary 2.2.1.12. *Seeing $\ker \delta$ and $\delta(\mathbb{H})$ as \mathbb{R} -vector spaces, let $q \in \mathbb{H} : q' \neq 0$, then,*

- *An orthogonal¹² basis of $\delta(\mathbb{H})$ is given by $\{q', q''\}$*
- *An orthogonal basis of $\ker \delta$ is given by $\{1, q'q''\}$*
- *q', q'' and $q'q''$ anticommute and so $\{q', q'', q'q''\}$ form an orthogonal basis of \mathbb{RL} , while $\{1, q', q'', q'q''\}$ form an orthogonal basis of \mathbb{H} . Note that $\delta(\mathbb{H}) \perp \ker \delta$*

Proof. q' and q'' are nonzero elements of $\delta(\mathbb{H})$ and they anticommute (hence are orthogonal), as $\dim \delta(\mathbb{H}) = 2$, $\{q', q''\}$ clearly forms an orthogonal basis. now $q'q''$ clearly anticommutes with q' as well as q'' (thus proving the last claim), and one can notice that as $q''' \in \delta(\mathbb{H})$ and is orthogonal to q'' , it must be parallel to q' , and so $q'q''' \in \mathbb{R}^\times$. Then

$$\mathbb{RL} \supseteq \delta(\mathbb{H}) \ni (q'q'')' = (q'')^2 + q'q''' \in \mathbb{R}$$

so $(q'q'')' = 0$ i.e. $q'q'' \in \ker \delta$ and forms an orthogonal basis of it together with 1. \square

Remark 2.2.1.13. *It is now trivial to see that two derivatives on \mathbb{H} have the same kernel **if and only if** they have the same image (as those are orthogonal)*

Proposition 2.2.1.14. *Let $\delta : Q \mapsto Q'$ be a nontrivial derivative on \mathbb{H} , then there exists $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^\times$ such that :*

$$\forall q \in \mathbb{H}, q''' + \lambda q' = 0 \tag{2.6}$$

and more precisely, we have:

- $q' = 0 \iff q \in \ker \delta$ (obviously)
- $q'' + \lambda q = 0 \iff q \in \delta(\mathbb{H})$ ("wave-like" equation)

¹²a priori not "orthonormal" -obviously-

Proof. Take any $q \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \ker \delta$, then by Corollary (2.2.1.12), an orthogonal basis of $\delta(\mathbb{H})$ is given by $\{q', q''\}$. As already mentioned, q''' has to be orthogonal to q'' in $\delta(\mathbb{H})$ and thus must be parallel to q' , i.e. $\exists \lambda_{(q)} \in \mathbb{R}^\times : q''' + \lambda_{(q)}q' = 0$. But then -by simply taking the derivative- we also have $q'''' + \lambda_{(q)}q'' = 0$, and as $\{q', q''\}$ forms a basis of $\delta(\mathbb{H})$, it is clear that all elements in $\delta(\mathbb{H})$ will satisfy the *wave-like equation* for $\lambda := \lambda_{(q)}$ (i.e. λ does not depend on q), while conversely, it is trivial that any element satisfying $q = -\lambda^{-1}q''$ must be in $\delta(\mathbb{H})$. It is also clear that composing $\delta(\mathbb{H}) \rightarrow \{0\} : v \mapsto v'' + \lambda v$ with $\mathbb{H} \rightarrow \delta(\mathbb{H}) : q \mapsto q'$, we get the global equation (2.6). \square

Remark 2.2.1.15. *The above "wave-like" equation gives us a natural way to construct the canonical (linear) projections:*

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\delta(\mathbb{H})}^+ &: \mathbb{H} = \ker \delta \oplus \delta(\mathbb{H}) \rightarrow \delta(\mathbb{H}) \\ P_{\ker \delta}^+ &: \mathbb{H} = \ker \delta \oplus \delta(\mathbb{H}) \rightarrow \ker \delta \end{aligned}$$

Indeed, from Proposition (2.2.1.14), we easily deduce that $P_{\delta(\mathbb{H})}^+$ and $P_{\ker \delta}^+$ should be given by :

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\delta(\mathbb{H})}^+ &: q \mapsto -\lambda^{-1}q'' \\ P_{\ker \delta}^+ &: q \mapsto q + \lambda^{-1}q'' \end{aligned}$$

Proof. It is enough to prove it for $P_{\delta(\mathbb{H})}^+$. It is clear that $q \mapsto -\lambda^{-1}q''$ maps \mathbb{H} to $\delta(\mathbb{H})$, hence it suffices to show that $P_{\delta(\mathbb{H})}^+ \circ P_{\delta(\mathbb{H})}^+ = P_{\delta(\mathbb{H})}^+$: let $q \in \mathbb{H}$, then¹³

$$P_{\delta(\mathbb{H})}^+(P_{\delta(\mathbb{H})}^+(q)) = -\lambda^{-1}(-\lambda^{-1}q'')'' = \lambda^{-2}(q')''' = \lambda^{-2}(-\lambda)(q')' = -\lambda^{-1}q'' = P_{\delta(\mathbb{H})}^+(q) \quad \square$$

Definition 2.2.1.16. *Two derivatives δ, Δ will be called equivalent iff :*

$$\exists r \in \mathbb{R}^\times : \forall q \in \mathbb{H}, \Delta(q) = r\delta(q)$$

in other words, if they are linearly dependant over \mathbb{R} (recall that by Remark (2.1.1.4), derivatives on \mathbb{H} form a \mathbb{R} -vector space)

Lemma 2.2.1.17. *Two derivatives $\delta : q \mapsto q', \Delta : q \mapsto q^*$ on \mathbb{H} are equivalent **if and only if** they have the same kernel (or equivalently, the same image (Rmk (2.2.1.13)))*

¹³also using the equation $q''' + \lambda q' = 0$ from Proposition (2.2.1.14)

Proof. If δ and Δ are equivalent, they trivially have the same kernel and image. Conversely, let us assume that δ and Δ are nontrivial and have the same kernel (or image). By Rmk (2.2.1.13), this is equivalent to having the same image (or kernel, respectively), so let $0 \neq v \in \delta(\mathbb{H}) = \Delta(\mathbb{H})$, then v' is orthogonal to v , while v^* is also orthogonal to v , and as the dimension of the image is 2, v' and v^* must be parallel, thus there must exist $r_{(v)} \in \mathbb{R}^\times$ such that $v^* = r_{(v)}v'$. Although it seems quite obvious from the previous result, that r cannot depend on v and that the proof should be finished, let's allow ourselves to be *ridiculously cautious* and assume that r might actually somehow depend on the chosen v . But then -for this specific $r_{(v)}$ - we can define

$$\Delta - r_{(v)}\delta : q \mapsto q * -r_{(v)}q'$$

which is clearly a derivative (by Rmk (2.1.1.4)), whose kernel obviously includes $\ker \delta = \ker \Delta$, but is strictly bigger, as it also contains $v \in \delta(\mathbb{H}) \setminus \{0\}$. Thus the kernel of this "new derivative" can only be \mathbb{H} , and so it is the Trivial derivative, i.e. $\Delta = r\delta$, with " $r := r_{(v)}$ " (which thus clearly does not depend on v) \square

Corollary 2.2.1.18. *Every nontrivial derivative on \mathbb{H} is equivalent to a commutator with some $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, and so can be identified to a commutator with an element of \mathbb{RL} . i.e. the \mathbb{R} -vector space of all derivatives on \mathbb{H} is isomorphic to \mathbb{R}^3 . Also, it is clearly a Lie Algebra (\mathbb{RL} with commutator or equivalently \mathbb{R}^3 with cross product) i.e. if δ, Δ are derivatives, so is $\delta\Delta - \Delta\delta$*

Proof. We know (from Corollary (2.2.1.11)) that the kernel of any nontrivial derivative will be a subfield of \mathbb{H} isomorphic to \mathbb{C} , and clearly, we know that all such subfields are of the form :

$$\mathbb{C}_\ell = \{a + b\ell, a, b \in \mathbb{R}\}, \quad \ell \in \mathbb{L}$$

Which corresponds exactly to the field of elements commuting with ℓ , i.e. the kernel of the derivative given by $q \mapsto q\ell - \ell q$, so by the previous Lemma (2.2.1.17), all nontrivial derivatives will be *equivalent* to to such a commutator $[q, \ell]$, and can thus be identified to some $r[q, \ell] = [q, r\ell] =: [q, v]$, $v \in \mathbb{RL} \setminus \{0\}$, while the commutator with 0 obviously corresponds to the trivial derivative. \square

2.2.2 Explicit form

Although the fact that all *all continuous derivatives on \mathbb{H} are given by commutators* may at first sight look a bit disappointing, I find that the *differential approach* remains a nice way to explore the non-commutative structure of Quaternions, and helps define *appropriate* tools to do so.

Definition 2.2.2.1. Let $a \in \mathbb{H}$, we define the following derivative :

$$\delta_a q := \frac{qa - aq}{2} \quad (2.7)$$

Note that geometrically, $\delta_a q$ is equivalent to a cross product between the imaginary parts of q and a . Also, it is clear that writing

$$a = t + v = t + r\ell, \quad t, r \in \mathbb{R}, \ell \in \mathbb{L}$$

we get

$$\delta_a = \delta_{t+v} = \delta_t + \delta_v = \delta_v = \delta_{r\ell} = r\delta_\ell$$

so as already mentioned, the only relevant derivatives to study will be the ones of the form $\delta_v, v \in \mathbb{RL}$, and more precisely, the ones of the form¹⁴ $\delta_\ell, \ell \in \mathbb{L}$.

Let $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, we can now explicitly describe $\ker \delta_\ell$ and $\delta_\ell(\mathbb{H})$:

- $\mathbb{C}_\ell = \ker \delta_\ell$ is the field of all elements **commuting** with ℓ
- $\ell^\perp := \delta_\ell(\mathbb{H})$ is the \mathbb{R} -vector space of all elements **anticommuting** with ℓ

(as in Corollary (2.2.1.12))

(Note that those definitions obviously still hold when replacing $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ by $v \in \mathbb{RL}$, while for a general $a \in \mathbb{H}$, a^\perp should be defined as the elements anticommuting with the *imaginary part* of a)

Although those features are obvious, they allow us to easily see how those two structures will interact with each other :

Proposition 2.2.2.2. Let $\delta_\ell, \ell \in \mathbb{L}$, then¹⁵ for $a, b \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$, $X, Y \in \ell^\perp$, we have :

- $ab \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$ (*obviously*)
- $XY \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$
- $aX = X\bar{a} \in \ell^\perp$

¹⁴to uniquely represent each *class* of nontrivial derivatives we would actually need to consider a subset of \mathbb{L} , isomorphic to $\mathbf{P}^2(\mathbb{R})$ (i.e. $\mathbb{L}/\{\pm 1\}$)

¹⁵it is obviously not required that $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, but as said, it is the only "relevant case" and the one we will focus on (see Corollary (2.2.1.18))

Proof. The first one is -the most- trivial as \mathbb{C}_ℓ is a field, the other ones are obvious as well : $\ell XY = -X\ell Y = XY\ell$, while $\ell aX = a\ell X = -aX\ell$ and X anticommutes with ℓ thus does so with the imaginary part of a \square

Remark 2.2.2.3. While \mathbb{C}_ℓ is a field, ℓ^\perp a priori only has a \mathbb{R} -vector space structure. However, there is an -obvious and- natural way to give it a field structure¹⁶ as well : it suffices for this to specify a Neutral element N . More precisely, let $N \in \ell^\perp \setminus \{0\}$, then by Proposition (2.2.2.2), we have :

$$\mathbb{C}_\ell N = \ell^\perp$$

The multiplication law is then given by $(X, Y) \mapsto XN^{-1}Y$ for which N is clearly the neutral element. It is obviously "nicer" to take N unitary, hence $N \in \ell^\perp \cap \mathbb{L}$, giving :

$$XN^{-1}Y = -XNY = X\bar{N}Y$$

Remark 2.2.2.4. Let $u \in \mathbb{H}$, then

$$|u| = 1 \iff \exists \ell_1, \ell_2 \in \mathbb{L} : u = \ell_1 \ell_2$$

In other words :

$$\ker |\cdot| = \mathbb{L}\mathbb{L}$$

Proof. If u is the product of two elements of \mathbb{L} , then it is clearly¹⁷ unitary. Conversely, let $u \in \ker |\cdot|$, without loss of generality, we can assume $u \neq \pm 1$ (otherwise trivial) then it is not real and must thus be in some \mathbb{C}_ℓ , $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$. Take $\ell_1 \in \mathbb{L} \cap \ell^\perp$ (i.e. a unitary element of ℓ^\perp), then $\ell_1^{-1} = -\ell_1 \in \mathbb{L} \cap \ell^\perp$. Now let $\ell_2 := \ell_1^{-1}u$, by Proposition (2.2.2.2) it is in $\ell^\perp \subseteq \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}$, and $|\ell_2| = |\ell_1^{-1}u| = |\ell_1^{-1}||u| = 1$, i.e. $\ell_2 \in \mathbb{L}$ \square

Remark 2.2.2.5. From now, the multiplicative subgroup of unitary elements in \mathbb{H}^\times ($\ker |\cdot|$) will be denoted by $\mathbb{L}\mathbb{L}$.

Note that adapting the results of Proposition (2.2.1.14) to the case where $\delta = \delta_\ell$, $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, we clearly have $\forall q \in \mathbb{H}$:

$$q''' + q' = 0 \tag{2.8}$$

$$q \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \iff q' = 0 \tag{2.9}$$

$$q \in \ell^\perp \iff q'' + q = 0 \tag{2.10}$$

And in other words, \mathbb{H} can somehow be seen as a *Differential Field Extension* of \mathbb{C}_ℓ by the *Differential Equation* $q'' + q = 0$ (notice the similarity with $x^2 + 1 = 0$)

¹⁶obviously not a *subfield* of \mathbb{H} , however (in the sense that it does not contain 1)

¹⁷(as $\mathbb{L} \subseteq \ker |\cdot|$ and $\ker |\cdot|$ multiplicative group)

2.3 Canonical Projections

2.3.1 Kernel and Image

For $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, $\delta_\ell : q \mapsto q'$, we know that

$$q \in \ell^\perp \iff q'' + q = 0 \iff q = -q''$$

i.e. by applying Remark (2.2.1.15) [with $\lambda = 1$] we get the canonical projections :

$$P_{\ell^\perp}^+ : \mathbb{H} = \mathbb{C}_\ell \oplus \ell^\perp \rightarrow \ell^\perp : q \mapsto -q'' \quad (2.11)$$

$$P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+ : \mathbb{H} = \mathbb{C}_\ell \oplus \ell^\perp \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_\ell : q \mapsto q + q'' \quad (2.12)$$

Let $X \in \ell^\perp$, then as *-by definition-* $\ell X = -X\ell$, we clearly have that $X' = X\ell$ hence for $q \in \mathbb{H}$, $-q'' = -q'\ell = \ell q'$, i.e. $P_{\ell^\perp}^+ = -\delta^2 = \ell\delta$ and thus

$$P_{\ell^\perp}^+(q) = \frac{q + \ell q \ell}{2} \quad (2.13)$$

$$P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(q) = \frac{q - \ell q \ell}{2} \quad (2.14)$$

Note that the link between $P_{\ell^\perp}^+$ and the derivative allows us to deduce relations such as:

$$P_{\ell^\perp}^+(ab) = P_{\ell^\perp}^+(a)b + \rho_\ell(a)P_{\ell^\perp}^+(b) \quad (\text{where } \rho_\ell(q) = -\ell q \ell) \quad (2.15)$$

$$= P_{\ell^\perp}^+(a)b + aP_{\ell^\perp}^+(b) - 2P_{\ell^\perp}^+(a)P_{\ell^\perp}^+(b) \quad (2.16)$$

The first equation directly arises from the fact that $P_{\ell^\perp}^+(q) = \ell q'$, while the second one is just

$$-(ab)'' = -(a''b + 2a'b' + ab'') = -(a''b - 2a'\ell b' + ab'') = -(a''b + 2\ell a'\ell b' + ab'')$$

Also, as we know :

$$P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(ab) + P_{\ell^\perp}^+(ab) = ab = (P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(a) + P_{\ell^\perp}^+(a))(P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(b) + P_{\ell^\perp}^+(b))$$

together with Proposition (2.2.2.2), we get :

$$(ab)_\parallel = a_\parallel b_\parallel + a_\perp b_\perp \quad (\text{"cosh-like eqn"}) \quad (2.17)$$

$$(ab)_\perp = a_\parallel b_\perp + a_\perp b_\parallel \quad (\text{"sinh-like eqn"}) \quad (2.18)$$

Where $q_\parallel := P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(q)$, $q_\perp := P_{\ell^\perp}^+(q)$

2.3.2 "Splitting" Quaternions "Algebraically"

From $P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+$ and $P_{\ell^\perp}^+$, other natural projections can be deduced; for example, for $N \in \ell^\perp \cap \mathbb{L}$, we know that $\mathbb{C}_\ell \cap \mathbb{C}_N = \mathbb{R}$, we can thus reformulate the "Projection to the Real Part" : $P_{\mathbb{R}}^+ : \mathbb{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : q \mapsto \frac{q+\bar{q}}{2}$ in terms of ℓ, N ; not requiring \bar{q} (note that the same can thus be done with the imaginary part $P_{\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}}^+ : \mathbb{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L} : q \mapsto \frac{q-\bar{q}}{2}$, hence \bar{q} can also be expressed "algebraically" in \mathbb{H}). To do so, it suffices to notice that projecting q onto its real part is the same as projecting it onto \mathbb{C}_N , then onto \mathbb{C}_ℓ , with the above defined ℓ, N .

$$P_{\mathbb{R}}^+(q) = P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(P_{\mathbb{C}_N}^+(q)) = \frac{\frac{q-NqN}{2} - \ell \left(\frac{q-NqN}{2} \right) \ell}{2} = \frac{1}{4} (q - \ell q \ell - NqN - \ell Nq\ell N) \quad (2.19)$$

Now the same can be done for the imaginary part :

$$P_{\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}}^+(q) = q - P_{\mathbb{R}}^+(q) = \frac{1}{4} (3q + \ell q \ell + NqN + \ell Nq\ell N) \quad (2.20)$$

Also, as $\{1, \ell, N, \ell N\}$ forms an orthonormal basis of \mathbb{H} , one might seek to isolate the coordinate in ℓ this can be easily achieved by applying a similar argument as above : this time with $\mathbb{R}\ell = N^\perp \cap \mathbb{C}_\ell$, thus defining :

$$P_{\ell^\parallel}^+(q) = P_{\mathbb{R}\ell}^+(q) := P_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^+(P_{N^\perp}^+(q)) = \frac{1}{4} (q - \ell q \ell + NqN + \ell Nq\ell N) \quad (2.21)$$

In particular, taking $\ell := \mathbf{i}$, $N := \mathbf{j}$, we get¹⁸ :

¹⁸Obviously assuming that $q = t + xi + yj + zk$, $\mathbf{i}^2 = \mathbf{j}^2 = \mathbf{k}^2 = \mathbf{ijk} = -1$

$$\bar{q} = \frac{-1}{2}(q + \mathbf{i}q\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{j}q\mathbf{j} + \mathbf{k}q\mathbf{k}) \quad (2.22)$$

$$P_{\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}}^+(q) = \frac{1}{4}(3q + \mathbf{i}q\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{j}q\mathbf{j} + \mathbf{k}q\mathbf{k}) \quad (2.23)$$

$$t = P_{\mathbb{R}}^+(q) = \frac{1}{4}(q - \mathbf{i}q\mathbf{i} - \mathbf{j}q\mathbf{j} - \mathbf{k}q\mathbf{k}) \quad (2.24)$$

$$x\mathbf{i} = \frac{1}{4}(q - \mathbf{i}q\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{j}q\mathbf{j} + \mathbf{k}q\mathbf{k}) \quad (2.25)$$

$$y\mathbf{j} = \frac{1}{4}(q + \mathbf{i}q\mathbf{i} - \mathbf{j}q\mathbf{j} + \mathbf{k}q\mathbf{k}) \quad (2.26)$$

$$z\mathbf{k} = \frac{1}{4}(q + \mathbf{i}q\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{j}q\mathbf{j} - \mathbf{k}q\mathbf{k}) \quad (2.27)$$

$$x = \frac{1}{4}(\mathbf{j}q\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{k}q\mathbf{j} - (q\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{i}q)) \quad (2.28)$$

$$y = \frac{1}{4}(\mathbf{k}q\mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}q\mathbf{k} - (q\mathbf{j} + \mathbf{j}q)) \quad (2.29)$$

$$z = \frac{1}{4}(\mathbf{i}q\mathbf{j} - \mathbf{j}q\mathbf{i} - (q\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{k}q)) \quad (2.30)$$

This this indicates that, in some sense, *everything that can be done algebraically in \mathbb{R}^4 (e.g. Systems of Polynomial Equations in four variables T, X, Y, Z) can also be done "algebraically" using Quaternions (e.g. Polynomials in one variable Q)*

As we will see in details in the next section, Automorphisms of \mathbb{H} (as an \mathbb{R} -Algebra) are rotations, and thus, if one were to do Algebraic Geometry in \mathbb{R}^4 by using Quaternions (i.e. *expressing Algebraic Varieties as zeros of polynomials in one Quaternionic variable Q*), rotations would be trivial to express...

(Note also that the above relations can be used to prove that the \mathbb{R} -Algebra of all linear endomorphisms of \mathbb{R}^4 (i.e. 4×4 matrices) is isomorphic to $\mathbb{H} \otimes_{\mathbb{R}} \mathbb{H}$)

2.4 Rotations and Differential Galois Group

We here see \mathbb{H} as an \mathbb{R} -Algebra and seek to characterize all its Automorphisms. Of course, as \mathbb{H} is a *Central Simple Algebra* the *Skolem-Noether Theorem* could be used to directly deduce that all of those should be of the form $q \mapsto aqa^{-1}$, $a \in \mathbb{H}^\times$ while the link with Rotations could be established by using matrices and/or cross-products... here again, I will avoid the use of

such tools, and rather use (some of) the ones we just defined. We will see that those will turn out to be more intuitive, and simplify some proofs...

2.4.1 Automorphisms of \mathbb{R} -Algebra

Let $\rho : \mathbb{H} \xrightarrow{\simeq} \mathbb{H}$ be a Division Ring Automorphism. Then, we clearly have $\forall n \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{0\}, m \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(1) = 1 &\implies \rho(n) = \rho(1 + 1 + \dots + 1) = n \implies \rho(-n) = -\rho(n) = -n \\ &\implies \rho(m^{-1}) = \rho(m)^{-1} = m^{-1} \implies \rho\left(\frac{m}{n}\right) = \frac{m}{n} \end{aligned}$$

In other words, \mathbb{Q} is fixed by such automorphisms. Now if we require that ρ be continuous¹⁹, we will have that ρ will fix \mathbb{R} as well, i.e. ρ will be linear, and thus an automorphism of \mathbb{R} -(Division) Algebra. Conversely, any automorphism of \mathbb{R} -(Division) Algebra on \mathbb{H} will be a \mathbb{R} -linear Automorphism of Division Ring, thus continuous (as linear in \mathbb{R}^4) w.r.t. the Standard Topology.

Definition 2.4.1.1. $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ will denote the set of all Continuous Division Ring Automorphisms of \mathbb{H} , or equivalently, all its Automorphisms of \mathbb{R} -Algebra.

We will now seek to characterize $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$.

Lemma 2.4.1.2. \mathbb{L} is stable under $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$, i.e.

$$\forall \ell \in \mathbb{L}, \forall \rho \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}), \rho(\ell) \in \mathbb{L}$$

Proof.

$$\rho(\ell)^2 = \rho(\ell^2) = \rho(-1) = -1$$

□

(Notice that this argument would work with any set of roots of a polynomial with real coefficients [in this case, we chose $Q^2 + 1 = 0$])

¹⁹w.r.t. the natural topology on \mathbb{H} , i.e. the standard topology on \mathbb{R}^4

As we know that $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ fixes \mathbb{R} , we will characterize it by only looking at its action on²⁰ $\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L} \approx \mathbb{R}^3$. Now let $r\ell \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L} : r \in \mathbb{R}^{>0}, \ell \in \mathbb{L}$, then clearly $\rho(r\ell) = r\rho(\ell)$, where $r = |r\ell|$ i.e. the distance to the origin is preserved ($|\rho(v)| = |v| \forall v \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}$). Better than that, we have that the distances between elements in $\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}$ are also preserved

Lemma 2.4.1.3. *Let $v, w \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}$, then $|\rho(v) - \rho(w)| = |v - w|$,
In other words, $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ must be isomorphic to a subgroup of $O(3)$*

Proof.

$$|\rho(v) - \rho(w)| = |\rho(v - w)| = |v - w|$$

□

Now it is clear that, as elements of $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ are Automorphisms -and not *Antiautomorphisms*- they will preserve orientation i.e.

Proposition 2.4.1.4. *$\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ is isomorphic to a subgroup²¹ of $SO(3)$, i.e. all automorphisms of \mathbb{H} are rotations*

2.4.2 Explicit form of Rotations

We know that any Automorphism (of \mathbb{R} -Algebra) of \mathbb{H} is a rotation, and it is trivial²² to check that any map of the form $q \mapsto aqa^{-1}$, $a \in \mathbb{H}^{\times}$ is an Automorphism of \mathbb{R} -Algebra. We will here explicitly show that all Rotations (and so all Automorphisms) can be represented this way.

Proposition 2.4.2.1. *Let $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, $\theta \in [0, 2\pi[$, and so $e^{\theta\ell} = \cos \theta + \ell \sin \theta$ then*

$$\rho_{e^{\theta\ell}} : q \mapsto e^{\theta\ell} q e^{-\theta\ell} \quad (2.31)$$

Is a rotation of angle 2θ about the axis $\mathbb{R}\ell$

Proof. As $\rho_{e^{\theta\ell}}$ is of the form $q \mapsto cq c^{-1}$, it is clearly an automorphism, and by Proposition (2.4.1.4) we know that it must be a rotation. As $e^{\theta\ell} \in \mathbb{C}_{\ell}$, it commutes (*by definition*) with ℓ , and $\rho_{e^{\theta\ell}}$ thus clearly fixes points of $\mathbb{R}\ell \subseteq \mathbb{C}_{\ell}$ so the rotation is around $\mathbb{R}\ell$. Now it just remains to "measure the angle" : let $N \in \ell^{\perp}$, then by Proposition (2.2.2.2), we have :

$$\rho_{e^{\theta\ell}}(N) = e^{\theta\ell} N e^{-\theta\ell} = e^{\theta\ell} \overline{e^{-\theta\ell}} N = e^{\theta\ell} e^{\theta\ell} N = e^{2\theta\ell} N \quad (2.32)$$

Which clearly corresponds to a rotation of an angle 2θ in $\mathbb{C}_{\ell}N = \ell^{\perp}$ (see Rmk (2.2.2.3)) □

²⁰actually, just looking at \mathbb{L} would obviously be enough

²¹not necessarily a "proper" subgroup (as we will see...)

²² $a(x+y)a^{-1} = axa^{-1} + aya^{-1}$, $axya^{-1} = axa^{-1}aya^{-1}$ etc...

Corollary 2.4.2.2.

$$\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) = \{\rho_a : q \mapsto aqa^{-1}, a \in \mathbb{H}^\times\} = \{\rho_u : q \mapsto uq\bar{u}, u \in \mathbb{L}\} \quad (2.33)$$

$$\simeq SO(3) \approx \mathbf{P}^3(\mathbb{R}) \quad (2.34)$$

Proof. (2.33) as well as the isomorphism with $SO(3)$ are clearly direct consequences from Propositions (2.4.2.1) and (2.4.1.4). Now, the homeomorphism with $\mathbf{P}^3(\mathbb{R})$ is easy to check²³ by calculating the kernel of the multiplicative epimorphism :

$$P_{\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})} : \mathbb{H}^\times \rightarrow \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) : a \mapsto (\rho_a : q \mapsto aqa^{-1}) \quad (2.35)$$

And finding that -for $a \in \mathbb{H}^\times$ -

$$\begin{aligned} a \in \ker P_{\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})} &\iff (\forall q \in \mathbb{H}, aqa^{-1} = q) \\ &\iff (\forall q \in \mathbb{H}, aq = qa) \\ &\iff a \in \mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{H}) = \mathbb{R} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{i.e. } \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) \simeq \mathbb{H}^\times / \ker P_{\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})} = \mathbb{H}^\times / \mathbb{R}^\times \approx \mathbf{P}^3(\mathbb{R})$$

□

Remark 2.4.2.3. *A useful equivalence relation is then given by*

$$\begin{aligned} a, b \in \mathbb{H}^\times, a \sim b &\iff \exists \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^\times : b = \lambda a \\ &\iff ab^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^\times \\ &\iff \rho_a = \rho_b \quad (\text{i.e.: induce the same rotation}) \end{aligned}$$

Note that in particular, we obviously have: $\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L} \sim \mathbb{L}$

Now we can look at the involutions in $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$. Clearly,

$$\rho_a \rho_a = \text{Id}_{\mathbb{H}} \iff \rho_{a^2} = \text{Id}_{\mathbb{H}} \iff a^2 \in \mathbb{R}$$

The only possibilities are either $a \in \mathbb{R}$, in which case ρ_a is trivial, or $a \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L} \sim \mathbb{L}$, i.e. the nontrivial involutions are exactly the ones of the form : $q \mapsto -lql$, $l \in \mathbb{L}$.

Definition 2.4.2.4. *The set of all nontrivial involutions in $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ (i.e. "half-turns") will be denoted by $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$. i.e.*

$$\rho_{\mathbb{L}} = \{\rho_\ell : q \mapsto lql^{-1} = -lql, \ell \in \mathbb{L}\}$$

Remark 2.4.2.5. $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$ is obviously not a group (not stable at all, and does not even contain the identity), however, it clearly **generates** $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$; more precisely, any morphism in $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ can be seen as the composition of **two** involutive morphisms in $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$ (direct consequence from Remark (2.2.2.4)). Note that as $\ell \sim -\ell$ and $\mathbb{L} \approx \mathbb{S}^2$, we clearly have :

$$\rho_{\mathbb{L}} \approx \mathbf{P}^2(\mathbb{R})$$

²³if one doesn't already know it from $SO(3)$...

2.4.3 The "Differential Galois Group"

For the reader who would expect something *amazingly complicated* -as the title would suggest- this section is a *complete scam*²⁴. The goal here will be to describe this group in the context of $(\mathbb{H}, \delta_\ell)$ and emphasize how simple -not to say *trivial*- it is (even though we are working in a non-commutative context), rather than trying to do anything *serious* with it..

We know that any (Continuous) Automorphism of \mathbb{H} is of the form $q \mapsto aqa^{-1}$ and represents some rotation, we will now seek to characterize those which could be *Differential Automorphisms* for some derivative δ_ℓ , $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$.

Lemma 2.4.3.1. *Let δ_ℓ , $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ be a derivative on \mathbb{H} , then the (Continuous) Differential Automorphisms w.r.t. δ_ℓ are exactly the maps of the form :*

$$\rho_c : q \mapsto cqc^{-1}, \quad c \in \mathbb{C}_\ell^\times \quad (2.36)$$

Proof. As we already know that those are (Continuous) Automorphisms (of Division Ring), we just have to check the "Differential" part, i.e. $\rho(\delta q) = \delta\rho(q) \forall q$. It is clearly the case for the maps of the form (2.36), as we have :

$$\rho_c(q)' = (cqc^{-1})' = c'qc^{-1} + cq'c^{-1} + cq(c^{-1})' = 0 + cq'c^{-1} + 0 = \rho_c(q')$$

Now if we want to make sure²⁵ that those are the *only ones* with that property, we just write the expression for a general $\rho_a : q \mapsto aqa^{-1}$, $a \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{R}$, as we want it to commute with the derivative:

$$\rho_a(q)' = \rho_a(q') \forall q \in \mathbb{H} \iff a'qa^{-1} + aq'a^{-1} + aq(a^{-1})' = aq'a^{-1} \forall q \in \mathbb{H}$$

Which after simplification as well as developing $(a^{-1})'$ according to²⁶ Remark (2.1.1.3) gives :

$$\forall q \in \mathbb{H}, \quad a'qa^{-1} - aqa^{-1}a'a^{-1} = 0$$

which can be simplified :

$$\forall q \in \mathbb{H}, \quad a'q - aqa^{-1}a' = 0$$

in particular, it should work for $q := a$, hence giving :

$$0 = a'a - aa' = a'a - a'\bar{a} = a'(a - \bar{a})$$

²⁴But it does look nice on the *table of contents*, doesn't it ?..

²⁵although it seems quite obvious...

²⁶The remark says : $(a^{-1})' = -a^{-1}a'a^{-1}$

Which clearly²⁷ implies $a' = 0$, i.e. $a \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$ □

Now, remind that by Corollary (2.2.1.9) and Proposition (2.2.1.14) we have $\mathbb{H} = \mathbb{C}_\ell \oplus \ell^\perp$ with $q \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \iff q' = 0$ while $q \in \ell^\perp \iff q'' + q = 0$. In other words, just as \mathbb{C} can be seen as a Field Extension of \mathbb{R} by adding solutions of

$$X^2 + 1 = 0$$

\mathbb{H} can be seen as a *Differential Field Extension* of \mathbb{C}_ℓ by adding solutions of

$$q'' + q = 0$$

Just as conjugation in \mathbb{C} fixes elements of \mathbb{R} and permutes solutions of $X^2 + 1 = 0$, the maps we just described (of the form $q \mapsto cqc^{-1}$, $c \in \mathbb{C}_\ell^\times$) are (Differential) Automorphisms that fix elements of \mathbb{C}_ℓ and move solutions of $q'' + q = 0$, in other words, they can be seen as a *Differential Galois Group*...

Definition 2.4.3.2 (Differential Galois Group). *Let δ_ℓ , $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ be a derivative on \mathbb{H} , then we denote by $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ -and refer to it as the Differential Galois Group- the subgroup of $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ composed of all Differential Automorphisms (w.r.t. δ_ℓ) that fix \mathbb{C}_ℓ and move solutions of $q'' + q = 0$. It turns out that those extra conditions are redundant, i.e. $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ is precisely the Group of All (Continuous) Differential Automorphisms (w.r.t. δ_ℓ), which can explicitly be characterized :*

$$\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) = \{\rho \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) : \rho\delta_\ell = \delta_\ell\rho\} \quad (2.37)$$

$$= \{\rho_c : q \mapsto cqc^{-1}, c \in \mathbb{C}_\ell^\times\} \quad (2.38)$$

Note that we clearly have : $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) \simeq \mathbf{U}(1) \approx \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{R})$ (rotations about the axis $\mathbb{R}\ell$). In particular it is commutative. Also although we worked with $\delta_\ell \ell \in \mathbb{L}$, we can obviously define such a Group for any "general" $\delta_a, a \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{R}$. Note that if two elements $a, b \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{R}$ commute, the associated *field of constants* will be the same, and δ_a, δ_b will obviously share the same *Differential Galois Group*, while if $ab \neq ba$, the intersection of the associated *Differential Galois Groups* will clearly²⁸ be trivial :

$$\text{Gal}_{\delta_a}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_a) \cap \text{Gal}_{\delta_b}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_b) = \{Id\} \quad (2.39)$$

We can now close this subsection with a last remark about the *more general case of differential Isomorphisms* (v.s. *Automorphisms*).

²⁷Note that $a'a - aa' = a'a - a'\bar{a}$ comes from Remark (2.2.1.3); also the last simplification is allowed as we had assumed without loss of generality that $a \notin \mathbb{R}$ (and even if it were, we would still get to the same conclusion, as $\mathbb{R} \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$ [so $a' = 0$])

²⁸as $ab \neq ba \implies \mathbb{C}_a \cap \mathbb{C}_b = \mathbb{R}$

Remark 2.4.3.3 (Differential Isomorphisms).

1. As each $q \in \mathbb{H}$ is always in some \mathbb{C}_ℓ for a well-chosen $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, we also obviously have that each $\rho \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ will be in a $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$, for some $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$
2. As $\delta_\ell q = \frac{q\ell - \ell q}{2}$, it is clear that any $\rho \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ will always give:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(\delta_\ell q) &= \rho\left(\frac{q\ell - \ell q}{2}\right) \\ &= \frac{\rho(q)\rho(\ell) - \rho(\ell)\rho(q)}{2} \\ &= \delta_{\rho(\ell)}\rho(q) \end{aligned}$$

In other words, for any $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ and any $\rho \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$, the map $\rho : (\mathbb{H}, \delta_\ell) \rightarrow (\mathbb{H}, \delta_{\rho(\ell)})$ is in fact a differential isomorphism (see Definition (2.1.3.1)). This can be seen as an alternative way of proving (and generalizing) Lemma (2.4.3.1).

3. For any $\ell, \tilde{\ell} \in \mathbb{L}$, it is always possible to find a nontrivial Involutive Automorphism of \mathbb{H} (in other words, an element of $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$) that swaps ℓ and $\tilde{\ell}$. In fact, if $\tilde{\ell} \neq -\ell$, this involution will be unique²⁹, and simply given by:

$$\rho_{\ell+\tilde{\ell}} : q \mapsto (\ell + \tilde{\ell})q(\ell + \tilde{\ell})^{-1}$$

This thus naturally provides a differential isomorphism between $(\mathbb{H}, \delta_\ell)$ and $(\mathbb{H}, \delta_{\tilde{\ell}})$, and it is then trivial to see that any general differential isomorphism between those fields can be obtained by composing the above-mentioned involution with an element of the appropriate Differential Galois Group ($\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ or $\text{Gal}_{\delta_{\tilde{\ell}}}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_{\tilde{\ell}})$ depending on left v.s. right composition). More precisely, the set of all Differential Isomorphisms

$$(\mathbb{H}, \delta_\ell) \simeq (\mathbb{H}, \delta_{\tilde{\ell}})$$

can be described as:

$$\rho_{\ell+\tilde{\ell}} \circ \text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$$

or equivalently:

$$\text{Gal}_{\delta_{\tilde{\ell}}}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_{\tilde{\ell}}) \circ \rho_{\ell+\tilde{\ell}}$$

The same argument still works if $\tilde{\ell} = -\ell$, except that the involution is no longer unique; we can instead take any $\rho_N : q \mapsto NqN^{-1}$ with $N \in \ell^\perp \setminus \{0\}$. More details about this particular case will be given in the next subsection.

²⁹Trivial for $\tilde{\ell} = \ell$. Now for $\tilde{\ell} \neq \pm\ell$, we have $\ell\tilde{\ell} \neq \tilde{\ell}\ell$, let $f, g : (\mathbb{H}, \delta_\ell) \simeq (\mathbb{H}, \delta_{\tilde{\ell}})$ be two nontrivial involutions, then clearly $f \circ g \in \text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) \cap \text{Gal}_{\delta_{\tilde{\ell}}}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_{\tilde{\ell}}) = \{Id\}$ (see (2.39))

2.4.4 Geometry of Involutive Automorphisms

Just as $\mathbb{RL} \approx \mathbb{R}^3$ and can thus be used to do 3-Dimensional Euclidean Geometry (e.g. using facts such as $A \parallel B \iff AB = BA$, $A \perp B \iff AB = -BA$, etc...), we notice that, as the set of all nontrivial Involutive Automorphisms $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$ is homeomorphic to $\mathbf{P}^2(\mathbb{R})$, it can potentially be used to do 2-Dimensional Elliptic Geometry³⁰. We will not explore it much in-depth (at all), but rather have a quick overview of the fact that Quaternions tend to bring quite elegant results (though the ones I will mention here are extremely basic)...

First note that, in \mathbb{RL} , $A \perp B \iff A \perp \tilde{B}$, $\forall \tilde{B} \sim B$ (with \sim defined as in Remark (2.4.2.3)). In other words it is equivalent to the two lines $A\mathbb{R}$ and $B\mathbb{R}$ being orthogonal; this property can thus naturally be *imported* to $\rho_{\mathbb{L}} \approx \mathbf{P}^2(\mathbb{R})$ -as it only depends on the equivalence class of A and B w.r.t. \sim -

Definition 2.4.4.1 (Orthogonal Automorphisms). *Let³¹ $\rho_A, \rho_B \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$, we say that ρ_A and ρ_B are Orthogonal, and denote it by $\rho_A \perp \rho_B$ iff the lines $A\mathbb{R}$ and $B\mathbb{R}$ are perpendicular in \mathbb{RL} , i.e. iff $A \perp B$*

Now, either visualising $\rho_{\mathbb{L}} \approx \mathbf{P}^2(\mathbb{R})$ as the set of all lines through the origin in \mathbb{R}^3 or simply as the 2-sphere \mathbb{S}^2 where each point is identified with its antipode, it is easy to define *Geodesics* : those are clearly the *Projective Lines* ($\approx \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{R})$), i.e. if we see $\mathbf{P}^2(\mathbb{R})$ as the set of lines in \mathbb{R}^3 passing through the origin, the geodesics will be given by subsets of lines (through the origin) lying in a same plane (note that such a plane can always be seen as a ℓ^\perp for some $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$), if seeing it as the 2-sphere with an equivalence relation on the antipodes, then Geodesics are simply the great circles of \mathbb{S}^2 with the same equivalence relation...

Definition 2.4.4.2 (Aligned Automorphisms). *Let $\rho_A, \rho_B, \rho_C \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$, we will say that ρ_A, ρ_B and ρ_C are **aligned** iff they lie on a same Geodesic (or equivalently, Projective Line), i.e. iff $A\mathbb{R}, B\mathbb{R}$, and $C\mathbb{R}$ are in the same plane*

Now a natural -and standard- way of defining a *distance* between two Automorphisms $\rho_A, \rho_B \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}} \approx \mathbf{P}^2(\mathbb{R})$ is to take something proportional to the angle³² between the two lines $A\mathbb{R}$ and $B\mathbb{R}$. We can, if we wish, normalize

³⁰which in some sense could be seen as a *more modern and elegant approach* to Spherical Trigonometry

³¹Note that the symbol ρ_A will of course be used to denote a nontrivial Involutive Automorphism of the form $q \mapsto AqA^{-1}$ for some $A \in \mathbb{RL} \setminus \{0\}$, or -without loss of generality- $A \in \mathbb{L}$

³²i.e. minimal angle

it such that $d(\rho_A, \rho_B) = 1 \iff \rho_A \perp \rho_B$. It is clear that all the axioms of a *metric* are satisfied (and note that $d(\rho_A, \rho_B) = d(\rho_c \rho_A \rho_c^{-1}, \rho_c \rho_B \rho_c^{-1}) \forall \rho_c \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ [”rotation-invariant³³”). Also notice that this definition of a *distance* is clearly consistent with the one of *Geodesic* we gave earlier.

Now let us look at some basic properties induced by the structure of \mathbb{H}

Proposition 2.4.4.3. *Let $\rho_A, \rho_B \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$, then the following are equivalent :*

1. $\rho_A \perp \rho_B$
2. $\rho_A \neq \rho_B \wedge \rho_A \rho_B = \rho_B \rho_A$
3. $\rho_A \rho_B \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$

in which case we also have, defining $\rho_C := \rho_A \rho_B$, that $\rho_C \perp \rho_A \wedge \rho_C \perp \rho_B$

Proof. (1) \iff (3) :

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_A \perp \rho_B &\iff A\mathbb{R} \perp B\mathbb{R} \iff A \perp B \iff AB = -BA \\ &\iff (AB)^2 = -BAAB = -|A|^2|B|^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{<0} \\ &\iff AB \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L} \iff \rho_{\mathbb{L}} \ni \rho_{AB} = \rho_A \rho_B \end{aligned}$$

Thus proving the first equivalence. Now reminding that $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$ is by definition the set of all nontrivial involutive automorphisms, and in particular, $(\rho_A \rho_B)^{-1} = \rho_B^{-1} \rho_A^{-1} = \rho_B \rho_A$, the condition (2) clearly becomes equivalent to

$$\rho_A \rho_B \neq Id \wedge \rho_A \rho_B = (\rho_A \rho_B)^{-1}$$

which is exactly the definition of a nontrivial involution, hence proving (2) \iff

(3). Finally, it is clear that as $\rho_C := \rho_A \rho_B$ is distinct from ρ_A, ρ_B and commutes with both, it will satisfy (2) and thus be orthogonal to ρ_A and ρ_B . Note that instead of (2), one can also easily use (3), as

$$\rho_A \rho_C = \rho_A \rho_A \rho_B = \rho_B \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}} \ni \rho_A = \rho_A \rho_B \rho_B = \rho_C \rho_B$$

□

Remark 2.4.4.4. *For the above result to hold, it is clearly important to take ρ_A, ρ_B in $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$ (and not anywhere else in $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$), otherwise, there would obviously be tons of counter-examples. It is however easy to characterize when a general automorphism $\rho_b \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ will commute with³⁴ $\rho_A \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$. It is precisely when $Ab \sim bA$ i.e. $Ab = \pm bA$ thus there are two cases :*

³³as $\rho_c \rho_A \rho_c^{-1} = \rho_{cAc^{-1}}$

³⁴the same remark can be done with a general $\rho_a \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ instead of just $\rho_A \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$, though orthogonality has only been defined on $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$

- $Ab = -bA$, so $b \in A^\perp \subseteq \mathbb{RL}$ thus $\rho_b \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$ and $\rho_A \perp \rho_b$: it is the case we just treated in Proposition (2.4.4.3)
- $Ab = bA$, in which case $b \in \mathbb{C}_A$ and so $\rho_b \in \text{Gal}_{\delta_A}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_A)$

Also, as for two distinct lines through the origin in \mathbb{RL} , -say $A\mathbb{R}, B\mathbb{R}$, $A, B \in \mathbb{RL} \setminus \{0\}$ - there exists one and only one line that is orthogonal to both, namely $(AB - BA)\mathbb{R} =: [A, B]\mathbb{R}$, it is obviously the same for $\rho_A \neq \rho_B$, and this (unique) orthogonal element is given by $\rho_{[A, B]} =: [\rho_A, \rho_B]$

Remark 2.4.4.5. Remark (2.4.4.4) gives us a nice and natural way to characterize the set of all automorphisms that are orthogonal to some $\rho_\ell \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$; we denote that set ρ_ℓ^\perp . Clearly, $\rho_A \in \rho_\ell^\perp \iff A \in \ell^\perp$, and as ℓ^\perp is a plan through the origin in \mathbb{RL} , ρ_ℓ^\perp is clearly a geodesic in $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$, and we can naturally refer to it as the **polar line** associated to the **pole** ρ_ℓ , and there is an obvious Duality between poles and polars. Now, as in \mathbb{H} , we have :

$$N \in \ell^\perp \implies \mathbb{C}_\ell N = \ell^\perp$$

giving ℓ^\perp a field structure whose neutral element is N , the same phenomenon will clearly occur in terms of Automorphisms, i.e.

$$\rho_N \in \rho_\ell^\perp \implies \text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) \circ \rho_N = \rho_\ell^\perp \quad (2.40)$$

thus naturally giving ρ_ℓ^\perp a group structure (isomorphic to $\mathbf{U}(1)$) whose neutral element is the chosen ρ_N , the group law being simply defined as :

$$\rho_\ell^\perp \times \rho_\ell^\perp \rightarrow \rho_\ell^\perp : (\rho_A, \rho_B) \mapsto \rho_A \rho_N \rho_B \quad (2.41)$$

Now while $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ corresponds to the group of all Automorphisms that fix the line $\mathbb{R}\ell$, i.e. act on \mathbb{C}_ℓ as the identity, ρ_ℓ^\perp corresponds to the set (or group once a neutral element is specified) of all Automorphisms that reverse the line $\mathbb{R}\ell$, i.e. act on \mathbb{C}_ℓ like the conjugation $z \mapsto \bar{z}$. In other words, the respective actions of $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ and ρ_ℓ^\perp on \mathbb{C}_ℓ can be seen as the standard Galois Group :

$$\text{Gal}(\mathbb{C}_\ell/\mathbb{R}) = \{Id : z \mapsto z, \neg : z \mapsto \bar{z}\}$$

Also note that, while elements of $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ are Differential Automorphisms, i.e. commute with δ_ℓ , elements of ρ_ℓ^\perp anticommute³⁵ with δ_ℓ

³⁵Should we refer to them as -something like- "Antidifferential Automorphisms" ? Note that this specific relation can be expressed in terms of conjugation $q \mapsto \bar{q}$ rather than "inversion" $q \mapsto -q$, as we know that $(\bar{q})' = -q' = \overline{(q')}$ so for $\rho_N \in \rho_\ell^\perp$, we have $\rho_N \delta_\ell = -\delta_\ell \rho_N$ i.e. $\rho_N(q') = -\rho_N(q)' = \rho_N(\bar{q})'$

Remark 2.4.4.6. Obviously, the relations between elements of $Gal_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ and ρ_ℓ^\perp are analogous to the ones from Proposition (2.2.2.2), i.e. for $\rho_a, \rho_b \in Gal_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$, $\rho_X, \rho_Y \in \rho_\ell^\perp$, we have :

- $\rho_a \rho_b \in Gal_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ (obviously)
- $\rho_X \rho_Y \in Gal_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$
- $\rho_a \rho_X = \rho_X \rho_a^{-1} \in \rho_\ell^\perp$

In particular, this shows, that $\rho_\ell^\perp \cup Gal_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ forms a Group, which is generated by ρ_ℓ^\perp and clearly isomorphic to $\mathbf{O}(2)$: the complete symmetry group of a circle.

Corollary 2.4.4.7. Let $\rho_A, \rho_B, \rho_C \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$, then T.F.A.E. :

1. $\rho_A \perp \rho_B \wedge \rho_B \perp \rho_C \wedge \rho_C \perp \rho_A$
2. ρ_A, ρ_B and ρ_C are all distinct and $\rho_A \rho_B \rho_C = \rho_B \rho_C \rho_A = \rho_C \rho_A \rho_B$
3. same as (2), but with **all** possible permutations of ρ_A, ρ_B and ρ_C
4. $\rho_A \rho_B \rho_C = Id$
5. $ABC = -CBA$ [*rmk*³⁶] (or equivalently³⁷ $BCA = -ACB$ or $CAB = -BAC$)

Proof. (1) \implies (3) Trivial by [Proposition (2.4.4.3), (2)]

(3) \implies (2) Trivial

(2) \implies (4) defining $f := \rho_A \rho_B \rho_C = \rho_B \rho_C \rho_A = \rho_C \rho_A \rho_B$, we get :

$$f = \rho_A f \rho_A = \rho_B f \rho_B = \rho_C f \rho_C$$

Which is clearly equivalent to saying that f should commute with ρ_A, ρ_B and ρ_C , and as those are distinct (implying in particular that f should itself be distinct³⁸ from ρ_A, ρ_B and ρ_C) f can clearly not be orthogonal to those 3 elements at the same time (otherwise we would have $f \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$ and $\rho_A, \rho_B, \rho_C \in$

³⁶once we fixed some $A, B, C \in \mathbb{RL} \setminus \{0\}$ to represent ρ_A, ρ_B, ρ_C

³⁷as $ABC = -CBA \iff A(ABC)A = -A(CBA)A \iff (A^2)BCA = (A^2)ACB \iff BCA = ACB$ etc...

³⁸e.g. otherwise w.l.o.g. $f = \rho_A \implies Id = f \rho_A = \rho_A \rho_B \implies \rho_A = \rho_B$: contradiction

f^\perp which by Remark (2.4.4.6) would imply $\rho_A\rho_B\rho_C \in f^\perp$ i.e. : $f \in f^\perp$: a contradiction), so by Remark (2.4.4.4) we have :

$$f \in \text{Gal}_{\delta_A}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_A) \cap \text{Gal}_{\delta_B}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_B) \cap \text{Gal}_{\delta_C}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_C) = \{Id\}$$

(4) \implies (1) we just write :

$$\rho_A\rho_B = \rho_A\rho_B\rho_C\rho_C = \rho_C \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$$

$$\rho_A\rho_C = \rho_A(\rho_A\rho_B\rho_C)\rho_C = \rho_B \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$$

$$\rho_B\rho_C = \rho_A\rho_A\rho_B\rho_C = \rho_A \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$$

Which by [Proposition (2.4.4.3), (3)] implies (1)

(1) \iff (5) note that (1) is obviously equivalent to saying that all pair of distinct elements in $\{A, B, C\}$ should anticommute, then [\implies] is trivial, as it suffices to write :

$$ABC = -ACB = CAB = -CBA$$

while for [\impliedby], just note that :

$$(ABC)^2 = -CBAABC = -(-|A|^2)(-|B|^2)(-|C|^2) = |ABC|^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{>0}$$

i.e. $ABC \in \mathbb{R}^\times$ and so $\rho_A\rho_B\rho_C = \rho_{ABC} = Id$ which we already proved to imply (1). \square

Lemma 2.4.4.8. *Let $A, B, C \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}$, then the the following are equivalent :*

1. A, B, C lie in a same plane³⁹ through the origin
2. $ABC = CBA$ (or equivalently⁴⁰ $BCA = ACB$ or $CAB = BAC$)
3. $ABC \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}$ (in any order)

In which case, we also have that ABC (in any order) is also in the same plane shared by A, B , and C , and it can easily be constructed geometrically from the point of view that some ℓ^\perp can naturally be given a Field Structure [see Remark (2.2.2.3)]

Proof. (2) \iff (3)

$$\begin{aligned} ABC = CBA &\iff (ABC)^2 = ABCCBA = -|A|^2|B|^2|C|^2 \in \mathbb{R}^{<0} \\ &\iff ABC \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L} \end{aligned}$$

³⁹which obviously corresponds to some ℓ^\perp

⁴⁰by the same remark as for Corollary (2.4.4.7)

(1) \implies (3)

$$A, B, C \in \ell^\perp \implies ABC \in \ell^\perp \text{ as } AB \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$$

(Note in particular that as ABC is in the same plane through the origin ℓ^\perp as A, B, C , and is easy to visualize as the product of A and B in $\mathbb{C}_\ell B^{-1}$ [in particular, if $|B| = 1$, it is exactly the multiplication in \mathbb{C} , replacing -1 by B])

(2) \implies (1) Assuming (2), we will show that there exists some $N \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L} \setminus \{0\}$ that anticommutes with A, B , and C , i.e. $A, B, C \in N^\perp$. Note that if A and B commute, (1) is trivially implied, so we can suppose without loss of generality that they do not, and define $N := AB - BA \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L} \setminus \{0\}$. Obviously, N anticommutes with both A and B , it just remains to check it also does so with C .

$$CN = C(AB - BA) = CAB - CBA = BAC - ABC = (BA - AB)C = -NC$$

□

Corollary 2.4.4.9. *Let $\rho_A, \rho_B, \rho_C \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$, then, T.F.A.E. :*

1. ρ_A, ρ_B and ρ_C are **aligned**
2. $ABC = CBA$ [⁴¹] (or equivalently $BCA = ACB$ or $CAB = BAC$)
3. $\rho_A \rho_B \rho_C \in \rho_{\mathbb{L}}$ (in any order)

In which case, we also have, that $\rho_{ABC} = \rho_A \rho_B \rho_C$ (in any order) is also aligned with ρ_A, ρ_B , and ρ_C , and can be seen as the "product" of ρ_A and ρ_C w.r.t. the natural group law on $\rho_\ell^\perp = \text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) \circ \rho_B$ that takes ρ_B as neutral element

Proof. Direct consequence of Lemma (2.4.4.8)

□

Remark 2.4.4.10. *Although we are not going to explore any further the "(elementary) links between the algebraic structure of Quaternions and the geometry of the Projective Plane", a natural "next step" could -for instance- be to define "triangles" in $\rho_{\mathbb{L}}$. Then note that for a triangle of vertices ρ_A, ρ_B, ρ_C , the associated "Polar Triangle" given by the lines : $\rho_A^\perp, \rho_B^\perp, \rho_C^\perp$, clearly has vertices $\rho_{[B,C]}, \rho_{[C,A]}, \rho_{[A,B]}$, (...) Duality is trivial, and results of Spherical Trigonometry could be deduced/adapted (...)*

⁴¹Same remark as in (2.4.4.7)

Chapter 3

Generalizing Automorphisms : Quaternionic Möbius Transformations

After having studied $\text{Aut } \mathbb{H}$, the group of automorphisms of \mathbb{R} -Algebra of \mathbb{H} , we will seek to generalize such transformations. For this, we will look at special kinds of Quaternionic Möbius Transformations. Further details about Quaternionic Möbius Transformations can be found in J.R.Parker's work^{[Pa][Pa-Sh]}, where he treats a much more general case than the one we are going to focus on. Relevant literature on this subject may also include Wilker's work^[Wi]. The approach we are going to take will be quite different, however.

In this chapter, "Möbius Transformations" are defined as in **Chapter 1** (section 1), and written in their *Right form*¹ $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$, i.e. invertible maps of the form $q \mapsto (aq + b)(cq + d)^{-1}$, which can then be represented as *matrices* $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$ The composition law being given by :

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (aA + bC) & (aB + bD) \\ (cA + dC) & (cB + dD) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.1)$$

Two *matrices* representing the same Möbius Transformation will be said to be *equivalent*².

¹See Chapter 1 for definition and extra details

²Note that I shall denote equivalence relations by " \sim "

3.1 Defining three subgroups : \mathcal{L} , \mathcal{S} , and \mathcal{R}

3.1.1 Basic Definitions

We will here define three subgroups of \mathfrak{M} , with the special property that each of them contains $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$, while completely generating \mathfrak{M} when put together.

In order to achieve this, we first isolate some particular features of $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$:

- Transformations of $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ are Linear (or equivalently³, fix 0 and ∞)
- Transformations of $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ fix \mathbb{R} , and in particular, fix 1 and -1
- Transformations of $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ stabilize \mathbb{L} (points are moved but stay in \mathbb{L}), and are entirely determined by their action on this subset

Now as it is clear that the property of *stabilizing* a specific subset remains true while composing or inverting the maps, i.e.

$$\forall f, g \in \mathfrak{M}^{\triangleright}, \emptyset \neq S \subseteq \mathbb{H}, ((f(S) = S \wedge g(S) = S) \implies ((f \circ g)(S) = S \wedge f^{-1}(S) = S))$$

the following subsets will in fact be subgroups :

Definition 3.1.1.1 (Linear Subgroup: \mathcal{L}). *I will denote by \mathcal{L} the set of all transformations of $\mathfrak{M}^{\triangleright}$ that fix 0 and ∞ (or equivalently, are Linear). This set will then be referred to as the "Linear Subgroup", and its elements will be called "Linear (Möbius) Transformations".*

Definition 3.1.1.2 (Symmetric Subgroup : \mathcal{S}). *I will denote by \mathcal{S} the set of all transformations of $\mathfrak{M}^{\triangleright}$ that fix 1 and -1 . This set will be referred to as the "Symmetric Subgroup", and its elements will be called "Symmetric (Möbius) Transformations".*

Pre-definition 3.1.1.3 (Relativistic Subgroup : \mathcal{R}). *I will denote by \mathcal{R} a set of transformations of $\mathfrak{M}^{\triangleright}$ that stabilize \mathbb{L} (i.e. send elements of \mathbb{L} to -a priori different- elements of \mathbb{L}). Once correctly defined, this set will be referred to as the "Relativistic Subgroup", and its elements will be called "Relativistic (Möbius) Transformations". Extra remarks will be needed in order to define \mathcal{R} accurately⁴*

³as we are in the context of Möbius Transformation i.e. $q \mapsto (aq + b)(cq + d)^{-1}$ fix 0 and ∞ iff $b = 0, c = 0$, i.e. iff Linear

⁴in fact, *The set of All Quaternionic Möbius Transformations that stabilize \mathbb{L} will turn out to be $\pm\mathcal{R}$, i.e. the elements of \mathcal{R} together with maps of the form $q \mapsto -f(q)$ with*

3.1.2 Characterizing the $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ form of \mathcal{L} , \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{R}

Now that we have defined subgroups of $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ in terms of fixed points, or more generally, *stabilized subsets*, it seems natural to seek to describe their explicit $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ form (which we can then express in terms of 2×2 Quaternionic matrices).

The easiest to start with, is to describe transformations of \mathcal{L} .

Proposition 3.1.2.1. *The transformations of \mathcal{L} are precisely the ones of the form :*

$$L : q \mapsto aqb^{-1} \quad a, b \in \mathbb{H}^\times \quad (3.2)$$

thus represented by the matrix :

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.3)$$

the inverse being given by

$$L^{-1} : q \mapsto a^{-1}qb \quad (3.4)$$

or in terms of matrices:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & b^{-1} \end{pmatrix}$$

Noting that it may always be assumed without loss of generality, that -for instance- $|a| = 1$ or any other relevant normalization.

Proof. Trivial □

We can now follow with the *Symmetric* Transformations:

Proposition 3.1.2.2. *The transformations of \mathcal{S} are precisely the ones of the form:*

$$f : q \mapsto (aq + b)(bq + a)^{-1} \quad (3.5)$$

which can be represented by the matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.6)$$

With the condition (for it to be invertible) that $f(0) \notin \{1, -1\}$, i.e. $b \neq \pm a$. The inverse is then easy to determine as we note that:

$f \in \mathcal{R}$. (It will then be seen that the action of \mathcal{R} on \mathbb{L} will be conformal, while $\pm\mathcal{R}$ will include anticonformal maps. \mathcal{R} will be related to the Restricted Lorentz Group, while $\pm\mathcal{R}$ will include time reversal. In other words, although it may look somewhat *artificial* for the moment, \mathcal{R} will really turn out to have very natural Geometric as well as Physical interpretations.)

- if $a = 0$, then the matrix takes the form : $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & b \\ b & 0 \end{pmatrix}$, whose inverse is clearly represented by the matrix $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & b^{-1} \\ b^{-1} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
- otherwise, we can split the transformation into a product :

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \beta \\ \beta & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \beta := a^{-1}b \quad (3.7)$$

the first matrix representing a rotation ($\in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ hence trivially invertible), while the inverse of the second being given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{1-\beta^2} & \frac{-\beta}{1-\beta^2} \\ \frac{-\beta}{1-\beta^2} & \frac{1}{1-\beta^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.8)$$

(the factor $\frac{1}{1-\beta^2}$ obviously being allowed to be dropped if $\beta^2 \in \mathbb{R}$)
 Note that instead of (3.7), we could have taken:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & \gamma \\ \gamma & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix}, \quad \gamma := ba^{-1} = a\beta a^{-1} = f(0) \quad (3.9)$$

Proof. We start by writing f as a general Möbius Transformation in its $\mathfrak{M}^{\triangleright}$ form, i.e.:

$$f : q \mapsto (aq + b)(cq + d)^{-1} \quad (3.10)$$

Now, as $f \in \mathcal{S}$, we have by definition that $f(1) = 1$ as well as $f(-1) = -1$. The first condition clearly implies that

$$a + b = c + d \quad (3.11)$$

while the second one shows that

$$(-a) + b = c - d \quad (3.12)$$

from which it naturally follows that

$$b = c, \quad a = d \quad (3.13)$$

Now as we know that 1 and -1 are fixed, i.e. their own image under f , an obvious necessary condition for f to be invertible is that they not be the image of 0 as well, i.e.:

$$f(0) \notin \{1, -1\} \quad (3.14)$$

or in terms of a, b

$$b \neq \pm a \quad (3.15)$$

We can then split the transformation according to (3.7), and notice that the condition (3.14) clearly implies that $\beta \neq \pm 1$, making (3.8) invertible i.e. that necessary condition is in fact also sufficient. \square

Finally, we will seek to *define* the "Relativistic" transformations by making some observations. We start by writing the general expression of $g \in \mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$, i.e.

$$g : q \mapsto (aq + b)(cq + d)^{-1} \quad (3.16)$$

Now reminding that a condition we *would like to have* is :

$$g(\mathbb{L}) = \mathbb{L}, \quad i.e. : \quad \forall \ell \in \mathbb{L}, g(\ell) \in \mathbb{L} \quad (3.17)$$

we look at the general expression of $g(\ell)$, noting that the latter can be rewritten as:

$$(a - b\ell)\ell(c\ell + d)^{-1} \quad (3.18)$$

An obvious **sufficient** condition for it to be in \mathbb{L} is that

$$a = d \wedge b = -c \quad (3.19)$$

as it would just *rotate* ℓ (by $\rho_{(a-b\ell)}$). For the moment, we will take this as the *definition* of \mathcal{R} .

Definition 3.1.2.3 (Relativistic Subgroup : \mathcal{R}). *I will denote by \mathcal{R} and call "Relativistic Subgroup" the set of all Transformations of the form*

$$g : q \mapsto (aq - b)(bq + a)^{-1} \quad (3.20)$$

i.e. whose Matrix representation is given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & -b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.21)$$

With the condition (necessary and sufficient for it to be invertible) that

$$g(0) \notin \mathbb{L} \quad (3.22)$$

Such transformations will be referred to as "Relativistic Transformations"

Remark 3.1.2.4. Note that Condition (3.19) was "sufficient but not necessary" to imply (3.17). As a result, \mathcal{R} is **not** the "group of all Quaternionic Möbius Transformations that stabilize \mathbb{L} ". A trivial counter-example is given by

$$q \mapsto -q \quad (3.23)$$

Which is clearly not in \mathcal{R} . However, it will later be seen that extending \mathcal{R} (as a group) by adding (3.23), we can naturally define

$$\pm\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R} \cup \{f : q \mapsto -g(q), g \in \mathcal{R}\} \quad (3.24)$$

which is in fact the "whole" group of "all Quaternionic Möbius Transformations that stabilizing \mathbb{L} ".

Now as we know that \mathcal{R} does *not* contain *all* transformations that stabilize \mathbb{L} (which would automatically be a group), we will be careful and check that \mathcal{R} does however still have a group structure, as suggested in Definition (3.1.2.3) and claimed in Remark (3.1.2.4) .

Proposition 3.1.2.5. As expected, \mathcal{R} is a Group, whose elements are composed in the following way :

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & -b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} A & -B \\ B & A \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (aA - bB) & -(aB + bA) \\ (aB + bA) & (aA - bB) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.25)$$

while the inverse of $g : q \mapsto (aq - b)(bq + a)^{-1}$ can be easily be determined by the following method :

- if $a = 0$, then the matrix representation takes the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -b \\ b & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.26)$$

and its inverse is clearly represented by

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -b^{-1} \\ b^{-1} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} 0 & b^{-1} \\ -b^{-1} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.27)$$

- otherwise, $a \neq 0$ and we can then split it as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & -b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \beta \\ -\beta & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix}, \quad \beta = g(0) = -ba^{-1} \quad (3.28)$$

The second matrix representing a rotation (hence trivially invertible) while the inverse of the first one being given by:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{1+\beta^2} & \frac{-\beta}{1+\beta^2} \\ \frac{\beta}{1+\beta^2} & \frac{1}{1+\beta^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.29)$$

(the factor $\frac{1}{1+\beta^2}$ obviously being allowed to be dropped if $\beta^2 \in \mathbb{R}$)
 Also noting that instead of (3.28), one could take

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \gamma \\ -\gamma & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \gamma = -a^{-1}b = a^{-1}\beta a \quad (3.30)$$

Proof. (3.25) is trivial by definition of the Matrix Product (3.1) (or see Chapter 1, end of section 1.1 for more details), and it obviously takes the form (3.21). Now according to the definition, g must satisfy (3.22), i.e.

$$g(0) \notin \mathbb{L}$$

which is clearly a necessary condition for g to be invertible. But decomposing the matrix as above described, it appears obvious that

$$g(0) \notin \mathbb{L} \iff \beta \notin \mathbb{L} \iff \beta^2 \neq -1$$

i.e. (3.29) is well defined, and the condition is thus also sufficient, showing that $g \in \mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ (and also g^{-1} is clearly of the wanted form, i.e. (3.21)). Note that it need not be checked that (3.22) is preserved under composition, as it is trivially implied by the above remark (necessary and sufficient condition for g to be invertible). \square

Keeping an eye on the above Proposition, it might be convenient to define the following quantity :

Definition 3.1.2.6. [Generalized Boost] Let $\mathfrak{b} \in \mathcal{R}$, \mathfrak{b} will be called a "Generalized Boost" if it takes the specific form :

$$\mathfrak{b} : q \mapsto (\beta + q)(1 - \beta q)^{-1} \quad (3.31)$$

i.e. represented by the matrix :

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & \beta \\ -\beta & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.32)$$

Remark 3.1.2.7. Note the similarity between (3.31) and the composition law of tangents. Also, according to Proposition (3.1.2.5), any element of \mathcal{R} not of the form $q \mapsto -bq^{-1}b^{-1}$ can be decomposed into a Generalized Boost and a Rotation.

Now according to Remark (3.1.2.4), we can define $\pm\mathcal{R}$.

Definition 3.1.2.8 (T-Relativistic Subgroup). *I will denote by $\pm\mathcal{R}$ the following set :*

$$\pm\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R} \cup \{f : q \mapsto -g(q), g \in \mathcal{R}\} \quad (3.33)$$

It will be referred to as the "Extended Relativistic Subgroup" or "T-Relativistic Subgroup" and its elements will be called "Extended Relativistic Transformations" or "T-Relativistic Transformations". Note that the matrix form of such transformations is given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & -b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix} \text{ or } \begin{pmatrix} -a & b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.34)$$

Proposition 3.1.2.9. $\pm\mathcal{R}$ is a group. More precisely, it is the group obtained as an extension of \mathcal{R} by including the element $T : q \mapsto -q$.

Proof. It appears clear as T is an involution, and it is trivial to check that

$$\forall g \in \mathcal{R}, T \circ g \circ T \in \mathcal{R} \quad (3.35)$$

From this, we can either directly deduce that T "can always be moved to the left" (more specifically $g \circ T = T \circ (T \circ g \circ T)$, while $\pm\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R} \cup T \circ \mathcal{R}$), making the claim obvious; or alternatively use (3.35) to deduce -with a more formal argument- that $\pm\mathcal{R}$ is a Group Extension of \mathcal{R} by $\{Id, T\} \simeq \{1, -1\}$, \mathcal{R} being a Normal Subgroup of $\pm\mathcal{R}$ \square

Remark 3.1.2.10. *The letter T here actually refers to the "Time-Reversal. Indeed, as already briefly mentioned, although from the moment, the only thing we could deduce about \mathcal{R} and $\pm\mathcal{R}$ is that, when restricted to \mathbb{C} , the first one fixes i and $-i$ while the second one may swap them, it will turn out that things will be much more subtle, but also more "natural" in \mathbb{H} : transformations of \mathcal{R} will be the ones that are conformal on \mathbb{L} while transformations of $(\pm\mathcal{R}) \setminus \mathcal{R} = T \circ \mathcal{R}$ will be the anticonformal ones. \mathcal{R} will be related to the "restricted" (i.e. "standard") Lorentz Group, while $\pm\mathcal{R}$ will also include Time-Reversal...*

3.1.3 Generating \mathfrak{M}

Now that we have determined the explicit $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ form of elements of \mathcal{L} , \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{R} , we can directly deduce the following:

Proposition 3.1.3.1.

1. *The common intersection of \mathcal{L} , \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{R} is precisely the the group of Automorphisms (of \mathbb{R} - Algebra) of \mathbb{H} ; more precisely, we have :*

$$\mathcal{R} \cap \mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S} \cap \mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L} \cap \mathcal{R} = \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) \quad (3.36)$$

2. The whole group $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ can be generated by combining elements of \mathcal{L} , \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{R} .

Proof. [1], and more precisely, (3.36) is trivial, as it suffices to look at the general form of elements of \mathcal{L} , \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{R} (see Propositions (3.1.2.1) and (3.1.2.2) as well as (3.1.2.3) : (3.3), (3.6) and (3.21) respectively), noticing that the only transformations to take two such forms simultaneously are the ones represented by

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & a \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.37)$$

In other words, rotations $q \mapsto aqa^{-1}$. Now regarding [2], we just note the following :

- $\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{L}$
- $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{R}$
- and finally, $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ can be generated by combining an element of \mathcal{L} with an element of \mathcal{R} and an element of \mathcal{S} . This can be checked by a simple calculus; however, the latter will not be required as the result will arise as a direct consequence from Remark (3.1.4.1), which will appear in the next subsection.

It then follows from Remark (1.1.2.1), Chapter 1, that [2] will be verified. \square

Illustration of (3.36), Proposition (3.1.3.1) [1]

Remark 3.1.3.2. *Topologically speaking, if we look at the dimension (w.r.t. real parameters) of those groups, we observe that : $\dim \mathfrak{M}^\triangleright = 15$, $\dim \mathcal{L} = \dim \mathcal{S} = \dim \mathcal{R} = 7$, $\dim \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) = 3$*

3.1.4 Restriction to \mathbb{C}

In order to better understand the structure of \mathcal{L} , \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{R} by getting some basic intuition, we can, as a first approach, restrict ourselves to \mathbb{C} . (Note that further details about the Complex Möbius Group can easily be found in the literature^[Ke-La])

There we can define $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}$, $\mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}$, and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}$, namely the groups of complex Möbius Transformations that can respectively be represented by matrices of the form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & A \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} b & B \\ B & b \end{pmatrix}, \text{ and } \begin{pmatrix} c & -C \\ C & c \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.38)$$

Which -on \mathbb{C} - can be simplified to :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} (1+\beta) & (1-\beta) \\ (1-\beta) & (1+\beta) \end{pmatrix}, \text{ and } \begin{pmatrix} (1+\gamma) & -(i\gamma-i) \\ (i\gamma-i) & (1+\gamma) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.39)$$

Remark 3.1.4.1. *On the Riemann Sphere, those transformations correspond to the Rotations combined with Hyperbolic transformations around each of the 3 axis, i.e. the transformations fixing 0 and ∞ in the case of $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}$, -1 and 1 in the case of $\mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}$, and i and $-i$ in the case of $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}$; using the well-known isomorphism between $PGL(2, \mathbb{C})$ and $SO(3, 1)_+$, we see that the decomposition of the (complex) Möbius group into $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}$, $\mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}$, and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}$ corresponds to the standard decomposition of a Lorentz transformation into 3 boosts combined with 3 rotations (one on each of the 3 orthogonal axis), which is the standard way of **parametrizing** the Lorentz group; we thus have that the transformations of $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}$, $\mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}$, and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}$ generate (and parametrize) the complex Möbius Group, and in particular, can be combined to obtain $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$, finishing the proof of Proposition (3.1.3.1) [2]*

This remark thus makes clear that $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathbf{U}(1) \times \mathbb{R}^{>0} \simeq \mathbb{C}^{\times}$:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathbb{R}^{>0} \times \mathbf{U}(1) \quad \mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathbb{R}^{>0} \times \mathbf{U}(1) \quad \mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathbf{U}(1) \times \mathbb{R}^{>0}$$

In other words, when looking at the Riemann Sphere, $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}$, $\mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}$ and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}$ can each be seen as rotations+dilations, but around 3 different axis; in particular, if the axis is the one passing through 0 and ∞ (case of $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}$), this simply corresponds to multiplying by an element of \mathbb{C}^{\times} . In the same way, it is possible to define natural Field Structures associated with \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{R} . For our purposes, we will only be interested in studying the multiplicative laws and will ignore the additive ones though. It is straightforward to define:

- $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times} := \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{C}) \setminus \{0, \infty\} = \mathbb{C}^{\times}$
- $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} := \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{C}) \setminus \{1, -1\}$
- $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} := \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{C}) \setminus \{i, -i\}$

and *naively* notice the natural compatibility with the following laws:

- $(a, b) \mapsto a.b$, i.e. the standard multiplicative law on \mathbb{C} , in the case of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times}$, and $(a, b) \mapsto -a.b$ for its "dual", both linked by the involution $z \mapsto -z$

- $(a, b) \mapsto \frac{a+b}{1+ab}$, i.e. the hyperbolic tangent law in the case of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times}$, and $(a, b) \mapsto \frac{ab+1}{a+b}$ for its "dual", both linked by the involution $z \mapsto \frac{1}{z}$
- $(a, b) \mapsto \frac{a+b}{1-ab}$ i.e. the tangent law in the case of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}$, and $(a, b) \mapsto \frac{ab-1}{a+b}$ for its "dual", both linked by the involution $z \mapsto \frac{-1}{z}$

Those are however not the *only ones*. There is in particular another class of -slightly more subtle- multiplicative group laws on $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times}$, $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times}$ and $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}$ that are strongly related to $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}$, $\mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}$ and $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}$, and which may also have relevant Geometric and Physical interpretations... For instance, one of those is:

$$\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} \times \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} : (a, b) \mapsto \frac{a + b + ab - 1}{a + b - ab + 1} \quad (3.40)$$

-Which, as we shall see, can be given a very natural Physical meaning, and easy geometrical construction-

In order to do this, a bit more formally, we can look at the above *involutions* naturally linking the above-defined laws to their respective *dual*. Those are

$$R : z \mapsto \frac{-1}{z}, \quad S : z \mapsto \frac{1}{z}, \quad T : z \mapsto -z \quad (3.41)$$

or in terms of matrices

$$R := \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S := \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad T := \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.42)$$

(Note that as an abuse of notation, I will tend to identify the matrix forms to the actual functions)

Their action on the Riemann Sphere can be regarded as half-turns around each of the 3 axis. In order to define the *extra laws* as well as the isomorphisms between them, we will look at "1/4 turns", which, unlike half-turns, have the property of sending $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times}$ to $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times}$ or $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}$ etc... We will thus look at functional square roots of R, S, T , i.e. define $\mathfrak{r}, \mathfrak{s}, \mathfrak{t}$ such that

$$\mathfrak{r}^2 = R, \quad \mathfrak{s}^2 = S, \quad \mathfrak{t}^2 = T \quad (3.43)$$

For this, we take :

$$\mathfrak{r} := \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}, \quad \mathfrak{s} := \begin{pmatrix} i & 1 \\ 1 & i \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}, \quad \mathfrak{t} := \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}} \quad (3.44)$$

whose inverses are clearly given by:

$$\mathfrak{r}^{-1} := \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathfrak{s}^{-1} := \begin{pmatrix} 1 & i \\ i & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathfrak{t}^{-1} := \begin{pmatrix} i & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.45)$$

Remark 3.1.4.2. *This will allow us to generate isomorphisms such as:*

- $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}} \ni \mathfrak{r} : \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{I}}^{\times} \xrightarrow{\sim} \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{J}}^{\times}$
- $\mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}} \ni \mathfrak{s} : \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{J}}^{\times} \xrightarrow{\sim} \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}$
- $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}} \ni \mathfrak{t} : \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} \xrightarrow{\sim} \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{I}}^{\times}$

More generally, $\mathfrak{r}, \mathfrak{s}$ and \mathfrak{t} generate a larger group, which is of course the Group of Orientation-Preserving Symmetries of an Octahedron (or Cube), or equivalently the Group of Permutations of Four Objects, which obviously has 24 elements. Note that we can easily study the latter using tools of **Section 2.4.4**, thanks to the following correspondence:

$$R \sim \rho_i, \quad S \sim \rho_j, \quad T \sim \rho_k \quad (3.46)$$

and more precisely:

$$\mathfrak{r} \sim \rho_{1+i}, \quad \mathfrak{s} \sim \rho_{1+j}, \quad \mathfrak{t} \sim \rho_{1+k} \quad \mathfrak{r}^{-1} \sim \rho_{1-i}, \quad \mathfrak{s}^{-1} \sim \rho_{1-j}, \quad \mathfrak{t}^{-1} \sim \rho_{1-k} \quad (3.47)$$

From which we can deduce ("commutation") relations such as:

$$\mathfrak{rs} = \mathfrak{tr} = \mathfrak{st}, \quad \mathfrak{rt} = \mathfrak{ts}^{-1} = \mathfrak{s}^{-1}\mathfrak{r}, \quad \mathfrak{sr} = \mathfrak{rt}^{-1} = \mathfrak{t}^{-1}\mathfrak{s}, \quad \mathfrak{ts} = \mathfrak{sr}^{-1} = \mathfrak{r}^{-1}\mathfrak{t} \quad (3.48)$$

This thus allows us to characterize the full group; indeed, we have that:

- The **Only** element of order **1** is of course the identity.
- The **9** elements of order **2** are R, S, T as well as $\mathfrak{r}S, \mathfrak{s}T, \mathfrak{t}R$ and $\mathfrak{r}T, \mathfrak{s}R, \mathfrak{t}S$
- The **8** elements of order **3** are $\mathfrak{rs}; \mathfrak{ts}, \mathfrak{rt}, \mathfrak{sr}$ and their inverses $\mathfrak{s}^3\mathfrak{r}^3; \mathfrak{s}^3\mathfrak{t}^3, \mathfrak{t}^3\mathfrak{r}^3, \mathfrak{r}^3\mathfrak{s}^3$
- The **6** elements of order **4** are $\mathfrak{r}, \mathfrak{s}, \mathfrak{t}$ and their respective inverses $\mathfrak{r}^3, \mathfrak{s}^3, \mathfrak{t}^3$

Using what has just been said in Remark (3.1.4.2), we can now describe the 12 Multiplicative Group Laws (4 per set) generated by the above isomorphisms (note that there are 12 of them rather than 24, as the isomorphisms also include multiplicative automorphisms -such as $S : z \mapsto z^{-1}$ in the case of $(\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{I}}^{\times}, \cdot_{\mathcal{I}}) = (\mathbb{C}^{\times}, \cdot)$, etc- In other words, although the above morphisms can generate 24 Fields, each of those will share the same multiplicative law as exactly one other Field, halving the number of multiplicative laws)

Proposition 3.1.4.3. *The Multiplicative Group Laws naturally obtained from $\mathfrak{r}, \mathfrak{s}, \mathfrak{t}$ and related to $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}, \mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}, \mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}$ are the following:*

- For $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{I}}^{\times} = \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{C}) \setminus \{0, \infty\}$:

- $\odot_{1\mathcal{L}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto \mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}$, with $\mathbf{1}$ as neutral element, a^{-1} as inverse of a , and \bar{a} its conjugate.
- $\odot_{i\mathcal{L}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto -\mathbf{a}.i.\mathbf{b}$ with i as neutral element, $-a^{-1}$ as inverse of a , and $-\bar{a}$ its conjugate.
- $\odot_{-1\mathcal{L}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto -\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}$ with -1 as neutral element, a^{-1} as inverse of a , and \bar{a} its conjugate.
- $\odot_{-i\mathcal{L}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto \mathbf{a}.i.\mathbf{b}$ with $-i$ as neutral element, $-a^{-1}$ as inverse of a , and $-\bar{a}$ its conjugate.

► For $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times} = \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{C}) \setminus \{1, -1\}$:

- $\odot_{0\mathcal{L}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto \frac{\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b}}{\mathbf{1}+\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}}$, with $\mathbf{0}$ as neutral element, $-a$ as inverse of a , and \bar{a} its conjugate.
- $\odot_{i\mathcal{L}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto \frac{(\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}+1)+(\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b}).i}{(\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b})+(\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}+1).i}$ with i as neutral element, $-a^{-1}$ as inverse of a , and \bar{a}^{-1} its conjugate.
- $\odot_{\infty\mathcal{L}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto \frac{\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}+1}{\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b}}$ with ∞ as neutral element, $-a$ as inverse of a , and \bar{a} its conjugate.
- $\odot_{-i\mathcal{L}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto \frac{(\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b})+(\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}+1).i}{(\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}+1)+(\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b}).i}$ with $-i$ as neutral element, $-a^{-1}$ as inverse of a , and \bar{a}^{-1} its conjugate.

► For $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} = \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{C}) \setminus \{i, -i\}$:

- $\odot_{0\mathcal{R}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto \frac{\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b}}{\mathbf{1}-\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}}$, with $\mathbf{0}$ as neutral element, $-a$ as inverse of a , and $-\bar{a}$ its conjugate.
- $\odot_{1\mathcal{R}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto \frac{\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b}+\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}-1}{\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b}+\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}-1}$ with $\mathbf{1}$ as neutral element, a^{-1} as inverse of a , and \bar{a}^{-1} its conjugate.
- $\odot_{\infty\mathcal{R}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto \frac{\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}-1}{\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b}}$ with ∞ as neutral element, $-a$ as inverse of a , and $-\bar{a}$ its conjugate.
- $\odot_{-1\mathcal{R}} : (\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}) \mapsto \frac{\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}-1-\mathbf{a}-\mathbf{b}}{\mathbf{a}.\mathbf{b}-1+\mathbf{a}+\mathbf{b}}$ with -1 as neutral element, a^{-1} as inverse of a , and \bar{a}^{-1} its conjugate.

Proof. It can be obtained from calculus by simply using the isomorphisms described in Remark (3.1.4.2). Note that it is however possible to find some "tricks" to "quickly check our results". e.g.:

► It is obvious that all of the possible "neutral elements" will be contained in the set

$$E := \{0, 1, i, \infty, -1, -i\}$$

while for each of the 3 sets $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times}, \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times}, \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}$, we are looking for four "possible neutral elements", those will thus clearly be given by:

- $E \setminus \{0, \infty\} = \{1, i, -1, -i\}$ in the case of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^\times = \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{C}) \setminus \{0, \infty\}$
 - $E \setminus \{1, -1\} = \{0, i, \infty, -i\}$ in the case of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^\times = \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{C}) \setminus \{1, -1\}$
 - $E \setminus \{i, -i\} = \{0, 1, \infty, -1\}$ in the case of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^\times = \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{C}) \setminus \{i, -i\}$
- On a same set, a law will obviously always share the same inverse (meaning "inverse function $z \mapsto z^{-1}$ ") as its "dual" w.r.t. the natural involution on the set, that plays the role of $z \mapsto -z$ on $(\mathbb{C}^\times, \cdot)$, namely R, S, T for $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^\times, \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^\times, \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^\times$ respectively, i.e. we will end up with only 2 inverse functions rather than 4, now we can notice that composing those two gives back the natural involution associated to the set (in other words, once one of the two inverse functions is known, the other one can automatically be obtained by applying the involution to it). This is due to the fact that $i^{-1} = -i$ or more precisely $(i^{-1}(ia)^{-1})^{-1} = -a = i^{-1}(ia^{-1})^{-1}$ or can also be visualised geometrically in terms of half-turns and 1/4 turns (e.g.: $\rho_i \circ (\rho_{1-j} \circ \rho_i \circ \rho_{1+j}) = \rho_j$). THE EXACT SAME remark also holds for conjugates (i.e. duals share the same conjugate, i.e. 2 per set rather than 4 and composing those two gives back the natural involution, as $i^{-1}\overline{i\bar{a}} = -a$) !
- Different sets with the same neutral element will also share the same inverse function, i.e. "no matter the set, same neutral \implies same inverse" :
- $T : a \mapsto -a$ if the neutral is 0 (or ∞)
 - $S : a \mapsto a^{-1}$ if the neutral is 1 (or -1)
 - $R : a \mapsto -a^{-1}$ if the neutral is i (or $-i$)

This can be seen geometrically as the fact that the inverses are entirely determined from the neutral element, by a symmetry. Algebraically, though, it can simply be noticed that T, S and R are the only involutive Möbius Transformations fixing $\{0, \infty\}$, $\{1, -1\}$ and $\{i, -i\}$ respectively.

- It can also be noted that if two different sets share the same neutral element, composing the two conjugates gives back the involution associated to the third set.
- Finally, it just remains to check that the laws we obtained are compatible with the neutrals, inverses and conjugates, and that the composition with a fixed element takes the canonical form of one of the three subgroups $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}}, \mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}}$ or $\mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}}$.

□

Remark 3.1.4.4. *Considering the laws listed in Proposition (3.1.4.3), one can note that:*

- For any of those laws **whose neutral element is not i or $-i$** , the map (defined on $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{C}) = \mathbb{C} \cup \{\infty\}$)

$$a \mapsto \bar{a} \quad (3.49)$$

is a multiplicative automorphism w.r.t. that ("local") law. (Trivial in the case of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times}$ and $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times}$, while for $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}$ it is the composition of the ("local") conjugate with the ("local") multiplicative inverse)

- Once one of the four laws associated to a set $\in \{\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times}, \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times}, \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}\}$ is known, it is clear that the three other ones can easily be obtained by "moving" the neutral element. For instance, if some law $\odot_{\mathbf{v}G}$ is known, we obviously get $\odot_{\mathbf{w}G}$ by moving \mathbf{v} to \mathbf{w} in the following way:

$$a \odot_{\mathbf{w}G} b = a \odot_{\mathbf{v}G} w^{\odot_{\mathbf{v}G}^{-1}} \odot_{\mathbf{v}G} b \quad (3.50)$$

where $\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \in E := \{0, 1, i, \infty, -1, -i\}$, $G \in \{\mathcal{L}, \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{R}\}$ according to the notational conventions adopted in Proposition (3.1.4.3), while $a^{\odot_{\mathbf{v}G}^{-1}}$ would denote the ("local") inverse of a w.r.t. $\odot_{\mathbf{v}G}$

Thanks to what has been said in Remark (3.1.4.4), in now seems relevant to *only* study three laws (one per set) -and possibly their dual- For this we define the following:

Definition 3.1.4.5. *I will denote by $\odot_{\mathcal{L}}$, $\odot_{\mathcal{S}}$ and $\odot_{\mathcal{R}}$ respectively the following laws:*

$$\odot_{\mathcal{L}} := \odot_{1\mathcal{L}}: \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times} \times \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times} : (a, b) \mapsto a.b \quad (3.51)$$

$$\odot_{\mathcal{S}} := \odot_{0\mathcal{S}}: \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} \times \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} : (a, b) \mapsto \frac{a+b}{1+a.b} \quad (3.52)$$

$$\odot_{\mathcal{R}} := \odot_{0\mathcal{R}}: \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} \times \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} : (a, b) \mapsto \frac{a+b}{1-a.b} \quad (3.53)$$

Now, either when there is no ambiguity, or when more generality is needed, the above "local" laws will tend to be abbreviated \odot . We will now quickly define duality.

Definition 3.1.4.6 (Duality). Let $\odot \in \{\odot_{\mathcal{L}}, \odot_{\mathcal{S}}, \odot_{\mathcal{R}}\}$, with $\mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} \in \{\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times}, \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times}, \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}\}$ the associated domain, let $a \in \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times}$, then I will denote by \hat{a} (when there is no ambiguity on the set $\mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times}$ we are working on) and call "local additive inverse" or simply "**Dual**" of a the image of the latter under the natural involution $\in \{T, S, R\}$ associated to $\mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times}$. More precisely :

- $\hat{a} = -a$ in the case where $\mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} := \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times}$ i.e. $(\wedge : a \mapsto \hat{a}) = T$
- $\hat{a} = a^{-1}$ in the case where $\mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} := \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times}$ i.e. $(\wedge : a \mapsto \hat{a}) = S$
- $\hat{a} = -a^{-1}$ in the case where $\mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} := \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}$ i.e. $(\wedge : a \mapsto \hat{a}) = R$

We also define the **Dual of \odot** in the following way :

$$\hat{\odot} : \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} \times \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} : (a, b) \mapsto \widehat{a \odot b} \quad (3.54)$$

Such that we obviously get the isomorphism:

$$\widehat{a \odot b} = \hat{a} \hat{\odot} \hat{b} \quad (3.55)$$

More precisely:

$$\hat{\odot}_{\mathcal{L}} := \odot_{-1\mathcal{L}} : \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times} \times \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times} : (a, b) \mapsto -a.b \quad (3.56)$$

$$\hat{\odot}_{\mathcal{S}} := \odot_{\infty\mathcal{S}} : \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} \times \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} : (a, b) \mapsto \frac{a.b + 1}{a + b} \quad (3.57)$$

$$\hat{\odot}_{\mathcal{R}} := \odot_{\infty\mathcal{R}} : \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} \times \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} : (a, b) \mapsto \frac{a.b - 1}{a + b} \quad (3.58)$$

Remark 3.1.4.7. Note that we trivially have:

$$\hat{a} \odot b = a \hat{\odot} b = a \odot \hat{b} = \widehat{a \odot b} = \hat{a} \hat{\odot} \hat{b} \quad (3.59)$$

and in particular

$$\hat{a} \odot \hat{b} = a \odot b \quad (3.60)$$

(obvious property of the "local additive inverse")

Remark 3.1.4.8. From now, I will tend to stick with the following conventions:

- $\odot \in \{\odot_{\mathcal{L}}, \odot_{\mathcal{S}}, \odot_{\mathcal{R}}\}$, and $\hat{\odot}$ its dual
- $\mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} \in \{\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times}, \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times}, \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}\}$
- $\mathbb{R}_{\odot}^{\times} := \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{R}) \cap \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times}$

- $(i\mathbb{R})_{\odot}^{\times} := (i\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}) \cap \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times}$
- $a^{\odot^{-1}} = a^{\hat{\odot}^{-1}}$ the "local" multiplicative inverse of $a \in \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times}$ w.r.t. \odot (or equivalently $\hat{\odot}$, as those laws share the same inverses), \hat{a} the Dual of a w.r.t. \odot
- More generally a^{\odot^n} the "nth power of a w.r.t. \odot "

We can finally define some tools that will provide Geometric intuition, and that will be relevant when extended to \mathbb{H} .

Definition 3.1.4.9. [Real and Imaginary endomorphisms] Let $\odot \in \{\odot_{\mathcal{L}}, \odot_{\mathcal{F}}, \odot_{\mathcal{R}}\}$, I will denote by \mathfrak{R} and \mathfrak{I} , which I will refer to as the "Real" and "Imaginary" endomorphisms respectively, the maps:

$$\mathfrak{R} : \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\odot}^{\times} \subseteq \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} : z \mapsto z \odot \bar{z} \quad (3.61)$$

$$\mathfrak{I} : \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} \rightarrow (i\mathbb{R})_{\odot}^{\times} \subseteq \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} : z \mapsto z \odot (\bar{z}^{\odot^{-1}}) \quad (3.62)$$

As well as their respective duals:

$$\hat{\mathfrak{R}} : \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\odot}^{\times} \subseteq \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} : z \mapsto z \hat{\odot} \bar{z} \quad (3.63)$$

$$\hat{\mathfrak{I}} : \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} \rightarrow (i\mathbb{R})_{\odot}^{\times} \subseteq \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} : z \mapsto z \hat{\odot} (\bar{z}^{\odot^{-1}}) \quad (3.64)$$

Remark 3.1.4.10. The fact that $\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{I}, \hat{\mathfrak{R}}, \hat{\mathfrak{I}}$ are endomorphisms is an immediate (and trivial) consequence of Remark (3.1.4.4) -as well as the fact that the laws we are working with are commutative⁵-.

Remark 3.1.4.11. It may be useful to have in mind the following -obvious-relations

- (Endo)morphisms:

$$\mathfrak{R}(a \odot b) = \mathfrak{R}(a) \odot \mathfrak{R}(b), \quad \hat{\mathfrak{R}}(a \hat{\odot} b) = \hat{\mathfrak{R}}(a) \hat{\odot} \hat{\mathfrak{R}}(b) \quad (3.65)$$

$$\mathfrak{I}(a \odot b) = \mathfrak{I}(a) \odot \mathfrak{I}(b), \quad \hat{\mathfrak{I}}(a \hat{\odot} b) = \hat{\mathfrak{I}}(a) \hat{\odot} \hat{\mathfrak{I}}(b) \quad (3.66)$$

- Symmetry w.r.t. $\hat{\cdot}$:

$$\mathfrak{R}(z) = \mathfrak{R}(\hat{z}), \quad \hat{\mathfrak{R}}(z) = \hat{\mathfrak{R}}(\hat{z}) \quad (3.67)$$

⁵otherwise, in the noncommutative case, we should check that the conjugation is an antiautomorphism (such that $a\bar{b}\bar{a} = ab\bar{b}\bar{a}$) and that the image of $q \mapsto q\bar{q}$ (in the case of \mathfrak{R}) is included in the center of the group we are working with (such that $a(b\bar{b})\bar{a} = a\bar{a}b\bar{b}$)

- Consistency with $\widehat{\cdot}$:

$$\widehat{(\Re(z))} = \widehat{\Re}(z), \quad \widehat{(\Im(z))} = \widehat{\Im}(z) \quad (3.68)$$

- Compatibility with the Dual law:

$$\Re(a \hat{\odot} b) = \Re(\widehat{a \odot b}) = \Re(a \odot b) = \Re(a) \odot \Re(b) \quad (3.69)$$

$$\widehat{\Re}(a \odot b) = \widehat{\Re}(\widehat{a \odot b}) = \widehat{\Re}(a) \hat{\odot} \widehat{\Re}(b) = \widehat{\Re}(a) \hat{\odot} \widehat{\Re}(b) \quad (3.70)$$

Remark 3.1.4.12. [Explicit form] It may also be useful to have in mind the "explicit form" of the objects we just defined :

- Case of $\odot = \odot_{\mathcal{L}}$

$$\Re_{\mathcal{L}}(z) = z \cdot \bar{z} = |z|^2, \quad \Im_{\mathcal{L}}(z) = \frac{z}{\bar{z}} \quad (3.71)$$

$$\widehat{\Re}_{\mathcal{L}}(z) = -z \cdot \bar{z} = -|z|^2, \quad \widehat{\Im}_{\mathcal{L}}(z) = -\frac{z}{\bar{z}} \quad (3.72)$$

- Case of $\odot = \odot_{\mathcal{S}}$

$$\Re_{\mathcal{S}}(z) = \frac{z + \bar{z}}{1 + z \cdot \bar{z}}, \quad \Im_{\mathcal{S}}(z) = \frac{z - \bar{z}}{1 - z \cdot \bar{z}} \quad (3.73)$$

$$\widehat{\Re}_{\mathcal{S}}(z) = \frac{z \bar{z} + 1}{z + \bar{z}}, \quad \widehat{\Im}_{\mathcal{S}}(z) = \frac{1 - z \bar{z}}{z - \bar{z}} \quad (3.74)$$

- Case of $\odot = \odot_{\mathcal{R}}$

$$\Re_{\mathcal{R}}(z) = \frac{z + \bar{z}}{1 - z \cdot \bar{z}}, \quad \Im_{\mathcal{R}}(z) = \frac{z - \bar{z}}{1 + z \cdot \bar{z}} \quad (3.75)$$

$$\widehat{\Re}_{\mathcal{R}}(z) = \frac{z \bar{z} - 1}{z + \bar{z}}, \quad \widehat{\Im}_{\mathcal{R}}(z) = \frac{-(z \bar{z} + 1)}{z - \bar{z}} \quad (3.76)$$

Remark 3.1.4.13. Note that as $\Re_{\mathcal{L}}(z) = |z|^2$, the map

$$\Re_{\mathcal{L}} : \mathbb{C}^{\times} = \mathbb{C}^{\times} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\times} = \mathbb{R}^{\times}$$

is obviously not surjective -as only positive elements are reached-. The same phenomenon occurring with $\Re_{\mathcal{S}}$ and $\Re_{\mathcal{R}}$ as well, we could define more accurately new subsets, i.e. for $\odot \in \{\odot_{\mathcal{L}}, \odot_{\mathcal{S}}, \odot_{\mathcal{R}}\}$ the set $\mathbb{R}_{\odot}^>$ as the "connected component of $\mathbb{R}_{\odot}^{\times}$ containing the identity element w.r.t. \odot " (and obviously

$\mathbb{R}_{\odot}^> = \widehat{\mathbb{R}_{\odot}^>} =: \mathbb{R}_{\odot}^<$). This may not have so much interest though, as, although in the case of $\odot_{\mathcal{I}}$, we would have

$$\mathbb{R}_{\odot}^> =] - 1, 1[\quad (3.77)$$

it would not bring much in the case of $\odot_{\mathcal{R}}$ given that

$$\mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{R}}^> = \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\} = \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{R}) = \mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} \quad (3.78)$$

(It allows however to have a surjective homomorphism, i.e. to study more formally concepts such as subgroups or equivalence classes)

Note that similar remarks can also be applied in the case of \mathfrak{I} , given the relations:

$$\mathfrak{R}(iz) = i\mathfrak{I}(z), \quad \mathfrak{I}(iz) = i\mathfrak{R}(z), \quad \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(iz) = i\widehat{\mathfrak{I}}(z), \quad \widehat{\mathfrak{I}}(iz) = i\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(z) \quad (3.79)$$

All these remarks will certainly become clearer after we look at the geometrical interpretation of such tools (\mathfrak{R} , $\widehat{\mathfrak{I}}$ etc..)

Proposition 3.1.4.14. *Let $\odot \in \{\odot_{\mathcal{I}}, \odot_{\mathcal{R}}\}$, defined over $\mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times}$, and let $\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{I}, \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}, \widehat{\mathfrak{I}}$ be the associated endomorphisms. Then the equivalence classes w.r.t. such morphisms can be "visualized" as "circles" on the complex plane $\mathbb{C} = \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{I}}$, whose respective centers are given by $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$ (in the case of the Real endomorphism) and $\widehat{\mathfrak{I}}$ (in the case of the Imaginary endomorphism).*

(Note that this should be seen as a "naive" way of visualizing the equivalence classes rather than a "formal statement". Indeed, this claim is in fact not very rigorous in the sense that -despite the isomorphism- $\mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} \neq \mathbb{C}^{\times}$, in particular, $\infty \in \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times}$ implying that $\mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times} \not\subset \mathbb{C}$, and to make it "worse", $1, -1 \notin \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{I}}^{\times}$ while $i, -i \notin \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}$, but we will see in the next remark -Rmk (3.1.4.15)- that a specific family of such "circles" will always pass through those points so they won't really be "circles" but can still be "visualized" as so, although being in fact rather homeomorphic to lines. There will also be -trivial- "degenerate cases" (center at ∞) in which those will simply be visualized as lines. To summarize, we are here naively talking about "circles" in the sense of their (constant) "curvature" when represented in the plane, rather than their topological properties. Topologically speaking, however, we will always have circles for one kind of endomorphism (Real vs Imaginary) and lines for the other one.)

Proof. The fact that their shape is "circular" is obvious geometrically if we visualize equivalence classes w.r.t. $\mathfrak{R}_{\mathcal{I}} : z \mapsto |z|^2$ as circles on the Riemann Sphere ("parallels"), orthogonal to "meridians" (which represent the equivalence classes w.r.t. $\mathfrak{I}_{\mathcal{I}} : z \mapsto z/\bar{z}$), then rotate the Riemann Sphere by 1/4 turn (isomorphism with $\mathbb{C}^{\times} = \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{I}}^{\times} \simeq \mathbb{C}_{\odot}^{\times}$) and project it back to the

complex plane (see figure illustrating Remark (3.1.4.1)). If one finds this approach "too vague and intuitive", it is still easy to calculate the locus of points explicitly. I will just illustrate this in the case of $\odot = \odot_{\mathcal{R}}$, and \mathfrak{R} as endomorphism; the proof obviously remaining the same in all other cases.

$$\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} \ni z = t + ix, \mathfrak{R}(z) = c \iff \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(z) = \hat{c} \quad (3.80)$$

$$\iff \frac{z\bar{z} - 1}{z + \bar{z}} = \hat{c} \quad (3.81)$$

$$\iff \frac{t^2 + x^2 - 1}{2t} = \hat{c} \quad (3.82)$$

$$\iff t^2 + x^2 - 1 = \hat{c}.2t \quad (3.83)$$

$$\iff t^2 - 2t\hat{c} + \hat{c}^2 + x^2 = 1 + \hat{c}^2 \quad (3.84)$$

$$\iff (t - \hat{c})^2 + x^2 = 1 + \hat{c}^2 \quad (3.85)$$

Where we clearly recognize the equation of a circle, centered at $\hat{c} = \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(z)$ and of squared radius $1 + \hat{c}^2$. (Note however that such a "circle" would always pass through $i, -i$ which do not lie in $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}$, as remarked at the end of the Proposition) \square

Remark 3.1.4.15. Proposition (3.1.4.14) allows us to describe locus of points sharing the same equivalence class w.r.t. $\mathfrak{R}, \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}, \mathfrak{J}, \widehat{\mathfrak{J}}$ a bit more accurately. Indeed, let

- $E_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathbf{c}) := \{i, -i\} \cup \{z \in \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} : \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}_{\mathcal{R}}(z) = \mathbf{c}\}, \quad \mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} = \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$
- $H_{\mathcal{R}}(\mathbf{d}) := \{z \in \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times} : \widehat{\mathfrak{J}}_{\mathcal{R}}(z) = \mathbf{d}\}, \quad \mathbf{d} \in i(\mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\leq}) := i(]-1, 1[^{-1}) = i.(\mathbb{R}^{<-1} \cup \{\infty\} \cup \mathbb{R}^{>1})$

as well as

- $E_{\mathcal{J}}(\mathbf{D}) := \{1, -1\} \cup \{z \in \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{J}}^{\times} : \widehat{\mathfrak{J}}_{\mathcal{J}}(z) = \mathbf{D}\}, \quad \mathbf{D} \in (i\mathbb{R})_{\mathcal{J}}^{\times} = i(\mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{R}}^{\times}) = (i\mathbb{R}) \cup \{\infty\}$
- $H_{\mathcal{J}}(\mathbf{C}) := \{z \in \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{J}}^{\times} : \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}_{\mathcal{J}}(z) = \mathbf{C}\}, \quad \mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{J}}^{\leq} :=]-1, 1[^{-1} = \mathbb{R}^{<-1} \cup \{\infty\} \cup \mathbb{R}^{>1}$

Then we can easily see -e.g. from Proposition (3.1.4.14)- that :

- $E_{\mathcal{R}}(\infty) = i\mathbb{R}$ (vertical line)
- For any other $c \neq \infty$, $E_{\mathcal{R}}(c)$ is the -unique- circle passing through i and $-i$ and whose center is c

- For any d in its domain, $H_{\mathcal{A}}(d)$ is orthogonal to All circles of the form $E_{\mathcal{A}}(c)$, and is the only such circle whose center is d

And the same remarks obviously also hold for $E_{\mathcal{S}}$ and $H_{\mathcal{S}}$ i.e.

- $E_{\mathcal{S}}(\infty) = \mathbb{R}$ (horizontal line)
- For any other $D \neq \infty$, $E_{\mathcal{S}}(D)$ is the -unique- circle passing through 1 and -1 and whose center is D
- For any C in its domain, $H_{\mathcal{S}}(C)$ is orthogonal to All circles of the form $E_{\mathcal{S}}(D)$, and is the only such circle whose center is C

(Note that the above-mentioned orthogonality is trivial from the isomorphism with $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} = \mathbb{C}^{\times}$ -where equivalence classes w.r.t. $z \mapsto |z|^2$ are circles centred at 0, hence orthogonal to any line passing through 0, and so, to any equivalence class w.r.t. $z \mapsto z/\bar{z}$ - as well as the fact that Möbius Transformations are biconformal)

As already mentioned, such circles could naively be seen as the projection of meridians (case of E) and parallels (case of H) from the Riemann Sphere to the plane; however, they are known since antiquity and wear the name of "**Apollonian Circles**". In the common literature, a family of circles of the "H-form" is usually referred to as a "**Hyperbolic Pencil**" (as its elements can literally be regarded as "Hyperbolic Circles" on the Upper Half-Plane -in the sense of Hyperbolic Geometry-), while a family of circle of the "E-form" will be called "**Elliptic Pencil**"^[Zy] (though they can also be seen as "Hyperbolic Equidistant Curves" (or "Hypercycles"), -or even "Hyperbolic Lines" if we "cut the plane in half, in the perpendicular direction to those circles"...-).

The Apollonian Circles and other tools we just defined have many remarkable Geometrical features. The following Example will illustrate some of them.

Illustration of the previously defined objects on $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}$ and some of their remarkable geometrical properties (see lines)
Green: region of points sharing the same $\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}_{\mathcal{S}}$ as a given $z \in \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}$
Red: region of points sharing the same $\widehat{\mathfrak{J}}_{\mathcal{S}}$ as $z \in \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}$

Illustration of the previously defined objects on $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}$ and some of their remarkable geometrical properties (see lines)
Blue: region of points sharing the same $\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}_{\mathcal{R}}$ as a given $z \in \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}$
Orange: region of points sharing the same $\widehat{\mathfrak{J}}_{\mathcal{R}}$ as $z \in \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}$

Example 3.1.4.16. As already mentioned, the circles in the above pictures will intersect orthogonally at z and \hat{z} (deduced from the conformity of the isomorphisms $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}} \simeq \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}$ and $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}} \simeq \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}$), implying that the tangent line at z or \hat{z} will eventually meet the other circle's center; in other words, we have that the line joining a point z to $\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}(z)$ will always be perpendicular to the one joining z to $\widehat{\mathfrak{J}}(z)$. Also, as we usually tend to work with the modulus rather than its square, we can here define a "square root" of $\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}(z)$ w.r.t. the associated law $: \hat{\odot}$, name it $\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}(z)^{\hat{\odot}\frac{1}{2}}$ such that

$$\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}(z)^{\hat{\odot}\frac{1}{2}} \hat{\odot} \widehat{\mathfrak{K}}(z)^{\hat{\odot}\frac{1}{2}} = \widehat{\mathfrak{K}}(z) \quad (3.86)$$

This can easily be achieved by adding (or removing) to $\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}(z)$ the value of $\sqrt{1 + (\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}(z))^2}$ in the case of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}$ or $\sqrt{(\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}(z))^2 - 1}$ in the case of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{S}}$ (while geometrically, it obviously corresponds to the intersection of the appropriate circle with the axis of real numbers); a similar principle obviously holds for $\widehat{\mathfrak{J}}(z)$ (using $\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}_{\mathcal{S}}(iz) = i\widehat{\mathfrak{J}}_{\mathcal{R}}(z)$ and $\widehat{\mathfrak{J}}_{\mathcal{S}}(iz) = i\widehat{\mathfrak{K}}_{\mathcal{R}}(z)$). In a more general context, once we have a square root, the second one can naturally be obtained from the latter, via the canonical involution, as we obviously have :

$$z \odot z = \widehat{\widehat{z}} = \hat{z} \odot \hat{z} \quad (3.87)$$

notice that equivalently, we could have defined $\mathfrak{K}(z)^{\odot\frac{1}{2}}$ such that :

$$\mathfrak{K}(z)^{\odot\frac{1}{2}} \odot \mathfrak{K}(z)^{\odot\frac{1}{2}} = \mathfrak{K}(z) \quad (3.88)$$

We then see that

$$\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(z) = \widehat{\mathfrak{R}(z)} = (\mathfrak{R}(z)^{\odot \frac{1}{2}} \odot \widehat{\mathfrak{R}(z)^{\odot \frac{1}{2}}}) = \mathfrak{R}(z)^{\odot \frac{1}{2}} \hat{\odot} \mathfrak{R}(z)^{\odot \frac{1}{2}} \quad (3.89)$$

Hence we can set :

$$\mathfrak{R}(z)^{\odot \frac{1}{2}} := \widehat{\mathfrak{R}(q)^{\hat{\odot} \frac{1}{2}}}, \quad \widehat{\mathfrak{R}(z)^{\odot \frac{1}{2}}} = \widehat{\mathfrak{R}(z)^{\hat{\odot} \frac{1}{2}}} \quad (3.90)$$

It is then remarkable that drawing the line passing through a point z and a square root of $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(z)$ (say $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(z)^{\hat{\odot} \frac{1}{2}}$) and intersecting it with the axis of purely imaginary numbers gives a square root of $\widehat{\mathfrak{I}}(z)$ (we can call it $\widehat{\mathfrak{I}}(z)^{\hat{\odot} \frac{1}{2}}$), we can obviously do the same with the other square root (i.e.: $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(z)^{\hat{\odot} \frac{1}{2}}$), and notice that the two lines we just drew are perpendicular...

This kind of argument will turn out to be quite useful when we will want to find a geometric construction for (Quaternionic) Möbius transformations⁶.

⁶Notice that many of the things we are doing or will be doing can be in some sense regarded as a "very strong generalization of Stereographic Projections"...

Illustration of the above mentioned properties for $z := 0.6 + 0.8i \in \mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}$

3.2 Back to \mathbb{H} : \mathcal{L} , \mathcal{S} , and $SO(4)$

After having gotten some geometric intuition about properties related to the restriction of our groups in \mathbb{C} , we can now come back to Quaternions and study each of the (full) groups \mathcal{L} , \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{R} . At first sight, an important feature, which may make things much more "subtle", is that in \mathbb{H} , the symmetry -between real part and imaginary part- we had in \mathbb{C} is broken, such

that those 3 groups should -a priori- no longer be isomorphic to each other.

3.2.1 Characterizing \mathcal{L}

When restricted to \mathbb{C} , we had seen that the three groups were isomorphic to $\mathbb{R}^{>0} \times U(1) \simeq \mathbb{C}^\times$. As in \mathbb{H} they are -a priori- no longer isomorphic to each other, we will characterize them one by one. Here again, the easiest to start with will be \mathcal{L} .

Proposition 3.2.1.1. *The center of \mathcal{L} consists of the dilations, while the unitary linear Möbius Transformations are precisely the rotations in 4 dimensions. In other words, we have:*

$$\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{L}) \simeq \mathbb{R}^\times, \quad \mathcal{L}/\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{L}) \simeq SO(4)/\{\pm 1\} \quad (3.91)$$

i.e.

$$\mathcal{L} \simeq \mathbb{R}^{>0} \times SO(4) \quad (3.92)$$

Proof. This claim is **trivial**. However, if one really wants to be careful to check those results, it is still easy to calculate :

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{L}) &\iff \forall \begin{pmatrix} x & 0 \\ 0 & y \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{L}, \begin{pmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} x & 0 \\ 0 & y \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x & 0 \\ 0 & y \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \\ &\iff \begin{pmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} xAx^{-1} & 0 \\ 0 & yBy^{-1} \end{pmatrix} \\ &\iff \begin{pmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} \rho_x(A) & 0 \\ 0 & \rho_y(B) \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

We could be careful noting that we a priori only have an equivalence relation (i.e. up to a multiplication by some $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^\times$) and not an equality, however, as rotations preserve the Norm, we have

$$\forall x, y, \rho_x(A) = \pm A, \rho_y(B) = \pm B$$

The case where the sign is negative obviously being impossible as the only element of \mathbb{H} orthogonal to everything is $0 \notin \mathbb{H}^\times$, from which it is clear that

$$A, B \in \mathbb{R}^\times$$

is a necessary and sufficient condition for $q \mapsto AqB^{-1}$ to be in $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{L})$. In other words, $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{L})$ consists of all dilations $q \mapsto rq$, $r \in \mathbb{R}^\times$. Now now it is clear that any general transformation $q \mapsto AqB^{-1}$ of \mathcal{L} can be decomposed into a dilation -as above described- together with a transformation of the

form $q \mapsto aqb^{-1}$ with $|a| = |b| = 1$. Such transformations clearly preserve the Norm : $|aqb^{-1}| = |a||q||b|^{-1} = |q|$ and so must be a subgroup of $O(4)$. They also obviously contain $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) \simeq SO(3)$ as well as all 4-dimensional rotations of the form $q \mapsto uq$ sending 1 to any u unitary, while clearly not containing $q \mapsto \bar{q}$ (as any transformation of \mathcal{L} fixing 1 is clearly a rotation $\in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) \ni \bar{\cdot} : q \mapsto \bar{q}$) and hence preserving orientation. It is then then straightforward to deduce from those remarks that the transformations we are describing are precisely all 4-dimensional rotations; in other words, $SO(4)$. The only such nontrivial transformation also lying in $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{L})$ is clearly

$$T : q \mapsto -q$$

Thus clearly proving the second part of (3.91) as well as (3.92) □

Remark 3.2.1.2. Notice so far, we have decomposed elements of \mathcal{L} into a dilation, combined with a 4-D rotation, which in terms of matrices gives :

$$\begin{pmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{pmatrix}, \quad r \in \mathbb{R}^{>0}, |a| = |b| = 1 \quad (3.93)$$

But it can be useful to "decompose it further" :

$$\begin{pmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \mu & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha \end{pmatrix}, \quad r \in \mathbb{R}^{>0}, |\mu| = |\alpha| = 1 \quad (3.94)$$

Allowing us to notice the following homeomorphism :

$$\mathcal{L} \approx \mathbb{R}^{>0} \times SU(2) \times SO(3) \approx \mathbb{H}^{\times} \times \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) \approx (\mathbb{R}^4 \setminus \{1\}) \times \mathbf{P}^3(\mathbb{R}) \approx \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{S}^3 \times \mathbf{P}^3(\mathbb{R})$$

But being careful as this relation is "only a homeomorphism", i.e. only useful in a topological point of view, to parametrize elements of \mathcal{L} , but not an "isomorphism" of groups (because of the non-commutativity of the two last matrices)... However, it is still possible to construct a "2 to 1" surjective homomorphism :

$$\mathbb{R}^{>0} \times SU(2) \times SU(2) \rightarrow \mathcal{L} \quad (3.95)$$

allowing us to generate

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{i.e. } q \mapsto aqb^{-1}) \quad (3.96)$$

from

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{i.e. } q \mapsto aq) \quad (3.97)$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & b \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{i.e. } q \mapsto qb^{-1}) \quad (3.98)$$

the reason why it is "2 to 1" is obviously the equivalence :

$$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{i.e. } q \mapsto -q = (-1).q = q.(-1)) \quad (3.99)$$

3.2.2 "Diagonalizing" \mathcal{S}

Now that we have characterized \mathcal{L} , it will be very easy to study the structure of \mathcal{S} . Indeed, it turns out that even in \mathbb{H} , \mathcal{S} is still isomorphic to \mathcal{L} , as the matrix can still be diagonalized in the exact same way as in \mathbb{C} .

Proposition 3.2.2.1. \mathcal{S} is isomorphic to \mathcal{L} , and in particular,

$$\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{S}) \simeq \mathbb{R}^\times, \quad \mathcal{S}/\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{S}) \simeq SO(4)/\{\pm 1\}, \quad \mathcal{S} \simeq \mathbb{R}^{>0} \times SO(4) \quad (3.100)$$

Proof. Let $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix}$ be the matrix representation of an element of \mathcal{S} , then we can simply diagonalize it the following way:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 2(a+b) & 0 \\ 0 & 2(a-b) \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} (a+b) & 0 \\ 0 & (a-b) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.101)$$

□

Remark 3.2.2.2. This allows us to make the following correspondence :

\mathcal{L}	\mathcal{S}
$\begin{pmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} A+B & A-B \\ A-B & A+B \end{pmatrix} =: \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & A \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & A \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
$\begin{pmatrix} R & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, R \in \mathbb{R}^{>0}$	$\begin{pmatrix} R+1 & R-1 \\ R-1 & R+1 \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \frac{R-1}{R+1} \\ \frac{R-1}{R+1} & 1 \end{pmatrix} =: \begin{pmatrix} 1 & r \\ r & 1 \end{pmatrix}, r \in]-1, 1[$
$\begin{pmatrix} \mu & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \mu = 1, \mu \neq -1$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & \frac{\mu-1}{\mu+1} \\ \frac{\mu-1}{\mu+1} & 1 \end{pmatrix} =: \begin{pmatrix} 1 & V \\ V & 1 \end{pmatrix}, V + \bar{V} = 0$

3.2.3 Associated Field and Endomorphisms

The isomorphism exhibited in Proposition (3.2.2.1) can be used in order to create -as we did in Proposition (3.1.4.3) when working in \mathbb{C} - a (skew) field $\mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{L}} \simeq \mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{L}} = \mathbb{H}$, whose multiplicative law will be given by:

$$\mathbf{a} \odot \mathbf{b} := (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{a})^{-1}(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})(\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b})^{-1}(\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{a}) \quad (3.102)$$

and its "Dual"

$$a \hat{\odot} b := (1 - a)^{-1}(1 + ab)(a + b)^{-1}(1 - a) \quad (3.103)$$

(with here $\hat{q} := q^{-1}$)

Where we obviously still have:

$$\hat{a} \odot b = a \hat{\odot} b = a \odot \hat{b} = \widehat{a \odot b} \quad (3.104)$$

and also, the conjugation $q \mapsto \bar{q}$ clearly remains an antimorphism w.r.t. \odot (directly follows from the isomorphism we used to construct " \odot ")

This implies that we can construct -but this time on \mathbb{H} - the maps \mathfrak{R} and $\hat{\mathfrak{R}}$ as we did in **Section 3.1.4**, Definition (3.1.4.9), and those will still be endomorphisms⁷...

if we now "drop the rotation" associated to " \odot ", defining

$$\mathbf{a} * \mathbf{b} := (\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})(\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b})^{-1} \quad (3.105)$$

...We lose associativity (thus getting a "gyrogroup law"), we also lose Property (3.104) and finally, the conjugation is no longer an antimorphism...
...However, we can notice that $\mathfrak{R}(q) = \mathfrak{R}(\rho(q)) \forall \rho \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ (the same remark obviously holds for $\hat{\mathfrak{R}}$ too), i.e. \mathfrak{R} and $\hat{\mathfrak{R}}$ are invariant under rotations...
It follows that they remain endomorphisms ("of gyrogroups") w.r.t. $*$ as the next proposition will show.

Proposition 3.2.3.1. *Let $(\mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{L}}, \odot)$ as defined in (3.102), $(a, b) \mapsto a * b$ as defined in (3.105), and the Endomorphism (w.r.t. \odot):*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{R} : \mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\times} := \mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{H}) \setminus \{1, -1\} &\rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{L}}^{\geq} :=]-1, 1[\\ q \mapsto q \odot \bar{q} &= \frac{q + \bar{q}}{1 + q\bar{q}} \end{aligned}$$

⁷Note however that this only applies to the "Real Endomorphisms" (i.e. maps of the form $q \mapsto q \odot \bar{q}$), while noncommutativity will prevent us from defining "Imaginary" ones (as maps of the form $q \mapsto q \odot \bar{q}^{-1}$ are no longer morphisms -see Remark (3.1.4.10)-)

Then, \Re remains an endomorphism w.r.t. $*$, thus mapping the Gyrogroup $(\mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}, *)$ to the Commutative Subgroup : $(\mathbb{R}_{>}, \odot)$

Proof. We know that:

- $\forall q \in \mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}, \forall \rho \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}), \Re(\rho(q)) = \Re(q)$ (as $\Re(q)$ only depends on the Norm and Real Part of q)
- $\forall a, b \in \mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}, \Re(a \odot b) = \Re(a) \odot \Re(b) \in]-1, 1[\subset \mathbb{R}$ (endomorphism w.r.t. \odot)
- $a * b = \rho_{1-a}(a \odot b)$ (by definition)
- $ab = ba \implies a \odot b = a * b$ (in particular trivially true when $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$)

it immediately follows that:

$$\Re(a * b) = \Re(\rho(a \odot b)) = \Re(a \odot b) = \Re(a) \odot \Re(b) = \Re(a) * \Re(b) \quad (3.106)$$

□

Remark 3.2.3.2. As a particular case of Proposition (3.2.3.1), we have the following relations:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall q, V \in \mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}, \quad \Re(V) = 0 \implies \Re(V * q) &= \Re(V) \odot \Re(q) = 0 \odot \Re(q) = \Re(q) \\ &= \Re(q) \odot 0 = \Re(q) \odot \Re(V) = \Re(q * V) \end{aligned}$$

which arise from the fact that 0 is the neutral w.r.t. \odot or $*$. But as we know that

$$\Re(q) = \frac{q + \bar{q}}{1 + q\bar{q}} \quad (3.107)$$

which implies:

$$\Re(q) = 0 \iff (q = \infty \vee q + \bar{q} = 0) \iff (q = \infty \vee \text{Re}(q) = 0) \quad (3.108)$$

it follows that in general, **composing q with a purely imaginary quaternion V will let \Re (and eventually \Re) unchanged**, just as multiplying it (in the usual sense) by a unitary Quaternion would preserve its norm (those cases are obviously isomorphic).

Before continuing any further, it may be convenient to give a name to a previously encountered subgroup of \mathcal{S} .

Definition 3.2.3.3. I will denote by $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$ the group generated by combining maps of the following form:

- $q \mapsto (q + V)(Vq + 1)^{-1} = V * q, \quad V + \bar{V} = 0 \vee V = \infty$
- $q \mapsto aqa^{-1}, \quad a \in \mathbb{H}^\times$

Remark 3.2.3.4. Note that, as its name indicates, $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$ is obviously isomorphic to $SO(4)$, as a result of Proposition (3.2.2.1) as well as Remark (3.2.2.2).

Thanks to all those tools and remarks, it will now be easy to visualize the action of \mathcal{S} on $\mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}$, as it should be kept in mind that the latter can be obtained from $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$ together with $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{S})$ (see Proposition (3.2.2.1)). We start by having a look at $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$.

Proposition 3.2.3.5. $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$ preserves \mathfrak{R} (and so $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$), i.e.

$$\forall q \in \mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}, \forall f \in \mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}, \quad \mathfrak{R}(f(q)) = \mathfrak{R}(q), \quad \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(f(q)) = \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q) \quad (3.109)$$

In other words, geometrically speaking, transformations of $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$ move points on "hyperspheres" (centred at $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q)$) that generalize the previously defined "Hyperbolic Circles" of the form " $\mathbf{H}_{\mathcal{S}}(\mathbf{C})$ " -see Remark (3.1.4.15)-

Proof. (3.109) is just a trivial consequence of Remark (3.2.3.2) together with the fact that $\mathfrak{R}(\rho(q)) = \mathfrak{R}(q) \quad \forall \rho \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ (and also $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q) := \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(\widehat{q}) = \mathfrak{R}(q)^{-1}$). Now regarding the Geometrical interpretation, we know that $\forall q \in \mathbb{H}, \exists \ell \in \mathbb{L} : q \in \mathbb{C}_{\ell}$, which allows us to visualize things as in Remark (3.1.4.15) (in particular, $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q) \in \mathbb{R} \subseteq \mathbb{C}_{\ell} \forall \ell$ i.e. it obviously remains the "center of the circle/hypersphere") \square

Now it just remains to study the case of $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{S})$. For this, inspiring ourselves from Definition (3.1.4.9), we define the following object:

$$\mathfrak{J}(q) := \frac{q - \bar{q}}{1 - q\bar{q}} \quad (3.110)$$

As already mentioned, unlike the "Complex" case this will **not** be a morphism on $\mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}$, however, it will still be interesting in order to study the action of $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{S})$ as the latter consists of transformations of the form:

$$q \mapsto (q + r)(rq + 1)^{-1} = r * q, \quad r \in \mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{S}}^\times = (\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}) \setminus \{1, -1\} \quad (3.111)$$

This will thus imply the following:

Proposition 3.2.3.6. *Let $q \in \mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}$, \mathfrak{J} as defined in (3.110), and $f \in \mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{S})$, then*

$$\mathfrak{J}(f(q)) = \mathfrak{J}(q) \quad (3.112)$$

Proof. We know that $\exists r \in \mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} : f(q) = r * q$, while $\forall Q \in \mathbb{H}, \exists \ell \in \mathbb{L} : Q \in \mathbb{C}_{\ell}$ i.e. q will be in some $\mathbb{C}_{\ell, \mathcal{S}}^{\times} := (\mathbb{C}_{\ell} \cup \{\infty\}) \setminus \{1, -1\} \simeq \mathbb{C}^{\times}$ and given the fact that $r \in \mathbb{R}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} \subseteq \mathbb{C}_{\ell, \mathcal{S}}^{\times}$ we can treat this exactly like in \mathbb{C} -e.g.: see Remark (3.1.4.11)- and as $\mathfrak{J}(r) = 0$ and 0 is neutral w.r.t. $*$ ($= \odot_{\mathcal{S}}$ on $\mathbb{C}_{\ell, \mathcal{S}}^{\times}$) it follows that:

$$\mathfrak{J}(f(q)) = \mathfrak{J}(r*q) = \mathfrak{J}(r \odot_{\mathcal{S}} q)_{(\mathbb{C}_{\ell})} = \mathfrak{J}(r) \odot_{\mathcal{S}} \mathfrak{J}(q) = 0 \odot_{\mathcal{S}} \mathfrak{J}(q) = \mathfrak{J}(q) \quad (3.113)$$

□

To summarize, the orbit of $q \in \mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}$ w.r.t. the action of $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$ will be a Hypersphere generalizing the "Hyperbolic Circles" $H_{\mathcal{S}}(C)$ defined in Remark (3.1.4.15), and centred at $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q)$ while its orbit w.r.t. $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{S})$ will be exactly a locus (in the subfield $\simeq \mathbb{C}$ containing q) of the form $E_{\mathcal{S}}(D)$ such as defined in Remark (3.1.4.15), and centred at $\widehat{\mathfrak{J}}(q)$, where $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$ and $\widehat{\mathfrak{J}}$ are defined as in Def. (3.1.4.9), i.e.

$$\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q) := \frac{q\bar{q} + 1}{q + \bar{q}}, \quad \widehat{\mathfrak{J}}(q) := \frac{1 - q\bar{q}}{q + \bar{q}} \quad (3.114)$$

(Note that, as an abuse of notation, I have been omitting the indexes, writing $\mathfrak{R}, \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}, \mathfrak{J}, \widehat{\mathfrak{J}}$ instead of $\mathfrak{R}_{\mathcal{S}}, \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}_{\mathcal{S}}, \mathfrak{J}_{\mathcal{S}}, \widehat{\mathfrak{J}}_{\mathcal{S}}$ though such objects will later also be (re-)defined in the context of \mathcal{R})

Now that we have a rough idea of how \mathcal{S} acts on $\mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}$ (or more generally, $\mathbf{P}^1(\mathbb{H})$), we will see that it is actually very simple to visualize, as it can in fact be constructed by *Compass-and-Straightedge*. This will be the object of the next subsection.

3.2.4 Compass-and-Straightedge Construction for \mathcal{S}

We now seek to suggest a geometrical construction for transformations of \mathcal{S} , which can be decomposed into $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$ and $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{S})$. We start by looking at $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$ with the following example.

Action of $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$

Example 3.2.4.1. As the above pictures illustrate, we managed to construct $(q+b)(bq+1)^{-1}$ by :

- Drawing the Apollonius Circle (*H-type*) associated to q
- Drawing a line passing through the Origin and q , that then allows us to find \bar{q}^{-1} as it intersects again with the Apollonius Circle
- Drawing the line from the point we just obtained ($= \bar{q}^{-1}$) to the point b (provided that $b + \bar{b} = 0$)

Although those illustrations are in two dimensions, and we would expect such a method to (at best) only work in Complex Numbers, it turns out that it still works perfectly well in 4 dimensions (just replace "circle" by "hypersphere"), when using Quaternions ! In other words, it is always possible, by only drawing a circle (or "hypersphere" in \mathbb{H}) and two lines, to construct any transformation of the form :

$$q \mapsto (q+b)(bq+1)^{-1} = b * q, \quad b + \bar{b} = 0 \quad (3.115)$$

(NB: Notice we implicitly assume that " \bar{q}^{-1} can be drawn", i.e. that it is well defined on \mathbb{H} ; although the case $q = 0$ is thus an exception to the above mentioned rule, it is in no means a problem, given the fact that this case is

trivial to deal with, as we have $(0 + b)(1 + b \cdot 0)^{-1} = b$

As we know -e.g. see Proposition (3.1.2.2)- that any transformation of $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$ can always be decomposed into a rotation and a map of the form (3.115) (or possibly $q \mapsto \hat{q} := q^{-1}$) it follows that the above method allows to represent virtually *any* transformation of $\mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$. The proof of this claim will be based on the following *Lemma*:

Lemma 3.2.4.2. *Let $q \in \mathbb{H}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\times} = (\mathbb{H} \cup \{\infty\}) \setminus \{1, -1\}$, and let $b \in \mathbb{RL}$, then the following holds :*

1. q, \bar{q}^{-1} and $(q + b)(bq + 1)^{-1}$ lie in the same Apollonius Circle (or "hypersphere") -**H(C)** including "degenerate case"-
2. O, q and \bar{q}^{-1} are in a same line
3. b, \bar{q}^{-1} and $(q + b)(bq + 1)^{-1}$ are also in a same line

Proof. The proof of (1) is trivial (noting that assuming $q \neq \infty$ as well as $q + \bar{q} \neq 0$ would imply $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q) \neq \infty$, in order to literally have a *circle* (Hypersphere), however, the argument still works in the degenerate case). Although the proof of (2) is more straightforward than (3), they both rely on the same principle : we may first assume without loss of generality that $q \notin \{0, \infty\}$ (otherwise, although it would seem to be a *degenerate case*, we can consider that $0, b, \infty$ are on the same line) then we define an equivalence relation:

$$A \sim B \iff \exists \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{\times} : B = \lambda A$$

Then it is obvious that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (2) \quad & \iff (q - O) \sim (\bar{q}^{-1} - O) \\
 & \iff q \sim \bar{q}^{-1} \\
 & \iff q \cdot (q\bar{q}) \sim \bar{q}^{-1} \cdot (q\bar{q}) \\
 & \iff q \cdot (q\bar{q}) \sim q \\
 & \iff q \sim q
 \end{aligned}$$

Now to prove (3), not only do we assume w.l.o.g. that $q \notin \{0, \infty\}$ but we also consider that $bq \neq -1$ (the cases where $q = 0$ or $bq = -1$ also being trivial to deal with separately, as q would be sent to ∞ , and it can be considered that any line meets ∞ , while in the case $q = \infty$, we would get $b, 0, b^{-1}$ which are obviously in the same line). The proof then follows the

same principle :

$$\begin{aligned}
(3) \quad &\iff b - \bar{q}^{-1} \sim b - (q + b)(bq + 1)^{-1} \\
&\iff (\bar{q}b - 1)(1 + bq) \sim \bar{q}(1 + bq) - q\bar{q} - \bar{q}b \\
&\iff -(1 + bq)\overline{(1 + bq)} \sim \bar{q}b + \bar{q}qb^2 - \bar{q}q - \bar{q}b \\
&\iff (1 + bq)\overline{(1 + bq)} \sim \bar{q}q(b^2 - 1)
\end{aligned}$$

The last equivalence being obviously true as both sides are real numbers, notice that thanks to our assumptions, they are also non-zero : on the left hand side thanks to our assumption that $bq \neq -1$, as well as on the right hand side as we assumed $q \neq 0$ and $b + \bar{b} = 0$ (i.e. its square is a negative real number); notice that the latter hypothesis has also clearly been used to allow us to transform \bar{b} into $-b$, as well as allowing b^2 to commute with q . \square

Corollary 3.2.4.3. *Let $q \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \{1, -1\}$ such that $q + \bar{q} \neq 0$, and $b \in \mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}$, then the transformation:*

$$q \mapsto b * q = (q + b)(bq + 1)^{-1} \quad (3.116)$$

can be constructed Geometrically with the method described in Example (3.2.4.1).

Proof. Direct consequence of Lemma (3.2.4.2), noting that our assumption that $q + \bar{q} \neq 0$ is sufficient to prevent any "Degenerate Case" (in particular, we have $\hat{\mathfrak{A}}(q) \neq \infty$, $q \neq 0, q \neq \infty$ (by assumption), $bq \neq -1$) \square

Remark 3.2.4.4. *Many of the ("degenerate") cases that we omitted with our assumptions are usually trivial to deal with, for instance, the case where $b = \infty$ would send q to q^{-1} , and the Geometrical argument would still work, the last line we would draw simply being vertical.*

Action of $Z(\mathcal{S})$

Remark 3.2.4.5. Using the Exact Same Arguments, we can study the action of $Z(\mathcal{S})$ i.e. transformations of the form :

$$q \mapsto r * q = (q + r)(rq + 1)^{-1}, \quad r \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{1, -1\} \quad (3.117)$$

(while $q \mapsto q^{-1}$: the case "r = ∞ ")

We basically just have to replace \bar{q}^{-1} by $-\bar{q}^{-1}$ in Example (3.2.4.1) and work with Apollonius Circles of Type **E** instead of Type **H** (see Rmk (3.1.4.15)) while the argument to prove it is exactly the same as in Lemma (3.2.4.2)

Now given the fact that every transformation in \mathcal{S} can be decomposed into:

- a rotation $q \mapsto aqa^{-1} \in \text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) \subset \mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$

- a transformation of the type $q \mapsto (q + b)(bq + 1)^{-1} \in \mathcal{S}_{SO(4)}$
- a transformation of the form $q \mapsto (q + r)(rq + 1)^{-1} \in Z(\mathcal{S})$

We can now geometrically construct any transformation of \mathcal{S} , as well as efficiently using the group laws \odot and $\hat{\odot}$ (or the gyrogroup laws $*$ and $\hat{*}$)

3.3 \mathcal{R} and the Lorentz Group $SO(3, 1)^+$

3.3.1 "Diagonalizing" \mathcal{R} using Biquaternions

Inspiring ourselves from the way we explored \mathcal{S} , we will seek to study \mathcal{R} . Here, however, unlike the case of \mathcal{S} , if we try to "diagonalize the matrix", imaginary numbers appear. This would not be a problem if we were only working in \mathbb{C} (and this is why $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathcal{S}_{\mathbb{C}} \simeq \mathcal{R}_{\mathbb{C}} \dots$) but here in \mathbb{H} , apart from the fact that things might a priori get more complicated because of the non-commutativity, the biggest issue probably remains the fact that we would like not to break the symmetry; in other words, avoiding to "privilege" a certain $\ell \in \mathbb{L} \dots$ It is actually possible to get around this problem by "cheating" a little bit : as we obviously can't find any $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ that would commute with all the rest, nor anything else in \mathbb{H} that would play the same role as i in \mathbb{C} , we go take something from outside \mathbb{H} ; more precisely, we look at biquaternions:

$$\mathbb{C} \otimes_{\mathbb{R}} \mathbb{H} =: \mathbb{C} \otimes \mathbb{H}$$

Let then $h := i \otimes 1 \in \mathbb{C} \otimes \mathbb{H}$, we do have :

$$h^2 = -1 \wedge hq = qh \forall q \in \mathbb{C} \otimes \mathbb{H}$$

This allows us to "diagonalize" the matrix, exhibiting an isomorphism between transformations of \mathcal{R} and a special kind of linear transformations on $\mathbb{C} \otimes \mathbb{H}$; we then recognize a group that is well known for being isomorphic to the **Lorentz Group** (standard formulation of the Lorentz Group in terms of Biquaternions)... Indeed, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -h \\ -h & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a & -b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & h \\ h & 1 \end{pmatrix} &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -h \\ -h & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a - bh & ah - b \\ b + ah & a + bh \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} 2(a - bh) & 0 \\ 0 & 2(a + bh) \end{pmatrix} \\ &\sim \begin{pmatrix} (a - bh) & 0 \\ 0 & (a + bh) \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

i.e.

$$q \mapsto (a - bh)q(a + bh)^{-1} \quad (3.118)$$

In fact, the group of transformations of the form (3.118) is not yet "exactly" the Lorentz group : it is a bit more general, but we can then define the following sets:

Definition 3.3.1.1 (Imaginary Open Ball). *I will call "Imaginary Open Ball" and denote by $\tilde{\mathbb{V}}$ the following set:*

$$\tilde{\mathbb{V}} := [0, 1[\mathbb{L} = \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q\bar{q} < 1 \wedge q + \bar{q} = 0\} \quad (3.119)$$

It will then turn out that transformations of \mathcal{R} sending 0 (or any other element of $\tilde{\mathbb{V}}$) to an element of $\tilde{\mathbb{V}}$ (actually stabilizing $\tilde{\mathbb{V}}$) will form a subgroup, as it will be shown. Anticipating this, we already define:

Definition 3.3.1.2 (Automorphisms of \mathbb{L}). *I will denote by $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ the following subset of \mathcal{R} :*

$$\mathbf{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) := \{g \in \mathcal{R} : g(0) \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}}\} \quad (3.120)$$

It will later be referred to as "Group of Automorphisms of \mathbb{L} "

Proposition 3.3.1.3. *$\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ is isomorphic to the standard representation of the Lorentz Group in terms of Biquaternions, i.e.*

$$\mathbf{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) \simeq \mathbf{SO}(3, 1)^+ \quad (3.121)$$

Proof. Let $g : q \mapsto (aq - b)(bq + a)^{-1}$ be an element of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$, we first "diagonalize" it as described above, in order to get a map of the form (3.118). Also, we note that $g(0) = -ba^{-1} \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}} \implies |b| < |a|$ and so in particular, (3.118) can be rewritten as

$$q \mapsto \left(\frac{a - bh}{a\bar{a} - b\bar{b}} \right) q \left(\frac{a + bh}{a\bar{a} - b\bar{b}} \right)^{-1} \quad (3.122)$$

Then, defining on $\mathbb{C} \otimes \mathbb{H}$ two different kinds of *conjugation*:

$$\overline{(q_1 + q_2h)} := \bar{q}_1 + \bar{q}_2h \quad (3.123)$$

$$(q_1 + q_2h)^* := q_1 - q_2h \quad (3.124)$$

we see from the fact that $ba^{-1} \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}} \implies b\bar{a} = -a\bar{b} \in \mathbb{RL}$ that $G := \frac{a+bh}{a\bar{a}-b\bar{b}}$ will satisfy $G\bar{G} = 1$, so that (3.122) can be rewritten as

$$q \mapsto G^*q\bar{G}, \quad G\bar{G} = 1 \quad (3.125)$$

which is precisely the *well-known*⁸ formulation of the Lorentz Group in terms of Biquaternions. \square

Remark 3.3.1.4. *As already mentioned, for $g : q \mapsto (aq - b)(bq + a)^{-1}$, the condition $g(0) \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}}$ is equivalent to $ba^{-1} \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}}$ thus implying $a \neq 0$, and so for any element of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$, it can be assumed without loss of generality (just dividing all coefficients by $|a|$) that $|a| = 1$. Such a normalization may often be useful; however, it will not be stable under composition. It is still possible, though, to find a normalization that would remain stable under composition (thus playing a role analogous to "Det = 1"). To notice this, it suffices to have a look at Equation (3.122) where it appears clear that such a normalization will be given by*

$$a\bar{a} - b\bar{b} = 1 \quad (3.126)$$

Also, it is easy to see that the center of \mathcal{R} , i.e. $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbb{R})$ is given by transformations of the form

$$\begin{pmatrix} r & -s \\ s & r \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.127)$$

where $r, s \in \mathbb{R}$, but -as we work with ratios ($r : s$)- this is clearly isomorphic to $U(1)$, and it can be seen that $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) \simeq \mathcal{R}/\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$. More formally:

Proposition 3.3.1.5. *Aut(\mathbb{L}) is a Normal subgroup of \mathcal{R} , furthermore, the following relations apply:*

$$\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R}) \simeq U(1) \quad (3.128)$$

$$\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) \simeq \mathcal{R}/\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R}) \simeq SO(3, 1)^+ \quad (3.129)$$

$$\mathcal{R} \simeq \mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R}) \times \text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) \simeq U(1) \times SO(3, 1)^+ \quad (3.130)$$

Proof. As most of those relations have already been discussed, the main point is to notice that any general element of \mathcal{R} can be split into an element of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ composed with an element of $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$. This is quite obvious, as for $g \in \mathcal{R}$,

- either $g(0) = \infty$, in which case composing it with $q \mapsto -q^{-1}$ will give an element of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ (sending 0 to $0 \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}}$ (more precisely, a rotation))
- or $g(0) \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \{\mathbb{L}\}$, in which case there will be $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ such that $g(0) \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \setminus \{\ell, -\ell\}$, thus getting back to the Complex case (e.g. see remark (3.1.4.15)), where the existence of $f \in \mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R}) : f(g(0)) \in \ell] - 1, 1[\subseteq \tilde{\mathbb{V}}$ is

⁸should the reader not be familiar with this specific formulation, another proof of the isomorphism $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) \simeq SO(3, 1)^+$ will be given later -see Proposition (3.4.1.5)-

trivial. (In fact, it is easy to calculate that the map $f \in \mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$ we are looking for will be of the form $f : q \mapsto (q-r)(1+rq) =: ((-r) \odot_{\mathcal{R}} q)_{(\mathbb{C}_\ell)}$ where $r \in \mathbb{R} \subseteq \mathbb{C}_\ell$ is of the form $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}_{\mathcal{R}}(g(0)) \pm \sqrt{(\mathfrak{R}_{\mathcal{R}}(g(0)))^2 + 1}$ (as in Def. (3.1.4.9), or Rmk. (3.1.4.12) for the explicit form), where $\sqrt{(\mathfrak{R}_{\mathcal{R}}(q))^2 + 1}$ represents the radius of $\mathbf{E}_{\mathcal{R}}(\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q))$, such that r is one of the two roots $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(g(0))^{\hat{\circ} \frac{1}{2}}$ as defined in Ex. (3.1.4.16))

□

We will now tend to focus more on $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ rather than $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$ (even though the latter also does have a Physical meaning).

Remark 3.3.1.6. If $\begin{pmatrix} a & -b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix}$ represents an element of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$, then its inverse is simply represented by $\begin{pmatrix} \bar{a} & -\bar{b} \\ \bar{b} & \bar{a} \end{pmatrix}$ as we have:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & -b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \bar{a} & -\bar{b} \\ \bar{b} & \bar{a} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (a\bar{a} - b\bar{b}) & -(a\bar{b} + b\bar{a}) \\ (a\bar{b} + b\bar{a}) & (a\bar{a} - b\bar{b}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (a\bar{a} - b\bar{b}) & 0 \\ 0 & (a\bar{a} - b\bar{b}) \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.131)$$

(Since the condition of being in $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ implies $a\bar{b} = -b\bar{a}$)

Remark 3.3.1.7. Note that obviously, any transformation of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ can always be decomposed into:

- a **Rotation**:

$$\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H}) \ni \rho_a : q \mapsto aqa^{-1}, \quad a \in \mathbb{H}^\times \text{ (w.l.o.g. } |a| = 1) \quad (3.132)$$

- a **Boost** (see Definition (3.1.2.6)):

$$\mathfrak{b} : q \mapsto (\beta + q)(1 - \beta q)^{-1}, \quad \beta \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}} \quad (3.133)$$

3.3.2 Gyrogroup Endomorphisms and invariants under $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$

Seeing the expression of a *boost*, i.e. (3.133), it is tempting to define (as we did in $\mathbb{C}_{\mathcal{R}}$, Proposition (3.1.4.3)) a *tangent-like composition law* :

$$* : (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\} \times (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\} \rightarrow (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\} \quad (3.134)$$

$$(a, b) \mapsto a * b := (a + b)(1 - ab)^{-1} \quad (3.135)$$

Note however that, unlike the *complex* case, this composition law is not associative when defined on Quaternions, however, it does keep *all* the other *nice properties* of a Group (in particular, the existence of a -unique- Neutral element, as well a -unique- inverse for each element), and is thus -again- referred to as *Gyrogroup*.

Remark 3.3.2.1. *The non-associativity appears obvious from the fact that the inverse map is a **Morphism**, rather than an **Antimorphism**, which on a group, should only occur if the latter is Commutative, which is obviously not the case here. To be more precise, it is clear that the Neutral element w.r.t. $*$ will be 0, while the inverse of q will be given by $-q$. then it appears that:*

$$-(a * b) = -((a + b)(1 - ab)^{-1}) \quad (3.136)$$

$$((-a) + (-b))(1 - (-a)(-b))^{-1} \quad (3.137)$$

$$= (-a) * (-b) \neq (-b) * (-a) \quad (3.138)$$

Remark 3.3.2.2. *Note however that restricted on any $(\mathbb{C}_\ell \setminus \{\ell, -\ell\}) \cup \{\infty\} \subset (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\}$, $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ and in particular, in $\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\} \subset (\mathbb{C}_\ell \setminus \{\ell, -\ell\}) \cup \{\infty\}$, $\forall \ell \in \mathbb{L}$, " $*$ " becomes associative, and I may denote it by $\odot_{\mathcal{R}}$ to emphasize this fact.*

It still remains possible, though, to define an "endomorphism" as we did before with in the case of \mathcal{S} Indeed, let us define:

$$\mathfrak{R} : (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\} : q \mapsto \frac{q + \bar{q}}{1 - q\bar{q}} \quad (3.139)$$

$$\widehat{\mathfrak{R}} : (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\} : q \mapsto \frac{q\bar{q} - 1}{q + \bar{q}} \quad (3.140)$$

(noting that here again, as an abuse of notation, I omitted the indexes, thus writing $\mathfrak{R}, \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$ instead of $\mathfrak{R}_{\mathcal{R}}, \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}_{\mathcal{R}}$, though such objects had already been defined in the case of \mathcal{S} -it seems quite clear that we are going to work on \mathcal{R} in this section thus avoiding any ambiguity-)

It can then be seen that, despite the loss of associativity, \mathfrak{R} will remain an "endomorphism" just as it was in the Complex case, as the following proposition will show.

Proposition 3.3.2.3. *\mathfrak{R} is an **Endomorphism**, mapping the **Gyrogroup** $((\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\}, *)$ to the (sub)**Group** $(\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}, *) = (\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}, \odot_{\mathcal{R}})$, i.e.*

$$\mathfrak{R}(a * b) = \mathfrak{R}(a) * \mathfrak{R}(b) = \mathfrak{R}(a) \odot_{\mathcal{R}} \mathfrak{R}(b) \quad (3.141)$$

Proof. We will prove this in a very "unsubtle" way, by just calculating the expressions and comparing the results.

First develop⁹ $\mathfrak{R}(a) * \mathfrak{R}(b)$

$$\mathfrak{R}(a) * \mathfrak{R}(b) = \frac{\mathfrak{R}(a) + \mathfrak{R}(b)}{1 - \mathfrak{R}(a)\mathfrak{R}(b)} \quad (3.142)$$

$$= \frac{\left(\frac{a+\bar{a}}{1-a\bar{a}}\right) + \left(\frac{b+\bar{b}}{1-b\bar{b}}\right)}{1 - \left(\frac{a+\bar{a}}{1-a\bar{a}}\right)\left(\frac{b+\bar{b}}{1-b\bar{b}}\right)} \quad (3.143)$$

$$= \frac{(a + \bar{a})(1 - b\bar{b}) + (1 - a\bar{a})(b + \bar{b})}{(1 - a\bar{a})(1 - b\bar{b}) - (a + \bar{a})(b + \bar{b})} \quad (3.144)$$

Now we seek to do the same with $\mathfrak{R}(a * b)$; for simplicity, we denote:

$$N := (a + b) \quad (3.145)$$

$$D := (1 - ab) \quad (3.146)$$

then,

$$\mathfrak{R}(a * b) = \mathfrak{R}(ND^{-1}) \quad (3.147)$$

$$= \frac{ND^{-1} + \overline{ND^{-1}}}{1 - ND^{-1}\overline{ND^{-1}}} \quad (3.148)$$

$$= \frac{\left(\frac{ND}{DD}\right) + \overline{\left(\frac{ND}{DD}\right)}}{1 - \left(\frac{ND}{DD}\right)\overline{\left(\frac{ND}{DD}\right)}} \quad (3.149)$$

$$= \frac{D\bar{D}(ND + D\bar{N})}{(D\bar{D})^2 - N(D\bar{D})\bar{N}} \quad (3.150)$$

$$= \frac{N\bar{D} + D\bar{N}}{D\bar{D} - N\bar{N}} \quad (3.151)$$

$$(3.152)$$

⁹Note that the fraction bar $\frac{A}{B}$ can be used when the numerator and denominator commute (in particular, $\mathfrak{R}(q) \in \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$)

and so,

$$= \frac{(a+b)\overline{(1-ab)} + (1-ab)\overline{(a+b)}}{(1-ab)\overline{(1-ab)} - (a+b)\overline{(a+b)}} \quad (3.153)$$

$$= \frac{a+b - a\bar{b}\bar{a} - b\bar{b}\bar{a} + \bar{a} + \bar{b} - ab\bar{a} - abb\bar{b}}{1-ab - \bar{b}\bar{a} + a\bar{a}b\bar{b} - a\bar{a} - a\bar{b} - b\bar{a} - b\bar{b}} \quad (3.154)$$

$$= \frac{(a+\bar{a}) + (b+\bar{b}) - (abb\bar{b} + \bar{a}b\bar{b}) + (ab\bar{a} + a\bar{b}\bar{a})}{1 - a\bar{a} - b\bar{b} + a\bar{a}b\bar{b} - (ab + \bar{b}\bar{a} + a\bar{b} + b\bar{a})} \quad (3.155)$$

$$= \frac{(a+\bar{a})(1-b\bar{b}) + (b+\bar{b}) + a(b+\bar{b})\bar{a}}{(1-a\bar{a})(1-b\bar{b}) - (a(b+\bar{b}) + (b+\bar{b})\bar{a})} \quad (3.156)$$

$$= \frac{(a+\bar{a})(1-b\bar{b}) + (b+\bar{b}) + a(b+\bar{b})\bar{a}}{(1-a\bar{a})(1-b\bar{b}) - (a(b+\bar{b}) + \bar{a}(b+\bar{b}))} \quad (3.157)$$

$$= \frac{(a+\bar{a})(1-b\bar{b}) + (1-a\bar{a})(b+\bar{b})}{(1-a\bar{a})(1-b\bar{b}) - (a+\bar{a})(b+\bar{b})} \quad (3.158)$$

which thus gives back (3.144), proving the equality. \square

This result has important consequences, as we can immediately deduce the following:

Corollary 3.3.2.4 (Invariants). \mathfrak{R} and $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$ are invariant under transformations of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$, i.e.

$$\forall q \in (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\}, \forall g \in \text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}), \mathfrak{R}(g(q)) = \mathfrak{R}(q), \quad \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(g(q)) = \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q) \quad (3.159)$$

Proof. Proving it for \mathfrak{R} is obviously enough -as $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$ is obtained from the latter-stability under Rotations is trivial, it thus just remains to check stability under Boosts (see Remark (3.3.1.7)), but the latter directly follows from Proposition (3.3.2.3), as any boost can be written as

$$q \mapsto \beta * q, \quad \beta \in \widetilde{\mathbb{V}} \subset \mathbb{RL}$$

and clearly

$$\forall \beta \in \widetilde{\mathbb{V}}, \mathfrak{R}(\beta) = 0$$

while 0 is the Neutral Element w.r.t. $*$ \square

Remark 3.3.2.5. Here again, the orbit of a point q w.r.t. the action of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ will -when adding \mathbb{L} - correspond to "hyperspheres" generalizing the previously-defined Apollonian Circles (\mathbf{E} - type), and centered at $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q)$ -see Remark (3.1.4.15)-

To be more precise, let $\mathbf{E}(\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q))$ be the unique hypersphere centred at $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q)$ and including \mathbb{L} , then the orbit of q under the action of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ will be $E(\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q)) \setminus \mathbb{L}$. In other words, $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$ can naturally be given:

- An Algebraic meaning (Invariant obtained from an Endomorphism)
- A Geometric meaning (Center of the Hypersphere containing the orbit of an element w.r.t. $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$)
- A physical meaning (may be used to replace the use of "Minkowski's pseudo-norm")

In the next subsection, we will see how to use the Geometrical interpretation of $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$ to better visualize the action of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ on $(\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\}$

3.3.3 Compass-and-Straightedge Construction for $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$

As we did for \mathcal{S} , it will here again be possible to represent geometrically a transformation of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$. As rotations are trivial to visualize, we will look at *boosts*. Here again, the set we are supposed to be working with is $(\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\}$, however, as the goal is rather to *visualize* things, we will tend not to bother trying to represent the "point at ∞ ", and will mainly look at points in \mathbb{H} , and even in some \mathbb{C}_ℓ when it comes to illustrations, just as we did in the case of \mathcal{S} . Here again, even though the method will be illustrated in 2 dimensions, it should be kept in mind that it also does work perfectly well in 4 dimensions, as the proof will show...

Example 3.3.3.1. *As the above picture shows, the image of q by the boost:*

$$q \mapsto (b + q)(1 - bq)^{-1}, b \in \tilde{\mathfrak{V}}$$

has been obtained by :

- Drawing the ($\mathbf{E}_{\mathcal{A}}$ -type) "Apollonian Circle¹⁰" (Hypersphere in 4D) passing through q
- Drawing the line passing through q and the origin, thus meeting the Circle/Hypersphere at $-\bar{q}^{-1}$
- Drawing the line passing through $-\bar{q}^{-1}$ and b , which should then meet the Circle/Hypersphere at $b * q$, i.e. the point we are looking for

The proof of this will be based on the Lemma that will follow. Note that, as already mentioned, although the drawing illustrates a situation in two dimensions (i.e. would a priori work at best in \mathbb{C}), the proof of the Lemma does Not use Commutativity nor any other property that \mathbb{C} could have over \mathbb{H} ; it is thus a *General Method* for \mathbb{H} , and by **no** means a "very particular case".

Lemma 3.3.3.2. *Let $q \in (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\}$, and $b \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}} \subset \mathbb{RL}$, then the following holds:*

1. $q, -\bar{q}^{-1}$, and $b * q = (b + q)(1 - bq)^{-1}$ lie in the same $\mathbf{E}_{\mathcal{A}}(c)$ (Apollonian Circle/Hypersphere, "degenerate case" included)
2. q, O and $-\bar{q}^{-1}$ are on a same line
3. $-\bar{q}^{-1}, b$, and $b * q = (b + q)(1 - bq)^{-1}$ are also aligned

Proof. The proof of **(1)** is trivial as $\mathfrak{R}(b * q) = \mathfrak{R}(q) = \mathfrak{R}(-\bar{q}^{-1})$ (noting that assuming $q \neq \infty$ and $q + \bar{q} \neq 0$ would imply $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q) \neq \infty$, in order to really have a "Circle" (Hypersphere), however, the claim still holds in the "degenerate case"). Now the proof of **(2)** and **(3)** will follow the same principle as in the case of \mathcal{S} -Lemma (3.2.4.2)- as we first assume without loss of generality that $q \notin \{0, \infty\}$ (otherwise, considering that "any line passes through ∞ ", both **(2)** and **(3)** become trivial), then we can -again- use the following Equivalence Relation:

$$A, B \in \mathbb{H}^\times, A \sim B \iff \rho_A = \rho_B \quad (\text{i.e. } \iff \exists \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^\times : A = \lambda B) \quad (3.160)$$

Then -in general- to prove that some α, β, γ are in a same line, it suffices to show that

$$(\alpha - \beta) \sim (\beta - \gamma)$$

¹⁰in the drawing (i.e. in two dimensions), it appears as a circle passing through q and $\pm \ell$ ($\ell^2 = -1$). In \mathbb{H} (i.e. 4 Dimensions), it should be seen as the Hypersphere passing through q as well as \mathbb{L} . Its center is given by $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q)$

We first show **(2)** :

$$(q - 0) \sim (0 - (-\bar{q}^{-1})) \iff q \sim \bar{q}^{-1} \iff q\bar{q} \sim 1 \quad (3.161)$$

which is clearly the case as $q\bar{q} \in \mathbb{R}$. Now with the same argument, we shall prove **(3)** (here we can also assume w.l.o.g. that $bq \neq 1$ otherwise trivial) :

$$(b - (-\bar{q}^{-1})) \sim (b * q - b) \iff (b - (-\bar{q}^{-1})) \sim ((b + q)(1 - bq)^{-1} - b) \quad (3.162)$$

$$\iff (q\bar{b} + 1)(1 - bq) \sim \bar{q}(b + q) - \bar{q}b(1 - bq) \quad (3.163)$$

$$\iff \overline{(1 - bq)}(1 - bq) \sim \bar{q}(b + q - b + b^2q) = q\bar{q}(1 + b^2) \quad (3.164)$$

while the expression at the left hand side of (3.164) arises from the fact that $\bar{b} = -b$ (as $b \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}} \subseteq \mathbb{RL}$) that expression is then real and, as $b^2 \in \mathbb{R}$, so is the expression at the right hand side. (also note that our assumptions imply that $q\bar{q} \neq 0$ and $|b| < 1$) \square

Corollary 3.3.3.3. *Let $q \in \mathbb{H}$ such that $q + \bar{q} \neq 0$, and $b \in \tilde{\mathbb{V}} \subset \mathbb{RL}$, then the transformation*

$$b * q = (b + q)(1 - bq)^{-1} \quad (3.165)$$

Can be constructed Geometrically exactly as described in Example (3.3.3.1).

Proof. Direct consequence of Lemma (3.3.3.2), noting that the condition that $q + \bar{q} \neq 0$ not only automatically implies that $q \in \mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}$, but also prevents any "degenerate case" from occurring, as we automatically get $q \neq \infty, q \neq 0, bq \neq 1, \hat{\mathfrak{R}}(q) \neq \infty \dots$ \square

Remark 3.3.3.4. *Although many "degenerate cases" we omitted with our assumptions are easy to deal with, we will not spend time describing them, as they would not be so relevant for our purposes. In particular, if one is interested in "doing Relativistic Physics" with those tools, the set which seems to be relevant to work with would rather be:*

$$\mathbb{H}^+ := \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q + \bar{q} > 0\} \quad (3.166)$$

Which would automatically satisfy the conditions of Corollary (3.3.3.3) (Note the analogy with "Poincaré's Upper Half-Plane")

3.3.4 Compass-and-Straightedge Construction for $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$

With the exact same argument, it can be shown that the transformations of $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$ can be constructed as follows:

Example 3.3.4.1. *The map*

$$\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R}) \ni F : q \mapsto r * q = (r + q)(1 - rq)^{-1}, \quad r \in \mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\} \quad (3.167)$$

is constructed by:

- Drawing the ($\mathbf{H}_{\mathcal{R}}$ -type) Apollonian Circle in \mathbb{C}_q passing through q and (thus centred at $\widehat{\mathcal{J}}_{\mathcal{R}}(q) := \frac{-(q\bar{q}+1)}{q-\bar{q}}$)
- Drawing the line passing through q and the origin, thus meeting the Circle again at \bar{q}^{-1}
- Drawing the line passing through r and \bar{q}^{-1} thus meeting the Circle at $r * q$

The proof follows the exact same arguments as for $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ (see Lemma (3.3.3.2) and Corollary (3.3.3.3))

Remark 3.3.4.2. Note that all those constructions¹¹ involving hypercycles as well as Apollonian Circles can clearly be seen as generalization of Stereographic Projections. In fact, a stereographic projection can be seen as the map :

$$f : q \mapsto (q - 1)(q + 1)^{-1}, \quad (f \in \mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})) \quad (3.168)$$

It is actually more general than it, since it maps $\mathbb{RL} \cup \{\infty\}$ to the hypersphere $\mathbb{LL} \approx \mathbb{S}^3$, but in particular, if we restrict ourselves to a plane (say ℓ^\perp) in \mathbb{RL} , we find back the standard Stereographic Projection (but expressed in a much simpler way). [note (3.168) describes an element of order 4 in $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$]

Another useful such map is the following Involution:

$$\tilde{\cdot} : q \mapsto \tilde{q} := (1 - q)(1 + q)^{-1}, \quad (3.169)$$

Which is this time an element of $\pm\mathcal{R}$ (more precisely, of $\mathbf{Z}(\pm\mathcal{R}) = \pm\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$) and can be seen as a stereographic projection combined with a reflection, and that maps :

$$\tilde{\mathbb{V}} = \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q + \bar{q} = 0, q\bar{q} < 1\} \quad (3.170)$$

to

$$\mathbb{V} := \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q + \bar{q} > 0, q\bar{q} = 1\} \quad (3.171)$$

This can easily be seen by calculating the norm and real part of \tilde{q} for a given q in $\tilde{\mathbb{V}}$ or \mathbb{V} .

It is also possible to construct Stereographic Projections that privilege a direction by using maps of the form:

$$f_N : q \mapsto (q + N)(Nq + 1)^{-1}, \quad N \in \mathbb{L} \quad (3.172)$$

which this time belong to \mathcal{S} , and map $\mathbb{L} \setminus \{N\}$ to N^\perp

3.4 Conformal Maps on \mathbb{L}

In section 3.3.1, Proposition (3.3.1.3), we used Biquaternions to show that $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ is Isomorphic to $SO(3, 1)^+$. If instead of using $h \in \mathbb{C} \otimes_{\mathbb{R}} \mathbb{H}$, we had simply taken $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ -thus privileging a direction- we would have found that $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) \simeq PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_\ell) \simeq PGL(2, \mathbb{C})$; this is what we shall do here, thus re-proving the isomorphism between $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ and the Lorentz Group, as well as showing that those transformations are biconformal on \mathbb{L} , by exhibiting explicit isomorphisms with $PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_\ell)$. We will then have a quick look at some of the consequences of such results...

¹¹transformations of \mathcal{R} as well as \mathcal{S}

3.4.1 Stereographic Projections and $PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_\ell)$

At first sight, it may look tempting to directly define $PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_\ell)$ as the Subgroup of $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ formed by transformations whose coefficients are all in \mathbb{C}_ℓ , however, this would not be isomorphic to $PGL(2, \mathbb{C})$. Indeed, such a group would contain all the maps of the form $q \mapsto cq c^{-1}$, $c \in \mathbb{C}_\ell^\times$, and while such maps could just be "simplified" if we were working on \mathbb{C} , it is not the case when acting on \mathbb{H} , as those are elements of $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ (see **Chapter 2**, Section 2.4.3). The definition of $PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_\ell)$ will thus be slightly more subtle. We proceed in two steps, first defining $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright$.

Definition 3.4.1.1. *Let $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, then we define $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright$ as the subgroup of $\mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ formed by all transformations whose coefficients are all in \mathbb{C}_ℓ , i.e.*

$$\mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright := \{f : q \mapsto (aq + b)(cq + d)^{-1} \mid f \in \mathfrak{M} \wedge a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{C}_\ell\} \quad (3.173)$$

Then we obviously know that Quaternionic Möbius Transformations fixing 0 and ∞ are Linear, while if they also fix 1 they belong to $\text{Aut}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{H})$ (3D Rotations), and imposing that they fix some $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ leads us to $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) \simeq U(1)$. In other words, it is clear that -in the context of Möbius Transformations- $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ can be (re-)defined as the Subgroup of All Quaternionic Möbius Transformations **Fixing** all elements of $\mathbb{C}_\ell \cup \{\infty\}$. Now as $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright$ clearly **Stabilizes** $\mathbb{C}_\ell \cup \{\infty\}$, it follows that $\text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell)$ is obviously a normal subgroup of $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright$, allowing us to define:

Definition 3.4.1.2. *Let $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, then we define $PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_\ell)$ as the following Quotient Group:*

$$PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_\ell) := \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright / \text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) \quad (3.174)$$

Remark 3.4.1.3. *The above-defined Groups are easy to characterize, as it is clear that:*

$$PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_\ell) \simeq PGL(2, \mathbb{C}), \quad \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright \simeq PGL(2, \mathbb{C}) \times U(1) \quad (3.175)$$

Also, although unlike $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright$, the action of $PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_\ell)$ is not well-defined on the entire set $\mathbb{H} \cup \{\infty\}$, it clearly remains well-defined on $\mathbb{C}_\ell \cup \{\infty\}$, where it clearly represents the Group of Biconformal maps.

Now we will try to relate those groups to our previously-studied \mathcal{R} , $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ etc... For this, we will need a couple of more tools, which will be described in the following remark:

Remark 3.4.1.4. Let $N \in \mathbb{L}$, then we can define the following map:

$$f_N : q \mapsto (q + N)(Nq + 1)^{-1} \quad (3.176)$$

which belongs to $\mathcal{S} \cap \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_N}^\triangleright$ and -as previously mentioned- clearly maps $\mathbb{L} \setminus \{N\}$ to N^\perp (and so \mathbb{L} to $N^\perp \cup \{\infty\}$) and it is not difficult to check that it can be visualized as a stereographic projection. Note that the inverse of f_N is obviously given by

$$f_{-N} : q \mapsto (q - N)(-Nq + 1)^{-1} \quad (3.177)$$

Now we have all the tools we needed to proof the following

Proposition 3.4.1.5. Let $N \in \mathbb{L}$, then there exists isomorphisms $\mathcal{R} \simeq \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_N}^\triangleright$, which can be constructed from Möbius Transformations, and visualized as Stereographic Projections -and rotations-. In other words,

$$\exists f \in \mathfrak{M}^\triangleright : \forall g \in \mathcal{R}, f \circ g \circ f^{-1} \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_N}^\triangleright \quad (3.178)$$

$$\forall G \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_N}^\triangleright, f^{-1} \circ G \circ f \in \mathcal{R} \quad (3.179)$$

Proof. We set $\ell, M, N \in \mathbb{L}$ such that $\ell \perp N$ (i.e. $\ell N = -N\ell$) and $M := N\ell$ (e.g. $\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}$, orthonormal basis of $\mathbb{R}\mathbb{L}$), then let $g \in \mathcal{R}$, thus of the -canonical- form :

$$g : q \mapsto (aq - b)(bq + a)^{-1} \quad (3.180)$$

We will demonstrate that it is equivalent to some transformation of $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_N}^\triangleright$: in order to construct $f \circ g \circ f^{-1} \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_N}^\triangleright$, we start from \mathbb{C}_N , then use the map $q \mapsto q\ell$ to go to $\mathbb{C}_N\ell = N^\perp$, from which we can use f_{-N} as in Remark (3.4.1.4), then -as we are now in \mathbb{L} - we apply g , after what we come back to \mathbb{C}_N with f_N and $q \mapsto -q\ell$ to get the corresponding transformation. In terms of matrices, this gives:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \ell \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & N \\ N & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a & -b \\ b & a \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -N \\ -N & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{\ell} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.181)$$

which after calculus should give:

$$\begin{pmatrix} ((a - NaN) + (bN + Nb)) & ((aN - Na) + (b + NbN))\ell \\ \ell((Na - aN) + (b + NbN)) & \ell((bN + Nb) - (a - NaN))\ell \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.182)$$

Where it is clear that N commutes with anything of the form $q - NqN$ as well as $qN + Nq$ (i.e. equivalently, those are in \mathbb{C}_N), while anticommuting

with expressions of the form¹² $Nq - qN$ or $q + NqN$ (i.e. $\in N^\perp$), but also with $\ell \in N^\perp$, i.e. (3.182) belongs to $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_N}^\triangleright$.

Note that conversely, for a map $q \mapsto (Aq + B)(Cq + D)^{-1}$, $A, B, C, D \in \mathbb{C}_N$, thus belonging to $\mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_N}^\triangleright$, we can get back to a map of the form $q \mapsto (aq - b)(bq + a)^{-1}$ with

$$a = A - BN\ell + \overline{C}N\ell + \overline{D} \quad (3.183)$$

$$b = -AN - B\ell - \overline{C}\ell + \overline{D}N \quad (3.184)$$

□

Corollary 3.4.1.6. *Transformations of \mathcal{R} , and in particular -as their name indicates- Transformations of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ are all **Biconformal** on \mathbb{L} , while any biconformal transformation of \mathbb{L} can be represented by some element of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ (given the fact that $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$ **Fixes** all points of \mathbb{L}). It is also clear now that the extension $\pm\mathcal{R}$ contains Anticonformal maps as well.*

Proof. Trivial from Proposition (3.4.1.5), as the isomorphism we constructed was obtained from Stereographic Projections and rotations, while the action of $PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_N)$ is obviously conformal on $\mathbb{C}_N \cup \{\infty\}$ which is mapped to \mathbb{L} . □

Remark 3.4.1.7. *It is easy to see -and even calculate explicitly- from Equations (3.182) as well as (3.183) and (3.184) that the isomorphism we described will map elements of $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$ to elements of $\text{Gal}_{\delta_N}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_N)$. In other words, for any given $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$, we always have the following correspondence:*

$$\mathcal{R} \simeq \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright \simeq PGL(2, \mathbb{C}) \times U(1) \simeq SO(3, 1)^+ \times U(1) \quad (3.185)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R}) \simeq \text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) \triangleleft \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright, \quad \text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) \simeq U(1) \quad (3.186)$$

$$\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) \simeq \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright / \text{Gal}_{\delta_\ell}(\mathbb{H}/\mathbb{C}_\ell) = PGL(2, \mathbb{C}_\ell) \simeq PGL(2, \mathbb{C}) \simeq SO(3, 1)^+ \quad (3.187)$$

Remark 3.4.1.8. *Given the fact that $PGL(2, \mathbb{C}) \simeq SO(3, 1)^+$, Proposition (3.4.1.5) provides an alternative proof of the isomorphism between $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ and the Lorentz Group, compared to the one we gave earlier using Biquaternions -see Proposition (3.3.1.3)-*

Remark 3.4.1.9. *Note than looking for an isomorphism, the expression can be considerably simplified by choosing appropriate ℓ, M, N (e.g.: taking $N \in a^\perp \cap b^\perp \dots$)*

¹²see definition of the derivative and projections in Chapter 2; in particular, Proposition (2.2.2.2)

3.4.2 Characterizing -and Redefining- \mathcal{R}

The goal of this subsection is to slightly improve the result we got in Corollary (3.4.1.6) and describe as accurately as possible $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}), \mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R}), \mathcal{R}, \pm\mathcal{R}$, leading to the conclusion that those Groups can be redefined as follows:

Definition 3.4.2.1 (Relativistic Subgroups).

- $\pm\mathcal{R}$ is The Group of **All** Quaternionic Möbius Transformations **Stabilizing**¹³ \mathbb{L}
- \mathcal{R} is The Group of **All** Quaternionic Möbius Transformations **Biconformal** on \mathbb{L}
- $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ is The Group of **All** Quaternionic Möbius Transformations **Stabilizing** $\mathbb{L}\mathbb{L}$ **and Biconformal** on \mathbb{L}
- $\mathbf{Z}(\mathcal{R})$ is the Group of **All** Quaternionic Möbius Transformations **Fixing** \mathbb{L}

(Reminding that $\mathbb{L}\mathbb{L} := \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q\bar{q} = 1\} = \mathbb{L} \cup \{q \in (\mathbb{H} \setminus \mathbb{L}) \cup \{\infty\} : \widehat{\mathfrak{R}}(q) = 0\}$, thus trivially stabilized by $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$)

Actually, most of these claims are quite trivial; the only detail that may remain to check -if one *wants to be careful*- is that **All** possible Quaternionic Möbius Transformations stabilizing \mathbb{L} will be in $\pm\mathcal{R}$ (in particular, their action will be either conformal or anticonformal on \mathbb{L}). This is what we shall check here.

Remark 3.4.2.2. Thanks to our isomorphism(s) $\mathcal{R} \simeq \mathfrak{M}^\triangleright \mathbb{C}_\ell$, proving that any Quaternionic Möbius Transformation that stabilizes the sphere \mathbb{L} is either conformal or anticonformal is equivalent to proving the same claim¹⁴ about some \mathbb{C}_ℓ instead of \mathbb{L} .

We shall show the following result:

Proposition 3.4.2.3. Let $f \in \mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ thus of the -canonical- form

$$f : q \mapsto (aq + b)(cq + d)^{-1}, \quad a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{H} \quad (3.188)$$

If f stabilizes some subfield \mathbb{C}_ℓ , then either $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$, in which case $f \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright$ and is thus conformal on \mathbb{C}_ℓ , or $a, b, c, d \in \ell^\perp$, in which case the transformation is anticonformal on \mathbb{C}_ℓ .

¹³reminding that I use the terminology : "stabilize L " = "send elements of \mathbb{L} to (a priori other) elements of \mathbb{L} " while "FIX \mathbb{L} " = "send each $\ell \in \mathbb{L}$ to ℓ itself"

¹⁴i.e. any Quaternionic Möbius Transformation that stabilizes a subfield \mathbb{C}_ℓ is either conformal or anticonformal on it

Before proving this, we will treat a particular case via the following Lemma:

Lemma 3.4.2.4. *Let $g \in \mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ thus of the -canonical- form*

$$g : q \mapsto (aq + b)(cq + d)^{-1}, \quad a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{H} \quad (3.189)$$

Now, we further suppose that $0 \in \{a, b, c, d\}$. Then, if g stabilizes some subfield \mathbb{C}_ℓ , either $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$, in which case $g \in \mathfrak{M}_{\mathbb{C}_\ell}^\triangleright$ and is thus conformal on \mathbb{C}_ℓ , or $a, b, c, d \in \ell^\perp$, in which case the transformation is anticonformal on \mathbb{C}_ℓ .

Proof. We start by assuming

$$\forall z \in \mathbb{C}_\ell, \quad (az + b)(cz + d)^{-1} \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \quad (3.190)$$

then, this condition is clearly equivalent (by multiplying by a squared norm) to

$$\forall z \in \mathbb{C}_\ell, \quad (az + b)(\bar{z}\bar{c} + \bar{d}) \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \quad (3.191)$$

i.e.

$$\forall z \in \mathbb{C}_\ell, \quad a\bar{c}z\bar{z} + az\bar{d} + b\bar{z}\bar{c} + b\bar{d} \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \quad (3.192)$$

from which we deduce, by evaluating at $0, 1, \ell$, and around ∞ (and using the fact that \mathbb{C}_ℓ is a field):

$$b\bar{d} \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \quad (3.193)$$

$$a\bar{c} \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \quad (3.194)$$

$$(\ell a + a\ell)\bar{d} + (\ell b - b\ell)\bar{c} \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \quad (3.195)$$

$$(\ell a - a\ell)\bar{d} + (\ell b + b\ell)\bar{c} \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \quad (3.196)$$

also, it is clear that

$$(a, b), (c, d), (a, c), (b, d) \neq (0, 0) \quad (3.197)$$

are necessary conditions in order to have a bijection. I will now just prove the **Case in which $a = 0$** , as it is easy to check that the same argument can be reused to prove the cases $b = 0, c = 0$, and $d = 0$ (but treating those cases are actually not even necessary for the proof of Proposition (3.4.2.3)).

Suppose $a = 0$, then (3.195) and (3.196) become :

$$(\ell b - b\ell)\bar{c} \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \quad (3.198)$$

$$(\ell b + b\ell)\bar{c} \in \mathbb{C}_\ell \quad (3.199)$$

Then (3.197) implies that at least one of those two expressions should be nonzero. Now¹⁵ if (3.199) is nonzero, then c is in \mathbb{C}_ℓ , but then in order not to contradict (3.198) it is required that $lb - bl = 0$ (otherwise, the expression in (3.198) would be in ℓ^\perp), i.e. this implies $b \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$, but then by (3.193), $d \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$. i.e. $a = 0$, $b, c, d \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$ and so the map is conformal. Now on the other hand, if the expression in (3.198), is nonzero, then $c \in \ell^\perp$, but then, in order not to contradict (3.199), it is required that $lb + bl = 0$, in other words, $b \in \ell^\perp$ and by (3.193) so is d . Thus we have $a = 0$, $b, c, d \in \ell^\perp$ and the map is anticonformal. □

Now we can proof the General Case:

*Proof of **Proposition 3.4.2.3**.* As the case in which one of the coefficients is zero is treated by Lemma (3.4.2.4), we can take $f \in \mathfrak{M}^\triangleright$ of the form

$$f : q \mapsto (aq + b)(cq + d)^{-1} \quad \mathbf{a, b, c, d \neq 0} \quad (3.200)$$

In this case, we can just write f in the following form (see \mathfrak{M}^\triangle):

$$f(q) = ac^{-1} + (b - ac^{-1}d)(cq + d)^{-1} = ac^{-1} + g(q) \quad (3.201)$$

Then ac^{-1} should clearly be in \mathbb{C}_ℓ as it is the image of ∞ , thus f sends \mathbb{C}_ℓ to \mathbb{C}_ℓ if and only if g does so, but g has a zero coefficient, thus -by Lemma (3.4.2.4)- c and d should be either in \mathbb{C}_ℓ , or in ℓ^\perp , and by equations (3.193) and (3.194), the same can be said about a and b , thus the general case is proved, and by the previous isomorphism, we can see that $\pm\mathcal{R}$ is *exactly* the subgroup of \mathfrak{M} of transformations that stabilize \mathbb{L} ... □

3.4.3 Remarks on Conformity and Fixed Points

We have just seen that transformations of \mathcal{R} , and in particular $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ do not only stabilize \mathbb{L} , but are also Biconformal on it. One may now be interested in Characterizing Fixed Points (on \mathbb{L}). This can of course easily be achieved by using the isomorphism described in Proposition (3.4.1.5), and this may even be considerably simplified by Choosing appropriate coordinates, such as taking $N \in a^\perp \cap b^\perp$, i.e. $N \sim ab - ba$, where a and b are the coefficients of the map $f : q \mapsto (aq - b)(bq + a)^{-1}$. However, although I will not be exploring this more in-depth (in this work), I remain convinced that it should be possible

¹⁵(reminding from Chapter 2 that we should have $lq - ql \in \ell^\perp$, $lq + ql \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$, and that the product of two elements of ℓ^\perp gives an element of \mathbb{C}_ℓ while the product of an element of \mathbb{C}_ℓ with an element of ℓ^\perp gives an element of ℓ^\perp)

to exploit the structure of Quaternions in order to characterize those in a more elegant way, without requiring the use of the Isomorphism. I will try to briefly give some hints/suggest some ideas in the following example:

Example 3.4.3.1. *Let $f \in \text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ of the -canonical- form $f : q \mapsto (aq - b)(bq + a)^{-1}$, and let ℓ_1, ℓ_2 be its fixed points on \mathbb{L} then it is at least easy to determine the "direction" of $\ell_1 + \ell_2$. Indeed, we may assume without loss of generality that $ab - ba \neq 0$ (otherwise it is trivial to determine the fixed points -which are $\pm \ell$, where $a, b \in \mathbb{C}_\ell$ -), it is then not difficult to see that $\ell_1 + \ell_2 \sim ab - ba$ (i.e. $= \lambda(ab - ba)$ for some $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^\times$), in other words, $\ell_1 + \ell_2$ is orthogonal to A and B , with $A := \frac{a-\bar{a}}{2}, B := \frac{b-\bar{b}}{2}$. Now in the same way, if one could -in an easy way- characterize the Product $\ell_1\ell_2$ (or equivalently the commutator $\ell_1\ell_2 - \ell_2\ell_1$), it would then be possible to fully determine the fixed points Geometrically, in an elegant way, hopefully avoiding the explicit use of square roots (they could implicitly appear when "taking the norm" $q \mapsto |q|$). One can also note further properties, as solving $f(\ell) = \ell$ for the above-defined f is clearly equivalent to solving*

$$a\ell - \ell a = b + \ell b\ell \quad (3.202)$$

(or in terms of derivatives $\delta_\ell : a' + b'' = 0$) while (left -or right-) multiplying by ℓ also gives:

$$a + \ell a\ell = -(b\ell - \ell b) \quad (3.203)$$

i.e. the equation exhibits the symmetry:

$$a \mapsto b, \quad b \mapsto -a \quad (3.204)$$

Furthermore, the two terms are linear in a or b and it is clear that any $X, Y \in \mathbb{R}$ will satisfy

$$X\ell - \ell X = 0 = Y + \ell Y\ell \quad (3.205)$$

in other words (as already suggested by the "derivative form") the fixed points of f will not depend on the real parts of a and b , in particular, one can choose to work with A and B (as above defined : respective imaginary parts of a and b) or with elements of \mathbb{RL} in general. It would then be tempting to define a kind of "quasi-dual" on the plane $(ab - ba)^\perp$ (= generated as a \mathbb{R} -Vector space by A and B -a priori Not orthonormal however-) i.e. associating to each v some v^* as follows:

$$v =: sA + tB, \quad s, t \in \mathbb{R} \quad (3.206)$$

$$v^* := sB - tA \quad (3.207)$$

(and so $v^{**} = -v$) then we have in general that

$$v\ell - \ell v = v^* + \ell v^* \ell \quad (3.208)$$

Which works for any $v \in (ab-ba)^\perp$, and in particular for $\ell_1 - \ell_2$ and $\frac{\ell_1\ell_2 - \ell_2\ell_1}{2}$, as applying the relations with $\ell = \ell_1$ and $\ell = \ell_2$ allows us to find:

$$(\ell_1 - \ell_2)^* = \frac{\ell_1\ell_2 - \ell_2\ell_1}{2} \quad (3.209)$$

$$\left(\frac{\ell_1\ell_2 - \ell_2\ell_1}{2}\right)^* = -(\ell_1 - \ell_2) \quad (3.210)$$

Also we note the following invariant:

$$\forall v \in (ab-ba)^\perp, \quad \frac{vv^* - v^*v}{v^2 + (v^*)^2} = \frac{AB - BA}{A^2 + B^2} \quad (3.211)$$

as developing for $v = sA + tB$ will make a factor $(s^2 + t^2)$ appear in both numerator and denominator, that will cancel each other...

I will now end this subsection with two other remarks about features I find may potentially be interesting, but which I will unfortunately not be exploring further in this work:

Remark 3.4.3.2. Using -for instance- the isomorphism from Proposition (3.4.1.5), it is possible to "import Rational Functions", meaning define a general class of -"algebraic"- Transformations on \mathbb{H} whose restriction to \mathbb{L} would be conformal; i.e. defining a "new class" of "Regular Functions" on \mathbb{H} . Although I have not explored that feature much in-depth yet, it would seem that determining absorbing or repelling points should be related to the following operator :

$$\mathcal{D} := \frac{-1}{2} (\partial_t + i\partial_x + j\partial_y + k\partial_z) \quad (3.212)$$

Remark 3.4.3.3. As seen in the previous Remark (3.4.3.2) it is possible to define -in a "natural way"- (algebraic) functions on \mathbb{H} , whose restriction to the sphere of square roots of -1 (i.e. \mathbb{L}) is conformal. Also, on $\mathbb{C} \otimes_{\mathbb{R}} \mathbb{C}$, it is possible to define a "unit torus". I would thus be tempted to naively ask the following question, which I have not thought much about yet:

-Would it then be possible to define in a "not too artificial way", maps

$$\mathbb{C} \otimes_{\mathbb{R}} \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{H} \quad (3.213)$$

which would send the unit torus $\mathbb{T} \subseteq \mathbb{C} \otimes_{\mathbb{R}} \mathbb{C}$ to the sphere $\mathbb{L} \subseteq \mathbb{H}$, such that the restriction to \mathbb{T} behave exactly like an Elliptic Function¹⁶ ?..

¹⁶Meromorphic & Doubly Periodic

3.4.4 Natural Connections with Relativistic Physics

Throughout this Chapter, the study of general Quaternionic Möbius Transformations led us to define several Mathematical Objects that seem to be naturally connected with Relativistic Physics. In particular, we have got:

- a Group isomorphic to $SO(3, 1)^+ : \text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$
- a 4-Dimensional space on which that Group can act : $\mathbb{H} \cup \{\infty\}$ (or one of its subspaces, e.g.: $\mathbb{H}^+ := \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q + \bar{q} > 0\}$)
- a quantity that stays invariant under that Group : $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}}$

In other words, all the -main- ingredients one would need in order to start doing Relativistic Physics. Although this has always been my main motivation for studying Quaternions, I will not have the opportunity to expose much of it in this work; however, I will still try to provide a quick overview of how we could potentially use our previously-defined "Quaternionic Tools" to do a bit of Physics.

The isomorphism between the Restricted Lorentz Group $SO(3, 1)^+$ and $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$, the Group of all Möbius Transformations of $\mathbb{H} \cup \{\infty\}$ that stabilize \mathbb{L} and are Biconformal on \mathbb{L} , has already been established, and one could work with $\pm \text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ if willing to include time-reversal... Despite the Groups being isomorphic to each other, their action on $\mathbb{R}^4 \approx \mathbb{H}$ is very different (e.g.: our *boosts* -see Definition (3.1.2.6)- are not even "Linear"), the next thing will then be to "replace" the "four-vectors" by other "Quaternionic Quantities", whose Physical Interpretation may differ a lot from the usual "four-vectors", but still providing a formulation of Special Relativity "isomorphic" to the standard one. Obviously, we are going to work on a (not necessarily "Proper") subset of $\mathbb{H} \cup \{\infty\}$: an example which I find may be interesting would be

$$\mathbb{H}^+ := \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q + \bar{q} > 0\} \quad (3.214)$$

not only for its similarity to *Poincaré's Upper Half-Plane*, but mainly for many other reasons, as it automatically excludes \mathbb{L} , as well as many "Degenerate" cases seen in **Section 3.3.3**, and the way it combines with $\widehat{\mathfrak{R}} : q \mapsto \frac{q\bar{q}-1}{q+\bar{q}}$, as we see that

$$\widehat{\mathfrak{R}} : \mathbb{H}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (3.215)$$

and in particular

$$\widehat{\mathfrak{R}} : \mathbb{R}^{>0} \simeq \mathbb{R} \quad (3.216)$$

The idea is then to start defining quantities at Rest. Those will obviously be represented by points lying in a subset of $\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$, e.g. if the space we chose

to work with is \mathbb{H}^+ , then quantities at Rest will obviously be represented by points of $\mathbb{R}^{>0}$. In other words, we will associate to each "standard four-vector at Rest" one of our new quantities, by constructing an isomorphism between our subset of $\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}$ (in our example, $\mathbb{R}^{>0}$) and the set of four-vectors representing quantities "at rest" (typically \mathbb{R}). Of course, the morphisms we may find should not be unique, but some will appear to be "much more appropriate" than other ones... Once the morphism between quantities at Rest is established, it just suffices to apply **boosts** to parametrize the entire space, thus getting the "full isomorphism". Geometrically, while in the standard representation, space-time would be parametrized by Hyperbolas (Hyperboloids), ours will rather be parametrized by Apollonian Circles (Hyperspheres). Such Morphisms will be illustrated in the following examples:

Example 3.4.4.1. *The picture below illustrates the Geometric Construction of the Isomorphism between the "four-velocities" (hyperbola) and our corresponding quantities (circle).*

One may also seek to "import" other kinds of four-vectors (e.g. four-momentum). Several morphisms may a priori be possible...

Example 3.4.4.2. *It is for instance possible to represent objects with (rest) mass $m \geq 1$ by Quaternionic Quantities q with $|q| \leq 1$ and $q + \bar{q} > 0$.*

The (rest) mass then corresponds to the radius of the $\mathbf{E}_{\mathcal{R}}$ - Type Apollonian Circle (blue), while the energy can be seen as the center of the $\mathbf{H}_{\mathcal{I}}$ - Type Apollonian Circle (green), with

$$E = \frac{q\bar{q} + 1}{q + \bar{q}} \quad (3.217)$$

Also, the momentum (that I write¹⁷ \wp) corresponds to the tangent (slope) and is given by:

$$\wp = \frac{q - \bar{q}}{q + \bar{q}} \quad (3.218)$$

Reminding that with such a representation, Boosts -and more generally, transformations of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L}) \simeq SO(3,1)^+$ - can be constructed by just drawing one "Circle" and two Lines, as described in **Section 3.3.3**.

¹⁷((which of course in this context, has nothing to do with the "Weierstrass \wp -function"...))

Note that in Example (3.4.4.2), although m , E and φ could be represented via associated objects -such as the previously-defined $\hat{\mathfrak{R}}_{\mathcal{R}}$, $\hat{\mathfrak{R}}_{\mathcal{I}}$ etc- it seems a priori difficult to directly give a Physical meaning to q . However, as we will see in the following example, there are cases in which our "Quaternionic Quantities" not only do have a clear Physical meaning, but are also much more intuitive than their "four-vector counterpart"! It is the case of Velocity.

Example 3.4.4.3. *Velocity can be expressed in a very simple way: as a*

unitary Quaternion of positive¹⁸ real part,

$$v \in \mathbb{V} = \{q \in \mathbb{H} : q\bar{q} = 1 \wedge q + \bar{q} > 0\} \quad (3.219)$$

The Imaginary part represents the "actual speed" (unlike "four-velocity"!) while the Real part represents the "flow of time" (time Dilation). One can visualize it as: "everything moves at the same constant speed in Space-Time; only the 'Direction' (Space vs Time) may change", e.g. (extreme cases) a Photon will only "move in Space", while an object at Rest will "only move in Time"... This representation makes it much more intuitive than the traditional four-velocity and makes the twin paradox look trivial (the "paths in Space-Time" are parametrized by arclength). Also the velocity addition formula becomes much simpler: it has a natural geometric interpretation (can be constructed with "a stereographic projection combined with a standard boost of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ ")

and can thus be written as :

$$f_b(q) = (b + q)(1 - bq)^{-1}, \quad b = \frac{1 + v}{1 - v} \quad (3.220)$$

or reformulated in many other ways, as for instance :

$$v, q \in \mathbb{V}, \quad v \star q = (1 + v)^{-1}(v + q + vq - 1)(v + q - vq + 1)^{-1}(1 + v) \quad (3.221)$$

¹⁸usually strictly positive; the real part is 0 iff $v \in \mathbb{L}$, i.e. moves at light-speed

It plays the same role as Einstein's velocity-addition formula+dilation of time, which **without** Quaternions would be formulated in the following way:

$$\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^3 : \|\mathbf{v}_1\|, \|\mathbf{v}_2\| < c$$

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{v}_1 \oplus_{\mathbb{R}^3} \mathbf{v}_2 = \frac{\langle \mathbf{v}_1 | \mathbf{v}_2 \rangle \mathbf{v}_1 / \|\mathbf{v}_1\|^2 + \mathbf{v}_1 + \sqrt{1 - \|\mathbf{v}_1\|^2 / c^2} (\mathbf{v}_2 - \langle \mathbf{v}_1 | \mathbf{v}_2 \rangle \mathbf{v}_1 / \|\mathbf{v}_1\|^2)}{1 + \langle \mathbf{v}_1 | \mathbf{v}_2 \rangle / c^2} \\ \gamma(v_1 \oplus_{\mathbb{R}^3} v_2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \|\mathbf{v}_1 \oplus_{\mathbb{R}^3} \mathbf{v}_2\|^2 / c^2}} \end{cases} \quad (3.222)$$

Remark 3.4.4.4. Note that the Geometric Method for adding velocities, described in Example (3.4.4.3) also works for the "non-relativistic Linear Approximation" as the picture below illustrates:

Now coming back to the relativistic case -and representing velocities as in Example (3.4.4.3)- it is trivial to characterize boosts $\mathbf{b} : q \mapsto (q + \beta)(1 - \beta q)^{-1}$, as the associated velocity v is simply given by $\mathbf{b}(1) = \frac{1 + \beta}{1 - \beta}$, and so $\beta = \frac{v - 1}{v + 1}$ ("Stereographic Projection")

Conclusion

As we have seen from Pontryagin's Theorem, Quaternions form a completely Unique Mathematical Structure, as they can be, amongst others, defined as The Most General Connected Locally Compact Division Ring -with a non-trivial Topology- as well as The Only One not to be commutative. The combination of the very strong (Topological) Field Structure with the very subtle Noncommutativity creates a very rich structure, which not only has *about all the "nice" properties one could dream of* in order to do Algebra or Analysis, but also possesses its own special features, allowing to do Geometry (not only Euclidean, but also Elliptic or Hyperbolic) in a very elegant way, always showing natural links between the Algebraic Structure (e.g. in one of the cases we explored, basic Differential Algebra) and the Geometrical Interpretation. Also, this such Unique Mathematical Structure is -as its name indicates- four-dimensional: exactly like Space-Time; what some people seem to consider as a "lucky coincidence"... It also seems to exhibit at first sight other links with Special Relativity, and the intuition is confirmed once we study Quaternionic Möbius Transformations. Indeed, when doing so, we see arise -amongst others- a very special subgroup -which we name $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ -, whose action on \mathbb{L} , the sphere of square roots of -1 , is Biconformal, and which is isomorphic to $SO(3,1)^+$: the Lorentz Group. Despite acting on a four-dimensional space, transformations of $\text{Aut}(\mathbb{L})$ can easily be visualized/constructed by Compass-and-Straightedge, by just drawing an Apollonian Circle and two lines. Although we did not explore this feature more in-depth, it seems to appear that this structure could potentially be used to do Special Relativity, in a sometimes much more intuitive, elegant, and simpler way, as shown in some examples, such as Velocity-Addition...

In sum, I strongly believe that Quaternions have a lot of potential and should be given more attention, not only from Mathematicians, but also from Physicists.

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